

diversity revolution

knowledge collection

diversity revolution

knowledge collection

**DIVERSITY REVOLUTION
THE KNOWLEDGE COLLECTION**

CREATED BY:

CEPORA – Center for Positive Youth
Development (Serbia)
Institute for Educational Research (Serbia)
Associazione Uniamoci (Italy)
Scuola elementare – Osnovna.sola Dante
Alighieri Isola (Slovenia)

EDITORS:

Branislava Popović-Ćitić
Lidija Bukvić
Marija Trajković

**EXPERTS INCLUDED IN THE CREATION OF
THE PUBLICATION:**

Marija Trajković, Marina Kovačević-Lepojević,
Milica Kovačević, Eleonora Di Liberto, Giulia
Messina, Tea Radojković, Anja Palčič

The publication was created within the project

**DIVERSITY REVOLUTION:
From value to practice**

Cover page designed by: Anica Novak
Design of the publication: Anica Novak

*Funded by the European Union. Views and
opinions expressed are however those of the
author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect
those of the European Union or the European
Education and Culture Executive Agency
(EACEA). Neither the European Union nor
EACEA can be held responsible for them.*

Contents

Editors note	7
I - Diversity in contemporary science	9
II - Diversity in contemporary legal frameworks: EU level	53
III - Instead of a conclusion: Minimum standards for diversity fostering in practice	79
Appendix – Current national legislation on diversity in Serbia, Italy and Slovenia	83

Editors note

Diversity is recognized as a highly important **value** in the youth field (and much wider) which is supposed to be respected and incorporated in the work of all institutions and organisations that interact with young people. High importance of addressing diversity as an opportunity for learning and not for exclusion and conflict is recognized all throughout EU (starting from the EU motto “United in diversity” and covered in a wide range of EU Strategies). As a result of years of efforts, a wide variety of available instruments, toolkits, guidebooks, articles tackling this topic is available to whomever is interested in diversity (usually alongside inclusion and/or cultural sensitivity), and legislative frameworks of most countries have diversity incorporated in some form as an important value in their strategies regarding youth and systems young people interfere with the most (such as education and social protection). But still, in practice, diversity is respected and „implemented“ partially.

There are three elements that are relevant and intertwined when it comes to **fostering diversity on an organisational level** (by an CSO organisation, school, social protection institution, or any other organisational unit). These are the context (organisational culture), relationship (climate) and individual (competences) level. Some institutions (such as schools) have the organisational culture (regulations, procedures, practices) that is in place in a way that supports diversity fostering. But when the staff doesn't have their competences strengthened enough, the overall climate is not supportive and young people in that facility do not feel the benefits of the positive culture. On the other hand, when youth organisations have highly competence individuals as their staff, that supports the positive climate in their activities, but if the organisational culture is missing, the moment there is a staff change, the quality of activities decreases automatically. We do have good practice examples where all three elements are developed and fostered continually, but these examples are more exceptions than the rule. All participating countries in the consortium (Serbia, Italy, Slovenia), as well as most of others in the region and even in the EU, even with all their current efforts, are facing prevalent issues of social exclusion, discrimination and violence towards those who are marked as different in the dominant culture, and are motivated to empower their young people to learn how to see diversity as an opportunity and not as an obstacle. There is a joint need for free, complete and effective instruments that can support those organisations/institutions interested in fostering diversity on all levels, but that is also needed for those organizations who state they are not interested in diversity at all, in order to spread the importance and the opportunities of it, showing how it is not a waste of time and resources but it provides a lot of benefit from the point of view of organisational and program success.

Throughout the project **“Diversity Revolution: From value to practice”** (ref.no. 2021-1-RS01-KA220-YOU-000029459), implemented by 4 organisations – CEPORA – Center for Positive Youth Development (Serbia), Institute for Educational Research (Serbia), Associazione Uniamoci (Italy) and Scuola elementare – Osnovna sola Dante Alighieri Isola (Slovenia), we want to support organisations and institutions enhance their fostering of diversity in practice, by helping them view this issue

holistically, „find their way“ through possibilities offered to them, so they can navigate towards those enhancement resources that are relevant for their specific cultural/climate/competences needs.

The publication **Diversity Revolution: The knowledge collection** summarizes the current knowledge relevant for fostering diversity, filled with information that will help professionals that work with youth in various fields raise their knowledge and understanding of diversity topic. The collection was created through analysis of findings based on scientific papers regarding diversity fostering on the organisational level, analysis of EU and national level non-formal resources regarding diversity, tailoring of “minimum standards” for diversity sensitive organisations and analysis of relevant current EU and national strategies, laws and procedures regarding diversity fostering and relevant for the 3 systems that are in contact with youth the most (youth work, education and social work).

Understanding new views on diversity and understanding the complementary effects of improving organisations culture, climate and competences of its staff regarding fostering diversity is of curtail importance of transferring our efforts of viewing diversity as a strength from an idea to practice.

The editors

diversity in contemporary science

Marina Kovačević-Lepojević
Marija Trajković

Introduction

In general, **diversity** can be described as the presence of individual differences that are innate or acquired through socialization. In addition to structural diversity (age, gender, socio-economic inequalities), other diversity factors recognized in scientific literature are cultural origin, national-ethno-cultural (multiple) affiliation, cultural values, religion, languages, physical conditions and individual abilities. Modern researchers in the US are referring to the so-called "Big 8" as the central category for addressing diversity: race/ethnicity, gender, nationality, class/socio-economic status, age, gender orientation, mental/physical abilities and religion. Finding the right balance between equality (sameness in treatment) and fairness (educational justice) shifts the social response from guaranteeing formal rights (e.g. in minority languages) to a better understanding of the needs of marginalized groups. Diversity is more than just a set of categories. It extends to the principles of inclusion, recognition and appreciation of diversity and the ability to participate equally in society. Diversity is usually linked to one's cultural affiliation. The term "culture" includes not only culture related to race, ethnicity, and origin, but also culture shared by people who share certain common characteristics (e.g. beliefs, shared experiences, and ways of being in the world).

Understanding **culture** is a very complex issue, resulting in different definitions, viewpoints and understandings. According to one of the understandings of culture, objective and subjective culture can be distinguished. **Objective culture** refers to visible, recognizable behaviors or artifacts that are culturally learned and can be identified by persons outside that cultural group, while **subjective culture** refers to internalized attitudes and opinions held by members of a cultural group, which are much more difficult to identify than by other individuals who do not belong to a specific cultural group. This understanding of culture raises awareness of the need to shift the focus from objective culture to subjective culture, in order to better understand the cultural characteristics of individuals, their cultural value and the specifics of the learning style. In other words, culture includes human values, language, religion, ideals, artistic expressions, patterns of social and interpersonal relationships, and ways of perceiving, behaving and thinking. The way we feel, think, react and behave reflects our cultural background, which indicates that all people have their own culture.

Diversity is highlighted as a very important **value**, especially in institutions that work directly or come into contact with children and young people, such as institutions within the educational system, social care or the youth work sector. In the scientific literature, various elements of the functioning of these institutions are identified, which are of key importance for the appreciation of diversity, and can be recognized at the level of organizational culture, mutual relations between employees, employees and young people, as well as their individual capacities and resources to see diversity as a value. For example, action plans for diversity, strategic plans and other **policy** documents are considered key mechanisms for promoting and formally influencing equality, diversity and inclusion.

In the light of current and future reality, the need to prepare each individual for a competent life and functioning in a multicultural and intercultural world becomes an essential aspect of the functioning of institutions at the global level. That is why it is often pointed out that in addition to action at the individual level, action on institutional structures and procedures is needed. For example, there must be a law to combat all manifestations of discrimination, hatred and intolerance, or public information campaigns on the social and personal consequences of intolerance and hatred must be implemented. All staff working in government bodies, public services and educational and civil society organizations should be trained in diversity and measures to promote intercultural dialogue, interaction and exchange both in the workplace and in the community. Despite interest in and commitment to equality, diversity, and inclusion, there are still significant variations in whether and how institutions define, understand, and respond to issues related to these constructs.

Diversity theoretical framework

An inclusive and supportive environment that fosters diversity in practice is based on several contemporary theoretical approaches and models: Bioecological Theory of Human Development; Relational Developmental System Perspective; Strength-based approach; The optimal distinctiveness model; Intergroup contact theory; Theory of Generative Interactions; Constrict theory; Socioemotional learning; Prosocial classroom model; Whole-school approach; Whole system approach, etc. Understanding the theoretical basis of diversity fostering allows us to frame our actions in scientific lines.

The bioecological model of human development represents a dynamic theoretical system for researching development over time while recognizing the complexity of interactions between subjective and objective environmental factors. In the latest version of the model, the authors introduce the concept of proximal processes that represent the transfer of exchange which takes place in the relationship between the individual and other people, objects and symbols in the immediate environment. They state: that for the purpose of development the person must be involved in the activity; for the activity to be effective it must take place regularly over a long period; processes important for development do not take place only in one direction, a certain level of reciprocity is needed in order for the exchange to take place; proximal processes do not only refer to interaction with people, but also with objects and symbols; intensification of proximal processes with the development of students' capacities and expansion of the circle of persons with whom they interact with age. Competence and dysfunction are distinguished as outcomes of proximal processes. An ecological systems perspective provides a conceptual lens that enables multicultural workers in social humanities to view diverse clients in the context of their transactions within and adaptations to various environments. The ecological systems perspective gives attention not only the physical space or geographic location but also the broader sociopolitical context that shapes the mental, physical, and social functioning of diverse individuals.

The perspective of relational development systems is based on four components: change and relative plasticity; relationalism and integration of the organizational level; historical foundation and temporality; and the limits of generalization, diversity, and individual differences. The change and relative plasticity of developmental systems emphasizes the focus on developmental change, where the potential for change exists. This focus is necessitated by the belief that the potential for change exists across the lifespan and the multiple levels of organization that make up the human ecology. These levels range from biological, through individual/psychological and proximal social relationships (eg, involving dyadic relationships, peer groups, and more), to the sociocultural macro level. Relational developmental systems theory goes beyond the simplistic division into sources of development in variables or processes related to nature and nurture; they see the multiple levels of organization that exist within the ecology of human development as part of an inextricably linked developmental system. All levels of organization within the development system are integrated with historical changes, where history as a level of organization, although continuously merged with all other levels, represents the broadest framework of the system. Something that at one historical moment is recognized as important for the relations between the levels of the system of human development at another moment may be completely insignificant. Individual differences inevitably result from the action of the developmental system, they shift the system in a way that further nurtures diversity, making individuals at the same time similar to other people and unique (like no other person).

The optimal distinctiveness model points to the two opposing needs of human beings for self-concept and social belonging. On the one hand, there is a need for assimilation and inclusion, and on the other for differentiation. As inclusiveness increases, the need for differentiation is activated and vice versa, as inclusiveness decreases, the need for differentiation decreases, but the need for belonging is activated. Competing needs thus keep each other in check, ensuring that interests at one level are not sacrificed for another. According to the optimal diversity model, two opposing motives produce the ability to socially identify with special groups that simultaneously satisfy both needs.

The main mechanism of the **Intergroup contact theory** is the development of a preference for persons or objects with greater exposure. Factors recognized as important for optimal contact when formulating the theory are: equal status, common goals, intergroup cooperation, authority support and clear rules are favorable, but not necessary conditions. With more intergroup contact, there is greater trust and interpersonal relationships. These contact effects concern not only ethnic groups, but also other groups such as homosexuals, the disabled and the mentally ill. Furthermore, these effects tend to generalize beyond the immediate outgroup members in the situation to the entire outgroup, other situations, and even other outgroups not involved in the contact. Also, the theory emphasizes the universality of the achieved effects - among peoples, genders and age groups. In order to look at new findings in the theory and research of intergroup contact, a meta-analysis was conducted in which 515 studies were processed and with more than 250,000 respondents, which showed that intergroup contact reduces prejudice. The main mediators of the effect are fundamentally affective:

reduced anxiety and empathy. Even indirect contact reduces prejudice – indirect contact through mass media. Some of the shortcomings of the theory concern, for example, the greater sense of deprivation of the minority population, which, with greater contact with the majority population, realizes how deprived it is, which has a positive side because, in this way, the capacity of minorities to fight for human rights increases. Research findings suggest that greater interethnic contact may foster greater segregation.

Generative Interactions Theory suggests that in order to facilitate inclusion, multiple types of exclusionary dynamics (self-segregation, fear of communication, stereotyping, and stigmatization) must be overcome through adaptive cognitive processing and skill development, and engagement in positive interactions must occur to facilitate inclusion created and sustained by contextually relevant sets of organizational practices. Organizational practices provide the following conditions for generative interactions: pursuing an important, shared organizational purpose, frequently mixing different members over long periods of time, allowing different groups to have equal status and insider status in contributing to success, and ensuring cooperative interdependence, interpersonal comfort and self-efficacy, equity for individuals and groups in the organization. Inclusion is shown as adaptive contact, contact that stimulates generativity for group members through continuous interaction that leads to the reduction of prejudices and the development of skills.

Constrict theory is based on the observation that greater ethnic diversity in a certain context does not result in more relationships, whether conflictual or friendly, but in general with fewer relationships. According to the constrictive theory, the distinction between minority and ethnic majority groups within the context is not relevant. Individuals withdraw, regardless of the group they belong to, which the author of the theory empirically confirmed at the community level. The research conducted by a group of authors testing the theory in the school context, in order to examine whether ethnic diversity brings fewer and less quality friendships among students in a sample of 85 secondary schools, confirmed that ethnic diversity generally brings less friendship and less attachment to friends. A more detailed analysis found that lower socioeconomic status, and not ethnic diversity, actually contributes to a lower number and quality of friendships. However, for the minority population of students, greater ethnic diversity brings more friends and greater attachment to friends, where in the context of the tendency for assimilation, students of minority (Turkish, Moroccan) ethnicity unite around the exchange of resources they need to better fit into the majority Flemish population. The constrictive theory was rejected at the school and community level in a sample of Dutch high school students.

Key factors for embracing diversity on the organizational level

Contemporary literature findings, focused on whole-organization level functioning, derived 3 key constructs that affect diversity fostering in practice. Those are organizational climate, organizational culture and cultural competences of organizations' personnel. The main focus of this knowledge collection is to provide managers and practitioners that work with young people in the sectors of education, youth work and social care with contemporary findings on how different elements of their organizations' culture, climate and staff competences should be organized in order to foster diversity in practice – to the fullest. Following chapters will focus on these 3 key constructs, providing you with findings from scientific literature from our 3 sectors of interest – youth work, education and social care. However, education has a lot more literature than the other two sectors, so this publication will try to support other forms of organizations to “take” for themselves lessons learned in the education setting (as the most researched context for diversity fostering).

The main idea is understanding the complexity of interactions that happen between the organisations' policies, governance, climate between all staff member and their youth users, and how all this affects diversity fostering in practice – in contact with diverse youth.

This approach is based on various ecosystem frameworks, emphasizing the idea of providing a holistic model of the complex network that affects every child and young person that encounters the institution/organisation. It emphasizes the need to acknowledge various factors from micro, meso, exo and macrosystems that co-exist and influence each other. Macrosystem implies a wider social, cultural and legislative context that shapes all other systems. The exosystem refers to the community context, that is, to building relationships with others in the community (other institutions/organizations, parents, other sectors, etc.). The meso-level refers to the institution/organization and the interactions that affect its structure, processes and practices, i.e. tradition, culture and ethos, values and ideology, authority and cooperation within the institution/organization. The micro level includes practices that directly affect young people, their development, and outcomes. It is precisely at this level that the competence of workers to respond adequately to the needs of young people comes to the fore.

Organizational culture that embraces diversity

Most of the work on defining organizational culture came from the business sector. In our fields, education has the most to say on this matter, so we will start the introduction to the construct of organizational culture in the social humanities field by introducing school culture.

Sociologists recognized the importance of school culture in the 30s of the 20th century. The origin of the use of the term "culture" to describe life in schools began

with Waller (1932), who noted that schools have their own identity, with complex rituals, a set of folk customs, traditions and moral codes. However, despite the general agreement on the importance of the culture of the institution, this construct is not easy to define, and there is an enormous number of different definitions, the number of which is continuously growing. Different authors agree that, at the end of the 20th century, there is no single universally accepted best definition of school culture. It seems that the biggest dilemma in the literature is the difference in defining culture and climate elements. It often happens that these terms are used interchangeably. Differences between climate and culture are highlighted in organizational studies, so that climate often refers to the behavioral aspect, that is, behavior, while culture is seen as the values and norms of a school or other form of organization.

When we sum up the literature on organizational culture, we can say that the culture of the institution/organization determines the correct way of behavior within it. It consists of shared beliefs and values established by leaders, then communicated and emphasized within the institution/organization, ultimately shaping employee perceptions, understandings, and behaviors. When the mentioned elements of the culture in the institution/organization are inconsistent or incongruent, things will not function adequately.

Lessons learned from youth work, education and social care literature:

◆ The **basic elements** of culture that fosters diversity include: a shared sense of purpose and vision; norms, values, beliefs and assumptions; rituals, traditions and ceremonies; history; people and relationships; architecture, artifacts and symbols. Each of these elements should reflect an appreciation of diversity. Culture influences and shapes the way educators, young people and other staff members think, behave and feel, and directs focus on what is important.

◆ The **characteristics** of a positive organizational culture are: shared mission and vision, collaborative culture, joint problem solving, continuous improvement. A positive organisational culture enhances motivation, efficiency and productivity, collegiality, communication, problem solving, innovation, commitment, energy, vitality, and trust among staff members, young people, and the community.

◆ Organisational culture should have an intercultural and inclusive **philosophy**, a positive view of diversity, high expectations for their users and their families, and a central principle related to community participation. An inclusive culture involves creating a safe, kind, collaborative and stimulating community where everyone is valued and which provides a foundation for all young people to achieve higher levels of achievement.

◆ Inclusive organisational culture is focused on the transformation of culture that increases **access** to all young people (not only inclusion of marginalized and vulnerable groups), improves the ability of organisational staff and users to accept

all young people, maximizes youth participation in various activities, improves the achievements of all young people involved. In organisations/institutions with an inclusive culture, there is some consensus among adults about the value of respecting differences and a commitment to offering all young people learning opportunities.

◆ An inclusive culture requires a **shared set of assumptions and beliefs** among policy makers and organisations/institutions staff that value differences, believe in collaboration, and are committed to all young people. When different elements of culture (beliefs, values, attitudes, expectations, ideas and behaviors) in an institution are inconsistent or incongruent things will not function adequately.

◆ **Organisations' leaders** have a key role in implementing inclusive policies and practices and especially in creating a culture that celebrates diversity. When leadership fails to do something proactive to enable equity and social justice, it often becomes an unwritten endorsement of inequality. It is for these reasons that organizational functioning researchers have long suggested that paying attention to culture is the most important aspect of leadership. There is considerable evidence in the literature to suggest that organisations' top management – principals/ directors/ leaders must first understand organisational culture in order to implement certain reforms. Successful leaders understand the critical role organizational culture plays in developing a successful organisation.

◆ Organisations' leaders have an obligation to create a safe and culturally sensitive organisational environment. This means that they influence the program, approach, organization of the institution (use of space, grouping of young people, etc.) and the development of cooperation with parents (if relevant) and the wider local community. For this reason, providing **professional development** of leaders in terms of improving their intercultural competence is the first important step in establishing positive leadership models for diversity in and among organisations/institutions.

◆ While top management (leaders) play an important role in setting the framework for a organisational culture that embraces diversity and promotes inclusion, the role of educators or other staff that work directly with youth is increasingly recognized as an essential aspect of successful improvement initiatives. A review of the literature shows that the **training of educators** and other relevant actors are important for the successful implementation of inclusion in different organisations and different sectors.

◆ Some authors use the term "comprehensive school reform" to describe the process of **"reculturing"** schools to make them more effective and inclusive. Key aspects of this reform include developing a culture of collaboration, using high-quality professional development to improve educator practice, and using strong leadership teams to support school improvement activities.

◆ Particular importance for the appreciation of diversity in the school environment is attached to the **curriculum**. There are usually three types of curricula that play

a role in fostering respect for cultural diversity, namely: formal curricula (followed by textbooks and curriculum guides issued mainly by government organizations) symbolic curriculum (pictures, symbols, rewards, celebrations and other artifacts displayed in the school); and social curriculum (knowledge, ideas, and impressions about different cultural groups portrayed in mass media).

◆ Therefore, young people need **teaching materials** that match their cultural background. These materials should improve young persons' self-concept, increase their interest in learning, and provide examples, vocabulary, and models related to their cultural backgrounds. Also, the main focus of any formal or non-formal learning curriculum should be on analytical and critical thinking skills, and materials, activities, and experiences should be authentic and multidimensional to help young people understand ethnic differences and cultural diversity.

◆ In social care, discussions are made on understanding the importance of the organizational culture for the overall diversity fostering in practice. Different authors point that an understanding of cultural competence that is reduced to interactions between social workers and clients will unavoidably obscure the fact that these interactions also are structured through a host of ideas and values that are produced in policies, organizational arrangements and the physical environment. The necessity for a **power perspective** and the need to ask questions about inclusion and exclusion in relation to the institutions are emphasized. So, effective cultural competence practice shouldn't be the responsibility of just social workers.

◆ From social care literature, an example of three models of **multicultural social care organizational development** was derived: monocultural, antidiscriminative and multicultural organizations.

Monocultural organizations. At one extreme are organizations that are primarily Eurocentric and ethnocentric. The following premises and practices are typical of a monocultural organization:

- There is an implicit or explicit exclusion of people of color, women, and other oppressed groups.
- The organization is rigged to the advantage of the dominant majority.
- There is only one best way to deliver health care, manage, teach, or administrate.
- Culture does not influence management, mental health, or education.
- Clients, workers, or students should assimilate.
- Culture-specific ways of doing things are neither recognized nor valued. Everyone should be treated the same.
- There is strong belief in the melting pot concept.

Nondiscriminatory organizations. As organizations become more culturally aware and enlightened, they enter this stage. The following premises and practices characterize a nondiscriminatory organization:

- The organization has inconsistent policies and practices in regard to multicultural issues.

- Certain departments or mental health practitioners, managers, or educators are becoming sensitive to multicultural issues, but these are not an organizational priority.
- Leadership may recognize the need for some action, but leaders lack a systematic program or policy addressing the issue of prejudice and bias.
- There is an attempt to make the climate or services of the organization less hostile or more culturally sensitive, but these changes are superficial and often made without conviction.
- Equal employment opportunity, affirmative action, and numerical symmetry of people of color and women are implemented grudgingly.

Multicultural organizations. As organizations become progressively more multicultural, they begin to value diversity and evidence continuing attempts to accommodate ongoing cultural change. A multicultural organization:

- Is in the process of working on a vision that reflects multiculturalism.
- Reflects the contributions of diverse cultural and social groups in its mission, operations, products, and/or services.
- Values diversity (does not simply tolerate it) and views it as an asset.
- Actively engages in visioning, planning, and problem-solving activities that allow for equal access and opportunity.
- Realizes that equal access and opportunity are not equal treatment.
- Works to diversify the environment.

◆ Youth work advocates that young people have **equal access** to community resources. Professional youth work itself should be an inclusive practice in which young people of different origins meet and together develop democratic ways of dealing with diversity. Being based on universal values regarding human rights, democracy, peace, anti-racism, cultural diversity, solidarity, equality and sustainable development, youth work should always:

- promote social participation and responsibility, voluntary engagement and active citizenship,
- strengthen community and civil society building at all levels (e.g. intergenerational and intercultural dialogue),
- contribute to the development of youth creativity, cultural and social awareness, entrepreneurship and innovation,
- provide opportunities for social inclusion of all children and young people,
- reach out to youth with fewer opportunities through various methods that are flexible and quickly adaptable.

◆ Respect for diversity is the cornerstone of holistic youth work. In other words, by **respecting the complexity of the individual**, space is given to young people to be who they are. Focusing on lifestyles, life choices, life management, peer group cultures, “culture of being young”, adapting to multiculturalism in society, interdisciplinarity, etc. instead of subcultures, marginalization or specific targeted services etc. resulted in the creation of the so-called “cultural youth work”.

◆ Youth work creates opportunities for social inclusion of different young people and represents a suitable context for testing **multicultural policies**. That is, young

people who participate in youth work activities are not just users of those services – they are future citizens who need to be educated for active citizenship.

◆ To successfully serve all people, organizations need to develop **standards, policies, and practices** within appropriate cultural frameworks. Policies are directed towards inclusion, access to rights and activities, describe the responsibility of the community for inclusion. In order to provide relevant programs for all youth – and especially for youth from minority cultural groups – local program leadership should consider ways to diversify and expand program modalities to meet the needs of all. **Knowing the needs** of different groups can provide critical information about constraints that may affect program participation (eg, transportation, family/work structure, costs), as well as potential topics for project areas that are meaningful to certain cultural groups.

◆ In youth work, there is often a tendency to offer young people programs and services that treat them as a homogeneous group, without **respecting individual characteristics** and needs. For example, organizers of recreational and leisure activities often inadequately address various elements of one's cultural affiliation, such as value orientation, ethnic identity, social capital, issues of biculturalism, language and acculturation, religious beliefs, and family structure. Therefore, the need to understand that many young people, especially those belonging to minority ethnic groups, are affected by poverty, are geographically isolated, live in disorderly neighborhoods with a lot of violence and crime, etc., which is reflected in the lack of adequate programs and services.

◆ Organisations and institutions that work with youth should strive for specific **values** that reflect respect for diversity, and refer to:

- recognition of culture as the predominant factor in shaping behavior and values;
- understanding when the values of the dominant mainstream groups are in conflict with the values of different cultural groups;
- respecting the culturally defined needs of a certain community;
- recognizing and accepting that cultural differences exist and affect the way services are provided and received;
- understanding the role of natural systems (e.g., family, community) as primary mechanisms for individual support and development;
- recognition that concepts of individual, family and community may differ among cultural groups;
- respecting cultural preferences that value the process more than the product, as well as harmony and balance in life in relation to achievement; and
- recognition that members of different cultural groups must be at least bicultural in order to cope with the dominant society, which in turn creates its own set of emotional and behavioral problems.

◆ When creating a program for leisure activities, it is necessary to respect certain principles, such as encouraging the engagement of young people who belong to **culturally different groups** (develop awareness and interest in recreational programs among young people of different ethnic groups; organize group

participation in activities, so that "different" young people do not feel isolated; organize different types of programs and the way they are implemented, so that they are adapted to the cultural affiliation of young people).

Organizational climate that embraces diversity

Organizational climate may be defined as the shared perceptions of and the meaning attached to the policies, practices, and procedures employees experience and the behaviors they observe getting rewarded and that are supported and expected. Institutions'/organizations' climate includes the feelings and current tone of the institution/organization, the emotional aspect of relationships, and morals. It represents opportunities for young people to learn about different cultures, norms and values, which is important for preventing discrimination, exclusion, prejudice, stereotypes and racism and promoting and encouraging interactions between young people from different cultures.

Disrespect for diversity in one institution/organization is often a reflection of its climate. The climate is the result of the interaction of elements of the institutions'/organizations' culture with specific people (with all their characteristics and competencies) who work in it and those who learn and develop in it. Therefore, the climate as an indicator can also point to the shortcomings in the hypothetically high-quality "set" organizational culture or to the lack of competence of the organizations' staff who fail to convey the benefits of a positive culture through their interaction with young people. Organizations must establish an empowering climate and make clear their disapproval of social inequality and injustice. If the climate is such that there is empowerment and cooperation, the presence of actions that indicate disrespect for diversity will be minimized. If the climate sends a message to one group that it is better than another, no matter how subtly, seeds of discord are necessarily created. When there is an atmosphere of positive relationships between staff members, a good level of communication, an administration that supports those who work directly with young people and a proactive and participative manager with an inclusive philosophy, a positive learning environment will prevail and a sense of belonging and appreciation of the institutions'/organization will develop among young people and the organizations' staff.

The following are identified as the main characteristics of an ideal climate for learning and work: inclusiveness and belonging; diversity; respect; physical, emotional and psychological safety; openness and freedom of expression, asking questions, taking risks and making mistakes without judgment; adequate mentoring to encourage learning and career development. A climate that respects diversity in the classroom, or youth club, or social service provider is of great importance for positive youth developmental outcomes.

Culturally diverse environments are not only diverse in the sense that young people are different from one another, but each young person brings different socio-cultural dimensions as part of their individual identity. The cultural diversity climate is a type of environment that reflects the way in which cultural diversity is dealt with at the institution/organization. Structural diversity (for example, ethnic

composition) and cultural diversity are two different concepts, with different effects on youth outcomes and are considered separately.

When the climate does not value diversity and sees it as an obstacle, young people experience frequent forms of discrimination and peer violence, feel rejected, have a weak sense of belonging and feel alienated. Various authors often call the role of school climate in the prevention of peer violence and discrimination "critical".

Research shows that students of minority ethnic origin achieve worse academic results compared to students of the majority population, show poorer knowledge in mathematics and poorer reading literacy, and are more likely to repeat a grade. In addition, students of minority ethnic origin feel a weaker sense of belonging to school compared to other students. Research results indicate that the psychological well-being of students of emigrant origin differs by country of origin, country of destination, as well as by how well schools and local communities in the country of destination help students overcome expected obstacles in school and other areas of life. With age, minority ethnic students are at greater risk of discrimination, educator rejection. Research findings indicate that female students compared to male students have better relationships with educators regardless of whether they belong to the minority or majority population. Researchers suggest that a lack of multicultural education leads to greater peer violence, discrimination, prejudice, and other forms of victimization.

Based on the analysis of the model of the connection between the school culturally diversity climate and student outcomes (achievement, academic self-confidence and life satisfaction) through the mediation of the sense of belonging to the school, at the individual level and at the level of the department, positive significant relationships and the presumed mediation of the sense of belonging to the school are observed. The study involved 1,971 students (61% emigrants) in 88 culturally diverse classes in southwestern Germany after their first year of high school. The key finding of this research is that there were no differences in the effects of a diversity-nurturing school climate on student outcomes in multi-ethnic schools regardless of ethnicity. This points to the conclusion that the effective management of diversity in school is beneficial for all students.

The results of a longitudinal research study in which the impact of different approaches to cultural diversity in schools on the achievement and sense of belonging among students of minority and majority populations was examined, point to the conclusion that approaches that value cultural diversity have a much greater perspective in terms of measured outcomes among students. However, it can be found that although the majority population of students generally "benefits" from a climate of respect for diversity, they report a mediocre quality of relations with educators, with the suspicion that certain teaching practices in schools that value cultural pluralism make students of the majority population feel excluded. The sense of belonging to the school

represents the level to which students feel personally accepted, respected, included and supported by others in the school environment.

Research results indicate that a climate of nurturing practices of equal treatment and inclusion has positive results on typically measured student outcomes. Moreover, research findings indicate that the practice of treating all students equally in the classroom can mitigate negative impacts such as discrimination and others. In a sample of 47 multi-ethnic schools in Belgium with a focus on students of Moroccan and Turkish origin, it was determined that the perception of discrimination at school predicts lower achievement, while the perception of equal treatment of students at school mitigates the negative effects of discrimination. On a sample of 1,875 adolescents of the majority Belgian population and 1,445 students of Turkish and Moroccan ethnicity, it was determined that the perceptions of students and educators about equality and multiculturalism enabled, and rejection or assimilation threatened, normative-positive trajectories for the minority student population. Better academic outcomes have been recorded for minority students with a climate of equality and inclusion. An inclusive, equity-based approach helps both majority and minority student populations to establish and maintain positive relationships with educators. Interestingly, educators' perceptions of multiculturalism and assimilationism affected the trajectories of minority and majority student populations differently. When educators perceived schools as more multicultural and less assimilationist, minority students were more likely, and ethnic majority students less likely, to form good relationships with their educators. On the other hand, the majority student population seems to benefit more from assimilationism than multiculturalism, given that it is not perceived by the ethnic majority student population as an approach that is inclusive for all. Good relationships with educators have been shown to be protective for minority student populations in terms of behavioral problems such as disruptive behavior and poor engagement in school (data from 2021).

Lessons learned from youth work, education and social care:

- ◆ The way an organisation manages diversity and the **quality of interpersonal relationships** are considered key to a positive organisational climate. Acceptance and care by adults, especially educators or other staff working directly with youth, is recognized as a central aspect of organisational support to young people. Educators are recognized as potential promoters of a positive climate of diversity in their organisations/institutions.
- ◆ In order for a staff member to be a promoter of diversity, apart from being expected to have a positive attitude towards youth from different cultural backgrounds, he/she should create a **positive atmosphere** in the activities and get to know the diverse needs of young people that attend them.
- ◆ Optimal results in multicultural groups depend on several important factors, which

- include monitoring and managing young peoples' behavior, creating positive educator-young person (and peer) relationships, teaching that engages youth and is open to their attitudes, as well as the educator's **specific knowledge of multiculturalism**.

The results of the Teaching and Learning International Study (TALIS) (2019) study in the Nordic countries (Denmark, Finland, Iceland, Norway, Sweden) suggest that if the educator is generally competent and their experience is that they can handle most typical classroom situations (general self-efficacy), they will cope better in a multicultural environment and will consider themselves able to cope adequately with such circumstances. The age of educators was not found to be significant for this relationship, except in Finland where increased age (and thus experience) has a positive effect. However, the total experience of the educator has a negative effect on the "multicultural self-efficacy" of the educator. The author of the report interprets this not-so-expected result as a result of lower self-efficacy in handling multicultural classrooms, as their experience might not be greater than the one of younger colleagues.

A research conducted at two points on a sample of 186 (majority) Dutch students, and 129 students with Turkish-Dutch or Moroccan-Dutch (minority) background in 29 classrooms from 4th to 6th grade aimed to examine to what extent student ethnic group attitudes are influenced by educators' perceived positive norms about cultural diversity, along with perceived positive educator-student interactions that can serve as role models for students. The results showed that both majority and minority students expressed more positive attitudes towards different ethnic groups when they perceived that their educator had a positive relationship with their classmates, only when this was supported by the educator's positive multicultural norms.

- ◆ Researchers point to the role of the **educator as a leader** who makes minorities more visible, who encourages interaction between groups, including parents, has a proactive role in approaching parents of the minority youth population instead of a policy of "blaming the minority", offers support in overcoming problems as a result of "learned helplessness" of the minority population.
- ◆ Educators have an important role in modeling respectful behavior and establishing prosocial norms in the classroom. Through their behavior, they promote a sense of **security** and influence the group climate.

Students' poor peer relationships, in terms of victimization and loneliness at school (measured by items such as "I have no one to hang out with at school"), were associated with their intentions to drop out, and the links between loneliness and intentions to drop out were significantly stronger for the group of immigrants than for the group of native students (data from 2021).

- ◆ Also, in culturally diverse groups, there is a tendency for educators to notice that students communicate more with peers of a similar cultural affiliation during breaks and informal gatherings. Given that the experience of lack of acceptance,

interaction and friendship can lead to feelings of alienation, it is important for educators to encourage group work and initiate projects in which young persons of different cultural affiliations cooperate with each other. **Shared engagement** encourages youth to accept and value each other.

◆ As a group leader, the educator is in a unique position to develop relationships with students and to stimulate relationships among them. Establishing **clear norms**, rules of behavior and consequences for violating them is part of building a relationship of **mutual trust**, which can prevent peer violence and exclusion.

◆ To be culturally responsive, educators themselves must be part of a **supportive environment**. The importance of support also suggests that organisations/institutions should provide their staff with the resources and tools to create a supportive environment.

A study published in 2021 shows that there can be challenges in creating stable relationships to promote student interactions and friendships. To address these challenges, educators need more knowledge about developing cross-cultural friendships and strategies to promote relationships between students. Educator-student collaboration is necessary to promote positive relationships, engagement, and learning among students.

◆ Positive interactions with diverse peers allow young people to gain insight into **different ways of thinking**, communication styles, and problem solving. A positive and inclusive climate is fruitful for both students and educators, especially in the domain of job satisfaction.

◆ Literature shows us **that perceptions of fairness** (such as discrimination or preferential treatment in hiring and promotion procedures) of people working with youth is an important organizational element that support the diversity climate.

Social workers often reported working with other professionals in their organizations – social workers and nonsocial workers whose assumptions, biases, prejudices, and stereotypes about their clients have been offensive and discriminatory.

◆ Understanding the way educators in different fields should implement their programs and activities allows them to foster the diversity climate in their organizations and their contact with youth. In their everyday work fostering **ethical principles** of equality, respecting diversity and accountability are the main components of the climate that is welcoming, secure and supportive to all.

Competences that embrace diversity

The cultural complexity of society leads to the necessity of developing a set of skills and knowledge for successful functioning in an intercultural society. These

skills include creative and critical thinking, cultural competence, and social and global awareness. It is emphasized that improving cultural competence is key to solving the challenges that modern society faces, such as intolerance, prejudice, hate speech, discrimination and violence.

Cultural competence is an important component of social culture, which enables effective interaction with people belonging to different cultural groups based on the understanding of different cultural heritage. The concept of "cultural competence" was developed on the basis of decades of research into intercultural communication and cross-cultural psychology within the framework of the study of organizational culture constructs. Cultural competence is defined as a set of values, attitudes, skills, knowledge that are needed to understand and respect, as well as establish positive and constructive relationships with those who are perceived as culturally different. As defined by some authors, intercultural/transcultural competence is conceived as the ability to communicate effectively and appropriately in intercultural situations based on one's own intercultural knowledge (for example, self-awareness, understanding and knowledge of intercultural differences), competence (for example, taking someone else's perspective, listening, observing and interpreting, the ability to interpret an event or document from the point of view of different cultures, the ability to create new knowledge concerning culture and cultural practice) and attitudes (respect - valuing other cultures, cultural diversity, openness - for intercultural learning and people from other cultures; restraint from judgment; curiosity and discovery - tolerance of ambiguity and uncertainty).

Cultural competence implies the development of a multicultural identity that reflects, understands and is sensitive to one's own and other people's cultural identities. It implies that a person is comfortable in the company of others who do not belong to his cultural group, that he/she possesses knowledge about other cultural groups, as well as that he has the ability to achieve positive interactions with people of different cultural characteristics.

According to one of the most commonly used models, cultural competence consists of three components: awareness, knowledge and skills. Cultural awareness refers to an individual's adequate and appropriate attitudes, opinions, and assumptions about different cultures. Cultural awareness actually requires constant reflection on one's own attitudes towards other cultures and how one's own culture affects those attitudes. Cultural knowledge refers to the understanding of other cultures and cultural norms, while cultural skills refer to the ability to interact effectively and impartially with people from different cultures. Empathy, self-awareness, self-management and good communication skills are often mentioned as key parts of cultural competence.

Cross's model of cultural competence is widely used in the theory and research of this construct. The model implies the presence of five stages of cultural competence development, starting from destructiveness to advanced cultural competence:

1 Stage of cultural destructiveness – The most negative end of the continuum. It

describes the competence of an organization or individual who view cultural differences as a problem. It is characterized by inflexible behavior. A culturally different individual or group is considered genetically and culturally inferior.

- 2 Stage of cultural incompetence – The individual or organization is not intentionally culturally destructive, but lacks the capacity to have adequate interactions with culturally different individuals or groups. At this stage the individual or organization is extremely biased. Decisions and actions are driven by ignorance or feelings of superiority. People of culturally different origins are not valued or recognized, and expectations from them are reduced.
- 3 Cultural Blindness Stage – This is the middle of the continuum. An individual or organization operates with the belief that there are no cultural differences. This view does not imply the presence of bad intentions towards cultural diversity, although the consequences of this belief may be ignoring or not recognizing the strengths of different cultures. For example, this stage may manifest in an organization's reluctance to use alternative assessments or to change policies and procedures to "open the door" to diverse students.
- 4 Stage of cultural pre-competence - At this level, the individual or organization accepts and respects cultural differences. There are attempts at continuous self-evaluation in terms of culture. At this stage, proactivity and the search for knowledge from different cultural groups are characteristic.
- 5 Stage of cultural competence - This is the most positive and progressive level of Cross's model. An individual or organization proactively develops models and approaches that are fully grounded and culturally aligned.

Similar to Cross' model of cultural competence, Cormier developed a Cultural proficiency continuum, which distinguishes levels of response to cultural differences (Figure 1).

Reactive >>>>>>>>>>Tolerance			Proactive >>>>>>>>>>Transformation		
Cultural Destructiveness	Cultural Incapacity	Cultural Blindness	Cultural Pre-Competence	Cultural Competence	Cultural Proficiency
See the difference; stomp it out.	See the difference; make it wrong	See the difference; dismiss it	See the difference; recognize what you don't know	See the difference; understand the difference that difference makes.	See the difference; respond positively and affirmingly.
Unhealthy Behavior			Healthy Behavior		

Figure 1. Cultural proficiency continuum (Cormier, 2021).

Cultural sensitivity

Cultural sensitivity can be defined as a critical awareness of one's own cognitive, affective, and behavioral responses to cultural differences that reflect how individuals interpret intercultural differences. Also, cultural sensitivity is defined as an active desire to understand, appreciate and accept differences between cultures. It represents the affective dimension of intercultural communication and is considered crucial for the development of one's ability to think and act in an intercultural appropriate way. In a culturally diverse learning community, students from different cultural backgrounds bring their own ways of thinking into the learning context. With increased sensitivity to other cultures, they can better participate in classroom interactions, which in turn contributes to better learning outcomes.

Milton Bennett's developmental model of intercultural sensitivity represents the best-known theoretical framework for the interpretation of cultural sensitivity, but it is also an important theoretical base for designing educational interventions for the development of cultural competencies, bearing in mind that it helps educators in better creation, planning and implementation of trainings, understanding the resistance that individuals show at different stages of the development of cultural sensitivity and creating a stimulating environment for intercultural learning. In addition to interpreting this model at the individual level, it is also possible to interpret it at the organizational level.

Bennett's Developmental Model of Intercultural Sensitivity describes the stages that individuals go through when meeting other cultures: from denying the existence of differences, ie. extreme ethnocentrism, towards the stages of observing and accepting them, that is, ethnorelativism. It distinguishes three basic stages of ethnocentrism and three stages of ethnorelativism, and within each of them several developmental intermediate stages, which is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Developmental Model of Intercultural Sensitivity (Bennet, 1986)

Ethnocentrism			Ethnorelativism		
Denial	Defense	Minimizing	Acceptance	Adaptation	Integration
Isolation	Disparagement	Physical universalism	Behavioral relativism	Empathy	Contextual evaluation
Separation	Superiority	Transcendental universalism	Value relativism	Pluralism	Constructive marginality
	Reversal				

Each of the stages implies the following:

- 1 Denial of difference – failure to perceive the existence or relevance of cultural diversity of others. Perceiving one's own culture is far more complex than perceiving other cultures. People are disinterested or perhaps even hostile

to intercultural communication. Depending on the severity, there are two subtypes of denial of differences: isolation – unintentional separation from members of other cultures, that is, the presence of life circumstances in which the individual does not have the opportunity to establish relationships with members of different cultures; separation – intentional separation from members of different cultures, because there is an opinion that this is better for their development and the development of the society to which they belong. In organizations, denial is a state in which there are no structures (policies and procedures) for recognizing and dealing with cultural diversity. Denial occurs when people who prefer stability (absence of differences) are forced by some circumstances to become aware of others (differences). This happens when, for example, a significant number of refugees or immigrants enter a community, or when people have to deal with cultural differences in a work organization.

2 Defense against differences – when the problem of denial is solved, people can move to the stage of defense against cultural differences. In this phase, the dichotomous categorization of "us and them" is characteristic, where others are perceived more complexly than in denial, but also in very stereotypical ways. People in this stage tend to be critical of other cultures and tend to blame cultural differences for society's general ills. There are three forms of defense: disparagement – a person treats other cultures as inferior, uses offensive terms to describe them, and applies negative stereotypes to other cultural groups; superiority – the tendency to emphasize and exaggerate the positive characteristics of one's own culture in comparison with other cultures, not necessarily disparaging other cultures; turning to the opposite – a person perceives another culture as superior, and looks down on his own culture and feels alienated.

3 Minimizing differences – in this stage, cultural differences are minimized with the assumption that it is much more important to emphasize similarities than differences. Similarities are based on known elements of one's own cultural worldview, and individuals assume that their own experiences are shared by others or that certain basic values and beliefs transcend cultural boundaries and are thus universally applicable. Emphasizing cross-cultural similarity creates "tolerance," whereby superficial cultural differences are seen as variations on common universal themes of humanity. However, minimization obscures deep cultural differences. The minimization problem for individuals is their desire to project sameness onto the wider world and that world's stubborn resistance to losing its real difference. This means that the more people seek contact with others in the name of shared values, the more likely they will be forced to confront significant cultural differences. Something similar happens in organizations, where an overemphasis on "unity" yields too much uniformity, which forces the organization to decentralize and focus on its diversity. In both individual and organizational cases, problem solving occurs when similarity and difference, unity and diversity, are put into dialectical form: similarities allow us to appreciate differences, and unity directs the focus to diversity. There are two different viewpoints about the same human nature in this phase, namely: physical universalism – insists on

physiological similarities, i.e. points out that all people have the same basic needs; transcendental universalism – implies the belief that all people are the same thanks to spiritual, political and other similarities.

4 Acceptance – at this stage, the individual notices and accepts cultural differences. Cultural differences are not evaluated based on the standards of one's own cultural group, but are studied in the cultural context from which they arise. Acceptance of cultural differences does not mean that they are necessarily evaluated positively, but the person's position is not ethnocentric. Individuals at this stage are curious about cultures and cultural differences. However, their limited knowledge of other cultures does not allow them to easily adapt their behavior to different cultural contexts. The guiding principle is cultural relativism, that is, the view that no culture is better or worse than others. Differences are accepted in two ways: behavioral relativism - a person accepts differences at the behavioral level, i.e. is aware that behavior changes depending on the cultural context; value relativism – means acceptance that the value system and beliefs, in addition to behavior, also vary from one cultural community to another. There is support for "diversity and inclusion" in organizations, but the incorporation of cultural sensitivity as a criterion for multicultural leadership has not yet been established.

5 Adaptation – in this phase the mechanism of "perspective taking" or empathy is present. This means that a person consciously tries to imagine what views of the world are held by members of other cultures. A person changes his frame of reference by adapting to the viewpoints, attitudes and beliefs of members of another cultural community. It is capable of changing perspectives, ways of communication or behavior according to the wishes, needs or demands of the cultural community. There are two types of adaptation: empathy – the ability to understand others by taking their point of view; pluralism – a person has internalized several different views on the world, i.e. more cultural frameworks. Organizations at this point in development have policies and procedures that are intentionally flexible enough to operate without undue cultural imposition. At the organizational level, adaptation is the essence of "incorporating" diversity into organizational processes.

6 Integration – while at the stage of adaptation a person is guided by several reference frames (which exist in parallel), in this phase the person has integrated these different cultural worldviews into a unique, own worldview. Her identity includes and, more importantly, transcends the cultural groups to which she belongs. This stage is also characterized by intercultural communication. Integration can occur in two forms: contextual evaluation - the ability to use different cultural frames of reference in the assessment of a given situation; constructive marginality – accepting an identity that is not primarily based on one of the cultures. A person is in constant development and does not limit or emphasize the influence of different cultures on personal development, does not identify with any culture, but sees them as a chance for development.

What we know from the literature is that, for quality fostering in practice, we primarily want our staff to have developed cultural competences (for they

will use those competences in their work), and we want to develop cultural sensitivity among our young people (for they will interact and connect with diverse youth).

Lessons learned from education, social care and youth work

- ◆ Cultural competence, in a broad sense, is understood as the ability of educators to **successfully teach** young people who come from different cultures, different from their own. The practices and artifacts that educators adopt to value cultural diversity are essential to developing a warm environment that supports the individual needs of young people and for the appreciation of diversity in the organisation/institution.
- ◆ Defining the standards for the implementation of policy and practice, with a special focus on the development of professional competences of staff to work with different groups of youth, is crucial for the realization of the organisations' vision. Initial training, **professional development** and ongoing support for staff members are key to developing an effective inclusive organisation.
- ◆ A culturally competent educator possesses **knowledge** about the characteristics of his own culture, the characteristics of the culture of others, the characteristics of his own organisational environment and the characteristics of culturally different youth and their families; has **attitudes** that point to the willingness to relativize cultural values, the absence of stereotypes and prejudices in contact with culturally different youth, awareness of the non-existence of universally applicable patterns of behavior in all cultures; possesses the **skills** of interpreting the meaning of thoughts, ideas and events of culturally different young people and their parents, accepting the expectations of culturally different young people and parents, adapting to verbal and non-verbal styles of communication, mediation and peaceful conflict resolution and is characterized by positive behavioral characteristics (patience, flexibility, openness, empathy).
- ◆ A culturally competent educator recognizes **diversity as a strength** and strives to create an inclusive group environment that simultaneously fosters positive cross-cultural relationships among young people and a sense of socio-political awareness.
- ◆ One of the key competences for lifelong learning defined by the European Commission implies precisely **cultural awareness and expression**.
- ◆ Educators and other actors in an intercultural educational environment (no matter in which formal setting it is placed) should:
 - Recognize that some organizational practices may contribute to exclusion and segregation; therefore, they should provide **teaching methods** adapted to the different cultural belonging of the youth they work with;
 - Plan a **program** and environment that reflects respect for all cultural, ethnic,

social and religious differences among people and that promotes the cultural identities of all youth included in it;

- Recognize and respond appropriately to **cultural perspectives** that affect the achievement and overall progress of culturally diverse youth;
- Create a teaching and learning environment that positively affects how young people **feel** about the organisation/ institution, feel accepted and cared for;
- Facilitate a **culturally diverse collective** that reflects the real differences that exist in a certain society and, more importantly, in the organisational environment itself;
- Prepare a **plan for the inclusion** of culturally diverse parents and close families in the teaching and learning process if that is possible or needed (if the organisation has a chance to collaborate with the family of the young person), that is, to deal with specific practical issues related to language barriers between organisational staff and parents, explaining the organisations expectations to parents and families who may not understand the way the organisation or institutions functions because they come from different environments, as well as ways of further engagement and inclusion of parents and family members in organisational activities (again, if the collaboration with the family is in the focus of the organisation).

◆ Educators, as "transmitters" of interculturality, are expected to know the principles and values of interculturality, to be sensitive and open, to analyze and question their own attitudes, as well as to be ready to improve their competences in order to be a **role model** for youth in the process of adopting values, attitudes and behaviors, which ensure the stability of culturally complex communities.

◆ Therefore, in order for educators to be culturally competent, they first need to develop **self-reflection**, that is, to know themselves well, their own values and beliefs; to understand diversity by knowing the characteristics, habits and behavior patterns of their students; apply culturally responsive teaching; to have a multicultural educational approach.

◆ The salient characteristics of a **culturally responsive and competent** educator are:

- Sociocultural awareness: recognizes that there are multiple ways of perceiving reality and that one's position in the social order affects those ways;
- Affirmative attitudes towards young people of culturally different backgrounds: seeing the learning resources of all young people, instead of viewing differences as problems to be overcome;
- Commitment and skills to act as agents of change: see themselves as responsible and capable of advocating for changes in the organisation or the system that will make the organisation more accountable for all young people it engages with;
- Constructive views of learning: understand how young people construct knowledge and are competent to encourage their construction of knowledge;
- Learning about the concrete young people: knowing about the lives of the youth he/she works with; and
- Culturally responsive teaching practices: use their knowledge of the lives of

the young people they work with to design instruction that builds on what they already know, while introducing them beyond the familiar.

◆ Some educators spend a lot of time finding appropriate and relevant materials that align with the learning objectives outlined in the curriculums they want to implement, while few consider social and cultural biases in the materials. **Curriculum transformation** requires educators to change the structure of their curriculum to enable young people to consider concepts, issues, events and topics from a multicultural perspective. It is important that the curriculum is flexible enough to provide opportunities for adaptation to individual needs and to stimulate educators to seek solutions that will be in accordance with the needs and abilities of each young person in their group. Many curricula expect all youth to learn the same things, at the same time and with the same means and methods, which reflects culturally unresponsive practice.

◆ While it is important for educators to focus on curriculum and various needs of the youth they work with regarding their personal and social life, it is also valuable for them to recognize the **role they play in the lives** of their group members, especially for those young people who may be vulnerable and marginalized. The ways and processes of work in a group based on the cultural competence of educators contribute to the development of a climate of mutual understanding, respect and equal cooperation, which is based on knowledge and respect for the different lifestyles of peers from the group, their values, beliefs, traditions, customs, stereotypes, cultural elements different – similarities and differences.

◆ Therefore, the need for culturally competent educators is critically important because young persons' academic achievement, critical awareness, cultural sensitivity, and social competence are closely related to a **culturally synchronized learning environment**.

◆ Educators' attitudes and beliefs about diversity as a value are reflected in their group members **experiences**.

Educators' attitudes about respecting diversity and cultural pluralism are associated with a lower perception of the degree of discrimination by youth who belong to minority groups.

◆ Educator competencies are also necessary for **culturally responsive management** in the group, which is an approach to managing the group dynamic with all its members in a culturally responsive manner. As culturally responsive leaders, educators recognize their own biases and values and reflect on how they affect their expectations of behavior and interactions with others. They also recognize that the goal of group management is not to achieve control, but to provide all its members with equal learning opportunities and understand that culturally responsive management is a function of social justice.

◆ **Cultural sensitivity** is considered an asset for every educator, necessary, not only for the formation of his own cultural view of the world, which will make it easier for

him to notice, analyze and accept the cultural diversity of young people, but also for the acquisition and development of intercultural competences necessary for working in culturally plural classes.

Previous studies in the school system often point to teachers' conceptual confusion in understanding cultural diversity and pedagogical difficulties in modifying practice in a responsive manner, which school practitioners usually attribute to inadequate teacher education and organizational/structural constraints such as lack of time and resources. School leadership is seen as key to providing such training, but also to promoting all aspects of a diversity-friendly school context. Also, citing the low time commitment to inclusive education training and the increasing demands on teachers to effectively include all students in the classroom, many teachers report feeling inadequately prepared to teach students with diverse needs and abilities.

Research in six European countries also showed that teachers feel that they receive insufficient or even no training to deal with cultural diversity in the classroom. The above points to the need to implement additional programs with the intention of improving the cultural competence of teachers, and there is strong research evidence that speaks in favor of the positive impact of training on improving the cultural competence of teachers.

◆ Integral to multicultural social work practice are four major competencies that effective multicultural social work practitioners should be able to **achieve and demonstrate** in their practice. These competencies are (1) becoming aware of one's own values, biases, and assumptions about human behavior; (2) understanding the worldviews of culturally diverse clients; (3) developing appropriate intervention strategies and techniques; and (4) understanding organizational and institutional forces that enhance or diminish cultural competence.

In Sweden, cultural competence is often singled out as both a strategy and solution for managing differences attributed to migrants, but few studies have critically investigated the idea of cultural competence. The analysis shows that cultural competencies almost exclusively attributed to staff who have a migrant background, and that the position as culturally competent is ambiguous. On the one hand a position as expert, on the other hand surrounded by a suspicion not to be professional. Cultural competence rather emerges as a tool to master and control the boys who are placed in the studied institutions than as a tool to affect a change process in support of multiculturalism. Through a latent content analysis of course syllabi from 27 US-based social work programs, three key assumptions emerged: social workers are members of dominant social groups; cultural competency and anti-oppression are compatible frameworks; self-awareness mitigates oppression. Findings reflect the reification of dominant culture groups in social work and promotion of individual-level skill development over structural change. Implications and recommendations for social work education and future research are discussed. Nylund criticized concept of cultural competence, noticed that the most cultural diversity classes in social work are taught from a liberal or conservative multicultural perspective that precludes a power analysis and

a critical discussion of whiteness. Author consider that in order to undo this practice, social educators need to incorporate critical multiculturalism as a tool in subverting racism. Study explored the challenges of newly employed social workers educated about diversity practice by Council of Social Work Education (CSWE) and the National Association of Social Workers (NASW) in practicing cultural competence relative to their professional experiences. The findings emphasized the multifaceted nature of cultural competence and highlighted: areas for growth in feelings of inadequacy (due to a lack of familiarity or a lack of experience); frustration with fundamental organizational barriers (lack of resources and education, good diversity policies) and prejudice from clients.

◆ A six-stage developmental **continuum of cultural competence** for is derived from the social care field, which can be of importance to all organisations working with youth, no matter in which field. These stages are (1) cultural destructiveness (forced assimilation), (2) cultural incapacity (discriminatory practice), (3) cultural blindness (helping methods used by the dominant culture as universally applicable), (4) cultural precompetence (hiring minority staff, but change stays only structural), (5) cultural competence (great opportunities to increase staff multicultural skills and knowledge, and (6) cultural proficiency (both the organization itself and individuals within the organization are operating at high levels of cultural competence).

◆ **Multicultural family social work**, should be guided by the following in everyday practice of practitioners that implement their work with young people including their families:

- Diversity management involves handling different cultural conceptions of the family.
- The expert should be aware that one definition of family cannot be seen as superior to another.
- The expert should know that families cannot be understood apart from the cultural, social, and political dimensions of their functioning. The traditionally defined nuclear family, consisting of heterosexual parents in a long-term marriage, raising their biological children, and with the father as sole wage earner, is starting to be a statistical minority.
- The expert should give an effort to learn as much as possible about how cultural group that is different that her/his, about how defines the family, the values that underlie the family unit, and your own contrasting definition of the family.
- The expert should be attentive to traditional cultural family structures and extended family ties. For example, nonblood relatives may be considered an intimate part of the extended family system.
- The expert should not prejudge from their own ethnocentric perspective. For example, they have to be aware that eastern compared to western, white population may have spousal relationships that are more patriarchal, view the wifely role as less important than the motherly role.
- Multicultural social work needs modifying the practitioners' goals and techniques to fit the needs of culturally diverse populations.
- The expert should assess the importance of ethnicity to clients, both individuals and families. Have to be aware that acculturation is very

important for the children and young people in a family, because they are the ones most likely to be influenced by peers. Also, many conflicts between younger and older generations are related to cultural conflicts. These conflicts are not pathological, but normative responses to different cultural forces.

◆ Education programs for professional development of practitioners that are in direct contact with youth should always include **explicit and implicit curriculum content** related to ethnic and cultural diversity, gender, language, nationality, religion, and sexual orientation.

◆ Quality diversity fostering practitioners should bear in mind:

- Sociodemographic group identities often dictate how we define problems and choose interventions. The cultural perspectives of young people and their families may often clash with that of the well-intentioned expert, who must develop culturally appropriate **intervention strategies** in working with clients and client systems.

- Experts must be able to **hear the voices** of their oppressed clients, to understand their experiences of marginalization, to empathize with the pain and hardships they have had to endure, and be aware that their position in this society may be due to no fault of their own.

- In many respects, work with youth in various fields is about **social justice**. Given this statement, it is important to realize that racism, sexism, ableism, heterosexism, and classism are functions of the unjust treatment of various socially marginalized groups in society.

- Have to understand that the work and responsibilities of the experts are directed at **changing** not simply the lives of individuals, but the very institutional and cultural policies and practices that prevent equal access and opportunity.

- Know that cultural competence is a **lifelong journey** that never ends. Practitioners and educators shouldn't be discouraged.

- The expert should be aware that the first step toward cultural competence is to work on **understanding** himself/herself's racial/cultural being. Understanding other groups becomes the next priority.

◆ In order for the educators to encourage the cultural competence and sensitivity of young people, it is necessary to:

- They recognize differences and that diversity and discrimination are not **taboo** topics;

- They encourage young people and adults from different backgrounds to cooperate in order to achieve common goals (they encourage young people to **cooperate** in order to achieve intercultural relations);

- Include leaders, volunteers and practitioners from **different backgrounds** (establish mentoring relationships between adults and youth; include community visitors and volunteers of different cultural, ethnic, racial, sexual, linguistic and religious backgrounds or orientations);

- Include **traditional elements** from different and numerous cultures (eg multicultural books, games and posters that reflect different experiences, culturally specific events).

- Support **cultural identity research** among young people and seek to understand them through their own definitions (eg, various books and resources that reflect open views on identity, diversity and cultural issues).
- ◆ Educators need to have **culturally specific knowledge** about the youth population they work with. This knowledge includes, but is not limited to, the history of a particular cultural group, experience with prejudice and discrimination, as well as general knowledge of culturally specific beliefs of a particular group.
- ◆ Professionals working with youth today must understand their own culture and its distinctive values, consider the different cultures and values of their youth participants and families, and examine **how to meet the needs** of each young person by acknowledging and respecting their culture and values.

Literature – where to learn more

- ◆ Abrams, L. S., & Moio, J. A., (2009). Critical race theory and the cultural competence dilemma in social work education. *Journal of Social Work Education*, 45(2), 245-261. <https://doi.org/10.5175/JSWE.2009.200700109>
- ◆ Adera, B., & Manning, M. L. (2014). Promoting social and cultural competence for students from diverse backgrounds with disabilities. *Multicultural Learning and Teaching*, 9(1), 67-82. <https://doi.org/10.1515/mlt-2013-0025>
- ◆ Ahponen, P., Harinen, P., Honkasalo, V., Kivijärvi, A., Pyykkönen, M., Ronkainen, J., Souto, A-M., & Suurpää, L. (2014). New challenges for nordic welfare services. *Nordic Journal of Migration Research*, 4(1), 30-39. <https://doi.org/10.2478/njmr-2014-0005>
- ◆ Ainscow, M. (2020). Promoting inclusion and equity in education: lessons from international experiences. *Nordic Journal of Studies in Educational Policy*, 6(1), 7-16. <https://doi.org/10.1080/20020317.2020.1729587>
- ◆ Ainscow, M., & Messiou, K. (2018) Engaging with the views of students to promote inclusion in education. *Journal of Educational Change*, 19(1), 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10833-017-9312-1>
- ◆ Ainscow, M., & Sandill, A. (2010). Developing inclusive education systems: The role of organisational cultures and leadership. *International journal of inclusive education*, 14(4), 401-416. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603110802504903>
- ◆ Ainscow, M., Booth, T., Dyson, A., with Farrell, P., Frankham, J., Gallannaugh, F., Howes, A. & Smith, R. (2006). *Improving Schools, Developing Inclusion*. London: Routledge.
- ◆ Ainscow, M., Chapman, C., & Hadfield, M. (2020). *Changing education systems: A research-based approach*. Routledge.
- ◆ Al Qadhi, S., Yousef, W., & Abu-Shawish, R. K. (2021). Impact of cultural competence and education of a preservice educator and pedagogical style. *Review of International Geographical Education Online*, 11(10), 2049-2059.
- ◆ Allen, K. A., & Bowles, T. (2012). Belonging as a guiding principle in the education of adolescents. *Australian Journal of Educational & Developmental Psychology*, 12, 108-119.
- ◆ Allport, G. W. (1954). *The nature of prejudice*. Addison-Wesley.
- ◆ Amor, A. M., Hagiwara, M., Shogren, K. A., Thompson, J. R., Verdugo, M. Á., Burke, K. M., & Aguayo, V. (2019). International perspectives and trends in research on inclusive education: A systematic review. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 23(12), 1277-1295. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603116.2018.1445304>
- ◆ Aral, T., Schachner, M. K., Juang, L., & Schwarzenhal, M. (2022). Cultural diversity approaches in schools and adolescents' willingness to support refugee youth. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 92(2), 772-799. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjep.12458>
- ◆ Artiles, A. J., & Ortiz, A. A. (Eds.). (2002). *English language learners with special education needs*. Center for Applied Linguistics.
- ◆ Baglieri, S., & Shapiro, A. (2017). *Disability studies and the inclusive classroom: Critical practices for embracing diversity in education*. Routledge.

- ◆ Banks, S. (Ed.) (2010). *Ethical issues in youth work* (2nd edition). Routledge.
- ◆ Barrett, M. (2013). Interculturalism and multiculturalism: Concepts and controversies. In M. Barrett (Ed.), *Interculturalism and multiculturalism: Similarities and differences* (pp. 15-41). Council of Europe Publishing.
- ◆ Barrett, M. (2016). *Competences for democratic culture: Living together as equals in culturally diverse democratic societies*. Council of Europe Publishing. <http://www.coe.int/en/web/education/competences-fordemocratic-culture>
- ◆ Barrett, M. (2018). How schools can promote the intercultural competence of young people. *European Psychologist*, 23(1), 93-104. <https://doi.org/10.1027/1016-9040/a000308>
- ◆ Baysu G, Hillekens J, Phalet K, & Deaux K. (2021). How diversity approaches affect ethnic minority and majority adolescents: Educator-student relationship trajectories and school outcomes. *Child Development*, 92(1), 367-387. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cdev.13417>
- ◆ Baysu, G., Celeste, L., Brown, R., Verschueren, K., & Phalet, K. (2016). Minority adolescents in ethnically diverse schools: Perceptions of equal treatment buffer threat effects. *Child development*, 87(5), 1352-1366. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cdev.12609>
- ◆ Bedeković, V. (2011). *Interkulturalne kompetencije nastavnika*. (Doktorska disertacija). Sveučilište u Zagrebu: Filozofski fakultet.
- ◆ Bektas, F., Çogaltay, N., Karadag, E., & Ay, Y. (2015). School culture and academic achievement of students: A meta-analysis study. *The Anthropologist*, 21(3), 482-488. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09720073.2015.11891837>
- ◆ Bell, L. A. (2007). Theoretical foundations for social justice education. In M. Adams, L. A. Bell, & P. Griffin (Eds.), *Teaching for diversity and social justice: A sourcebook* (2nd ed., pp. 1-14). Routledge.
- ◆ Bennett, C. I. (2007). *Comprehensive multicultural education: Theory and practice* (6th edition). Allyn and Bacon.
- ◆ Bennett, M. (1986). Toward ethnorelativism: A developmental model of intercultural sensitivity. In R. M. Paige (Ed.), *Cross-cultural orientation: New conceptualizations and applications* (pp. 27-70). NY University Press of America.
- ◆ Bennett, M. J. (2013). *Basic concepts of intercultural communication* (2nd edition). Intercultural Press.
- ◆ Bernstein, R. S., Bulger, M., Salipante, P., & Weisinger, J. Y. (2020). From diversity to inclusion to equity: A theory of generative interactions. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 167, 395-410. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-019-04180-1>
- ◆ Berry, J. W. (2019). *Acculturation: A personal journey across cultures*. Cambridge University Press.
- ◆ Björnsson, J. K. (2020). Teaching culturally diverse student groups in the nordic countries – what can the TALIS 2018 data tell us?. In T. S. Fronnes, A. Pettersen, J. Radišić, N. Buchholtz (Eds.), *Equity, equality and diversity in the Nordic model of education* (pp. 75-97). Springer, Cham.
- ◆ Booth, T., & Ainscow, M. (2002). *Index for INCLUSION: Developing Learning and Participation in Schools*. Centre for Studies on Inclusive Education.
- ◆ Bourhis, R. Y., Moise, L. C., Perreault, S., & Senecal, S. (1997). Toward an interactive acculturation model: a social psychological approach. *International Journal of Psychology*, 32(6), 369–386. <https://doi.org/10.1080/002075997400629>

- ◆ Bowie, L. and Bronte-Tinkew, J. (2006). Professional development for youth workers. Research brief. Child Trends.
- ◆ Brewer, M. B. (1991). The social self: On being the same and different at the same time. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 17, 475-482. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0146167291175001>
- ◆ Broadbent, R., & Corney, T. (2008). Professional youth work in Victoria: the whole 'kitbag'. *Commonwealth Youth and Development*, 6(1), 15-22. <https://hdl.handle.net/10520/EJC30884>
- ◆ Bronfenbrenner, U., & Morris, P. A. (2006). The Bioecological model of human development. In Richard M. Lerner, & W. Damon (Eds.), *Handbook of Child Psychology- Volume 1: Theoretical Models of Human Development* (pp. 793–828). Hoboken: John Wiley & Sons.
- ◆ Brown, C. S. (2019). The importance, and the challenges, to ensuring an inclusive school climate. *Educational Psychologist*, 54(4), 322-330. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00461520.2019.1655646>
- ◆ Brown, C. S., & Chu, H. (2012). Discrimination, ethnic identity, and academic outcomes of mexican immigrant children: The importance of school context. *Child Development*, 83(5), 1477-1485. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8624.2012.01786.x>
- ◆ Brown-Jeffy, S., & Cooper, J. E. (2011). Toward a conceptual framework of culturally relevant pedagogy: An overview of the conceptual and theoretical literature. *Educator education quarterly*, 38(1), 65-84.
- ◆ Bukvić Branković, L., Popović-Čitić, B., Stojanović, M., Popović, V., Larsen, M., Kaarup, T., Lee, M., Jovanović Bramsen, D., & Stojković, B. (2022). Act as professionals: Training module for the use of professional principles in youth work. CEPORA – Center for Positive Youth Development. http://cepora.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/12/Act-as-professionals_ENG.pdf
- ◆ Bulris, M. E. (2009). A meta-analysis of research on the mediated effects of principal leadership on student achievement: Examining the effect size of school culture on student achievement as an indicator of educator effectiveness. East Carolina University.
- ◆ Bužinkić, E., Čulum, B., Horvat, M., & Kovačić, M. (2015). Youth work in Croatia: collecting pieces for a mosaic. *Child & youth services*, 36(1), 30-55. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/0145935X.2015.1015879>
- ◆ Cakrawati, L. M. (2018). Promoting Multicultural Literacy through Learning Materials in EFL Classroom: Benefits and Challenges. *Proceedings of the Tenth Conference on Applied Linguistics and the Second English Language Teaching and Technology Conference in collaboration with the First International Conference on Language, Literature, Culture, and Education (CONAPLIN and ICOLLITE 2017) - Literacy, Culture, and Technology in Language Pedagogy and Use*, pp. 213-218. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5220/0007164702130218>
- ◆ Carales, V. D., & López, R. M. (2020). Challenging deficit views of Latinx students: A strength based perspective. *New Directions for Community Colleges*, 190, 103-113. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cc.20390>
- ◆ Carpenter, D. (2015). School culture and leadership of professional learning communities. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 29(5), 682-694. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEM-04-2014-0046>

- ◆ Cefai, C., Bartolo P. A., Cavioni, V., & Downes, P. (2018). Strengthening Social and Emotional Education as a core curricular area across the EU. A review of the international evidence, NESET II report, Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2766/664439>
- ◆ Celeste, L., Baysu, G., Phalet, K., Meeussen, L., & Kende, J. (2019). Can school diversity policies reduce belonging and achievement gaps between minority and majority youth? Multiculturalism, colorblindness, and assimilationism assessed. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 45(11), 1603-1618. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0146167219838577>
- ◆ Celinskā, D., & Swazo, R. (2021). Multicultural curriculum designs in counselor education programs: Enhancing counselors-in-training openness to diversity. *The Journal of Counselor Preparation and Supervision*, 8(3), 1-23. <http://dx.doi.org/10.7729/83.1124>
- ◆ Central Vancouver Island Multicultural Society (2015). Cultural Competence Self-Assessment Checklist. Available at: <http://www.coloradoedinitiative.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/10/cultural-competence-self-assessment-checklist.pdf>
- ◆ Chan, A. S. (2005). Policy discourses and changing practice: Diversity and the university-college. *Higher Education*, 50(1), 129-157. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-004-6351-3>
- ◆ Chen, G. M., & Starosta, W. J. (2000a). The development and validation of the intercultural Communication Sensitivity Scale. *Human Communication*, 3, 1-15.
- ◆ Chen, G.-M., & Starosta, W. J. (2000b). Intercultural sensitivity. In L. A. Samovar, & R. E. Porter, (Eds.), *Intercultural Communication: A Reader*. (pp. 406-414). Wadsworth Publishing Company.
- ◆ Cherkowski, S., & Ragoonaden, K. (2016). Leadership for diversity: Intercultural communication competence as professional development. *Educator Learning and Professional Development*, 1(1), 33-43.
- ◆ Cheung, R. S., Hui, A. N., & Cheung, A. C. (2020). Gifted education in Hong Kong: A school-based support program catering to learner diversity. *ECNU Review of Education*, 3(4), 632-658. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2096531120967447>
- ◆ Chireshe, R. (2011). Special needs education in service educator trainees: views on inclusive education in Zimbabwe. Available at: <http://www.krepublishers.com/02-Journals/JSS/JSS-27-0-000-11-Web/JSS-27-3-000-11=Abst=PDF/JSS-27-3-157-11=1194-Chireshe-R-Tt.pdf>. Accessed on 22/04/2012
- ◆ Civitillo, S., Schachner, M., Juang, L., van de Vijver, F. J., Handrick, A., & Noack, P. (2017). Towards a better understanding of cultural diversity approaches at school: A multi-informant and mixed-methods study. *Learning, Culture and Social Interaction*, 12, 1-14. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.lcsi.2016.09.002>
- ◆ Coburn, A. (2011). Building social and cultural capital through learning about equality in youth work. *Journal of Youth Studies*, 14(4), 475-491. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/13676261.2010.538041>
- ◆ Collaborative for Academic, Social and Emotional Learning (2013). *The 2013 CASEL Guide: Effective social and emotional learning programs-preschool and elementary school edition*. Author.
- ◆ Collaborative for Academic, Social and Emotional Learning (2020). *CASEL SEL Framework*. Available at: <https://casel.org/wpcontent/uploads/2020/12/CASEL->

[SEL-Framework-11.2020.pdf](#)

- ◆ Conklin, H. G., & Hughes, H. E. (2016). Practices of compassionate, critical, justice-oriented educator education. *Journal of Educator Education*, 67(1), 47-60. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022487115607346>
- ◆ Cormier, D. R. (2021). Assessing preservice educators' cultural competence with the cultural proficiency continuum Q-sort. *Educational Researcher*, 50(1), 17-29. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3102/0013189X20936670>
- ◆ Cressey, G. (2008). No spare rib: Supporting Muslim young women's agency. *Scottish youth issues journal*, 11, 53-63.
- ◆ Cross, T. L., Bazron, B. J., Dennis, K. W., & Isaacs, M. R. (1989). Towards a culturally competent system of care. Georgetown University – Child Development Center, CASSP Technical Assistance Center.
- ◆ Crouch, R., Keys, C. B., & McMahon, S. D. (2014). Student–educator relationships matter for school inclusion: School belonging, disability, and school transitions. *Journal of prevention & intervention in the community*, 42(1), 20-30. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/10852352.2014.855054>
- ◆ Darnell, A. J., & Kuperminc, G. P. (2006). Organizational cultural competence in mental health service delivery: A multilevel analysis. *Journal of Multicultural Counseling and Development*, 34, 194-207. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2161-1912.2006.tb00039.x>
- ◆ Deal, T. E., & Peterson, K. (1999). *Shaping school culture: The heart of leadership*. San Jossey-Bass.
- ◆ Demanet, J., Agirdag, O., & Van Houtte, M. (2012). Constrict in the school context: The impact of ethnic school diversity on the quantity and quality of friendships. *The Sociological Quarterly*, 53(4), 654-675. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1533-8525.2012.01245.x>
- ◆ Devlin, M. (2010). Young people, youth work and youth policy: European developments. *Youth Studies Ireland*, 5(2), 66-82.
- ◆ Devos, G., Bouckenooghe, D., Engels, N., Hotton, G., & Aelterman, A. (2007). An assessment of well-being of principals in Flemish primary schools. *Journal of Educational Administration*, 45(1), 33-61. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09578230710722449>
- ◆ Diaz, J., Suarez, C., & Valencia, L. (2019). Culturally responsive teaching: A framework for educating diverse audiences. *EDIS*, 2019(5), 1-5.
- ◆ DomNwachukwu, C. S. (2010). *An introduction to multicultural education: From theory to practice*. Rowman & Littlefield Publishers.
- ◆ Engels, N., Hotton, G., Devos, G., Bouckenooghe, D., & Aelterman, A. (2008). Principals in schools with a positive school culture. *Educational Studies*, 34(3), 159-174. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03055690701811263>
- ◆ Erickson, F. (1987). Conceptions of school culture: An overview. *Educational Administration Quarterly*, 23(4), 11-24. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013161X87023004003>
- ◆ Essed, Ph. (1996). *Diversity: Gender, Color, and Culture*. University of Massachusetts Press.
- ◆ European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education (2017). *Inclusive Early Childhood Education: New Insights and Tools – Contributions from a European Study*. <https://www.european-agency.org/resources/publications/inclusive-early-childhood-education-new-insights-and-tools-contributions>

- ◆ European Commission (2019). Key competences for lifelong learning. Publications Office. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2766/569540>
- ◆ Fandrem, H., Tvedt, M. S., Virtanen, T., & Bru, E. (2021). Intentions to quit upper secondary education among first generation immigrants and native Norwegians: The role of loneliness and peer victimization. *Social Psychology of Education*, 24, 489-509. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11218-021-09614-1>
- ◆ Fine-Davis, M., & Faas, D. (2014). Equality and diversity in the classroom: A comparison of students' and educators' attitudes in six European countries. *Social Indicators Research*, 119(3), 1319-1334. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11205-013-0547-9>
- ◆ Finnish Youth Act 1285/2016 (2018). Retrieved from: <https://www.finlex.fi/fi/laki/alkup/2016/20161285>
- ◆ Fox, J., & Hoffman, W. (2011). *The differentiated instruction book of lists*. Jossey Bass.
- ◆ Fultz, D. (2017). *Ten steps for genuine leadership in schools*. Routledge.
- ◆ Gay, G. (2010). *Culturally responsive teaching: Theory, research, and practice* (2nd edition). Educators College Press.
- ◆ Gay, G. (2018). *Culturally responsive teaching: Theory, research, and practice*. Educators College Press.
- ◆ Geeraerts, K., Tynjälä, P., & Heikkinen, H. L. (2018). Inter-generational learning of educators: what and how do educators learn from older and younger colleagues? *European Journal of Educator Education*, 41(4), 479-495. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02619768.2018.1448781>
- ◆ Geerlings, J., Thijs, J., & Verkuyten, M. (2019). Preaching and practicing multicultural education: Predicting students' outgroup attitudes from perceived educator norms and perceived educator-classmate relations. *Journal of School Psychology*, 75, 89-103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsp.2019.07.003>
- ◆ Gharabaghi, K. (2008). Professional issues in child and youth care. *Child & Youth Services*, 30(3-4), 145-163. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01459350903107285>
- ◆ Gruber, S. (2015). Cultural competence in institutional care for youths: Experts with ambivalent positions. *Nordic Social Work Research*, 6(2), 89-101. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2156857X.2015.1109541>
- ◆ Gruenert, Š., & Whitaker, T. (2017). *School culture recharged: Strategies to energize your staff and culture*. ASCD.
- ◆ Guimond, S., Sablionniere, R., & Nugier, A. (2014). Living in a multicultural world: Intergroup ideologies and the societal context of intergroup relations. *European Review of Social Psychology*, 25, 142-188. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10463283.2014.957578>
- ◆ Gutvajn, N., Kovačević Lepojević, M. & Mišćević, G. (2021). Školska klima i motivacija za učenje matematike i prirodnih nauka: medijacija vršnjačkog nasilja. U I. Đerić, N. Gutvajn, S. Jošić, & N. Ševa (Ur.), *TIMSS 2019 u Srbiji* (str. 107-123). Institut za pedagoška istraživanja.
- ◆ Gwayi-Chore, M. C., Del Villar, E. L., Fraire, L. C., Waters, C., Andrasik, M. P., Pfeiffer, J., Slyker, J., Mello, S. P., Barnabas, R., Moise, E., & Heffron, R. (2021). "Being a person of color in this institution is exhausting": Defining and optimizing the learning climate to support diversity, equity, and inclusion at the university of Washington school of public health. *Frontiers in public health*, 9(642477), 1-12.

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2021.642477>

◆ Halpin, A.W. & Croft, D.B. (1963). The organizational climate of schools. Midwest Administration Center, University of Chicago.

◆ Hamm, J. V., & Faircloth, B. S. (2005). The role of friendship in adolescents' sense of school belonging. *New Directions for Child and Adolescent Development*, 2005(107), 61-78. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cd.121>

◆ Hammer, M. R., Bennett, M. J., & Wiseman, R. (2003). Measuring intercultural sensitivity: The intercultural development inventory. *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, 27(4), 421-443. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0147-1767\(03\)00032-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0147-1767(03)00032-4)

◆ Hamre, B. K., Pianta, R. C., Downer, R. C., DeCoster, J., Mashburn, A. J., Jones, S. M., et al. (2013). Teaching through interactions: Testing a developmental framework of educator effectiveness in over 4,000 classrooms. *The Elementary School Journal*, 113(4), 461-487. <https://doi.org/10.6027/ANP2018-74210.1086/669616>

◆ Hancock, C. H. H., Midthassel, U. V., & Fandrem, H. (2021). Upper secondary educators' experiences promoting belonging and engagement in culturally diverse classrooms. *Acta Didactica Norden*, 15(2), 1-22. <http://doi.org/10.5617/adno.8381>

◆ Hargreaves, A. (1994). *Changing educators, changing times: Educators' work and culture in the postmodern age*. Educators College Press.

◆ Hargreaves, D. H. (1995). School culture, school effectiveness and school improvement. *School effectiveness and school improvement*, 6(1), 23-46. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0924345950060102>

◆ Hemmings, B., & Woodcock, S. (2011). Preservice educators' views of inclusive education: A content analysis. *Australasian Journal of Special Education*, 35(2), 103-116. <https://doi.org/10.1375/ajse.35.2.103>

◆ Hlatywayo, L., & Muranda, Z. A. (2014). An evaluation of the Leonard Cheshire Zimbabwe Trust (LCZT) pilot inclusive education programme in Zimbabwe: The perspective of educators and heads. (PART A). *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science (IOSR-JHSS)*, 19(11), 124-138.

◆ Howard, T. C. (2010). *Why race and culture matter in schools: Closing the achievement gap in America's classrooms*. Educators College Press.

◆ Hrvatić, N. (2007). Interkulturalna pedagogija: nove paradigme. U V. Previšić, N. Šoljan, N. Hrvatić (Ur.), *Pedagogija prema cjeloživotnom obrazovanju i društvu znanja* (str. 41-58). Hrvatsko pedagoško društvo.

◆ Isaacs, M. R., & Benjamin, M. P. (1991). *Towards a Culturally Competent System of Care. Volume II: Programs Which Utilize Culturally Competent Principles*. Georgetown University Child Development Center.

◆ Jackson, T. O., & Boutte, G. S. (2018). Exploring culturally relevant/responsive pedagogy as praxis in educator education. *The New Educator*, 14(2), 87-90. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1547688X.2018.1426320>

◆ Jennings, P. A., Frank, J. L., Snowberg, K. E., Coccia, M. A., & Greenberg, M. T. (2013). Improving classroom learning environments by Cultivating Awareness and Resilience in Education (CARE): results of a randomized controlled trial. *School Psychology Quarterly*, 28(4), 374-390. <https://doi.org/10.1037/spq0000035>

◆ Jennings, P. A., Snowberg, K. E., Coccia, M. A., & Greenberg, M. T. (2011). Improving classroom learning environments by cultivating awareness and resilience in education (CARE): Results of two pilot studies. *The Journal of classroom*

interaction, 37-48.

◆ Jerald, C. D. (2006). School culture: "The hidden curriculum". Center for Comprehensive School Reform and Improvement. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED495013.pdf>

◆ Johnson, C. S., Sdunzik, J., Bynum, C., Kong, N., & Qin, X. (2021). Learning about culture together: enhancing educators' cultural competence through collaborative educator study groups. *Professional development in education*, 47(1), 177-190. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19415257.2019.1696873>

◆ Johnson, Y. M., & Munch, S. (2009). Fundamental contradictions in cultural competence. *Social Work*, 54(3), 220-231. <https://doi.org/10.1093/sw/54.3.220>

◆ Jurčić, M. (2014). Kompetentnost nastavnika-pedagoške i didaktičke dimenzije. *Pedagogijska istraživanja*, 11(1), 77-91.

◆ Juvonen, J., Kogachi, K., & Graham, S. (2018). When and how do students benefit from ethnic diversity in middle school? *Child Development*, 89(4), 1268-1282. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cdev.12834>

◆ Kennedy, E., Bronte-Tinkew, J., & Matthews, G. (2007). Enhancing cultural competence in out-of-school time programs: What is it, and why is it important. *Research to Results*.

◆ Khalifa, M. A., Gooden, M. A., & Davis, J. E. (2016). Culturally responsive school leadership: A synthesis of the literature. *Review of Educational Research*, 86(4), 1272-1311. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3102/0034654316630383>

◆ Kiefer, S. M., Alley, K. M., & Ellerbrock, C. R. (2015). Educator and peer support for young adolescents' motivation, engagement, and school belonging. *RMLE Online*, 38(8), 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19404476.2015.11641184>

◆ Kozina, A., Vidmar, M., Veldin, M. (2020). Social, emotional and intercultural/transcultural learning in a European perspective: Core concepts of the HAND in HAND project. In *Social, emotional and intercultural competencies for inclusive school environments across Europe: Relationships matter* (pp. 107-130). Verlag Dr. Kovač.

◆ Krasilnikov, I. M. (2021). Forming the fundamentals of social culture and cultural competence in school students in the process of mastering the content of musical pieces. *Laplace em Revista*, 7(3D), 50-59. <https://doi.org/10.24115/S2446-6220202173D1690p.50-59>

◆ Krueger, M. (2007). Questioning my presence in multicultural youth work. *Qualitative inquiry*, 13(8), 1189-1208. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1077800407304507>

◆ Kumar, R., Zusho, A., & Bondie, R. (2018). Weaving cultural relevance and achievement motivation into inclusive classroom cultures. *Educational Psychologist*, 53(2), 78-96. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00461520.2018.1432361>

◆ Ladson-Billings, G. (2014). Culturally relevant pedagogy 2.0: aka the remix. *Harvard educational review*, 84(1), 74-84. <https://doi.org/10.17763/haer.84.1.p2rj131485484751>

◆ Leithwood, K. (2001). School leadership in the context of accountability policies. *International Journal of Leadership in Education*, 4(3), 217-235. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603120110057082>

◆ Lerner, R. M., Lerner, J. V., Almerigi, J., & Theokas, C. (2006). Dynamics of individual ↔ context relations in human development: A developmental systems

perspective. In J. C. Thomas, D. L. Segal, & M. Hersen (Eds.), *Comprehensive Handbook of Personality and Psychopathology, Vol. 1, Personality and Everyday Functioning* (pp. 23–43). John Wiley & Sons, Inc.

◆ Loreman, T., Forlin, C., & Sharma, U. (2014). Measuring indicators of inclusive education: A systematic review of the literature. *Measuring Inclusive Education*, 3, 165-187. <https://doi.org/10.1108/S1479-363620140000003024>

◆ MacNeil, A. J., Prater, D. L., & Busch, S. (2009). The effects of school culture and climate on student achievement. *International Journal of Leadership in Education*, 12(1), 73-84. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/13603120701576241>

◆ Macura, S., Čuk, I., & Peček, M. (2020) Beliefs of student educators in Serbia and Slovenia about supporting vulnerable pupils in learning and social participation. *European Journal of Special Needs Education*, 35(1), 55-69. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08856257.2019.1607660>

◆ Manning, M. L., Baruth, L. G., & Lee, G. L. (2017). *Multicultural education of children and adolescents*. Routledge.

◆ Maslowski, R. (2001). *School culture and school performance: An explorative study into the organizational culture of secondary schools and their effects*. Twente University Press.

◆ Maslowski, R. (2006). A review of inventories for diagnosing school culture. *Journal of Educational Administration*, 44(1), 6-35. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09578230610642638>

◆ Mattingly, M., Stuart, C., & VanderVen, K. (2012). Competencies for professional child and youth work practitioners: An overview. *Journal of Child and Youth Care Work*, 24, 16-24.

◆ Mehrotra, G., R., Hudson, K D., & Self, J. M. (2018). A critical examination of key assumptions underlying diversity and social justice courses in social work. *Journal of Progressive Human Services*, 30(2), 127-147. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10428232.2018.1507590>

◆ Melendres, M. (2020). Cultural competence in social work practice: Exploring the challenges of newly employed social work professionals. *Journal of Ethnic & Cultural Diversity in Social Work*, 31(2), 108-120. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15313204.2020.1855492>

◆ Metropolitan Center for Urban Education (2008). *Culturally Responsive Classroom Management Strategies*. <https://www.asdn.org/wp-content/uploads/Culturally-Responsive-Classroom-Mgmt-Strat2.pdf>

◆ Metz, J. (2017). The professionalism of professional youth work and the role of values. *Social Work & Society*, 15(2), 1-16.

◆ Miravet, L. M., & García, O. M. (2013). The role of educators' shared values and objectives in promoting intercultural and inclusive school cultures: a case study. *International Journal of Qualitative Studies in Education*, 26(10), 1373-1386. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/09518398.2012.731535>

◆ Moos, R. H. (1979). *Evaluating educational environments*. Jossey-Bass.

◆ Moule, J. (2011). *Cultural competence: A primer for educators* (2nd ed.). Wadsworth Cengage Learning.

◆ Munniksma, A., Scheepers, P., Stark, T. H., & Tolsma, J. (2017). The impact of adolescents' classroom and neighborhood ethnic diversity on same-and cross-

ethnic friendships within classrooms. *Journal of Research on Adolescence*, 27(1), 20-33. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jora.12248>

◆ National Association of Social Workers. (2015). *NASW standards and indicators for cultural competence in social work practice*. NASW Press.

◆ Nelson, J. A., & Bustamante, R. B. (2008). The school-wide cultural competence observation checklist for professional school counselors: An assessment tool for leading culturally and linguistically diverse schools. In G. R. Walz, J. C. Bleuer, & R. K. Yep (Eds.), *Compelling counseling interventions: Celebrating VISTAS' fifth anniversary* (pp. 211-220). *Counseling Outfitters*.

◆ Nelson, J. A., Bustamante, R. B., Wilson, E. D., & Onwuegbuzie, A. J. (2008). The school-wide cultural competence observation checklist for professional school counselors: An exploratory factor analysis. *Professional school counseling*, 11(4), 207-217. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2156759X0801100401>

◆ Nelson, J. A., Bustamante, R., Sawyer, C., & Sloan, E. D. (2015). Cultural competence and school counselor training: A collective case study. *Journal of Multicultural Counseling and Development*, 43(3), 221-235. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jmcd.12016>

◆ Nishina, A., Lewis, J. A., Bellmore, A., & Witkow, M. R. (2019). Ethnic diversity and inclusive school environments. *Educational Psychologist*, 54(4), 306-321. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00461520.2019.1633923>

◆ Nybell, L. M. & Gray, S.S. (2004). Race, place, space: Meanings of cultural competence in three child welfare agencies. *Social Work*, 49(1), 17-26. <https://doi.org/10.1093/sw/49.1.17>

◆ Nylund, D. (2006) Critical multiculturalism, whiteness, and social work. *Journal of Progressive Human Services*, 17(2), 27-42. https://doi.org/10.1300/J059v17n02_03

◆ OECD. (2015). *Immigrant students at school: Easing the journals towards integration (OECD Reviews of Migrant Education)*. OECD Publishing.

◆ OECD. (2016). *PISA 2015 results (volume I): Excellence and equity in education*. OECD Publishing.

◆ OECD. (2019). *TALIS 2018 results (Volume I): Educators and school leaders as lifelong learners*. Paris: OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/1d0bc92a-en>

◆ Okagbue, E. F., Wang, M., & Ezechikulo, U. P. (2022). Does school bullying show lack of effective multicultural education in the school curriculum? *International Journal of Educational Research Open*, 3, 100178. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijedro.2022.100178>

◆ Ord, J. (2007). *Youth work process, product and practice*. Lyme Regis: Russell House.

◆ Óskarsdóttir, E., Donnelly, V., Turner-Cmuchal, M., & Florian, L. (2020). Inclusive school leaders – their role in raising the achievement of all learners. *Journal of Educational Administration*, 58(5), 521-537. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jea-10-2019-0190>

◆ Outley, C. W., & Floyd, M. F. (2002). The home they live in: Inner city children's views on the influence of parenting strategies on their leisure behavior. *Leisure Sciences*, 24(2), 161-179. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01490400252900130>

◆ Outley, C. W., & Witt, P. A. (2006). Working with diverse youth: Guidelines for achieving youth cultural competency in recreation services. *Journal of Park and*

- Recreation Administration, 24(4), 111-126.
- ◆ Palmer, S., & Pitts, J. (2006). Othering' the brothers: black youth, racial solidarity, and gun crime. *Youth and policy*, 9(1), 5-21.
 - ◆ Paolillo, A., Silva, S. A., & Pasini, M. (2016). Promoting safety participation through diversity and inclusion climates. *International Journal of Workplace Health Management*, 9(3), 308-327. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/IJWHM-01-2015-0002>
 - ◆ Patel, R. (2018). Measuring cultural competency in educators: The educators scale of student diversity (Doctoral dissertation). Seattle Pacific University.
 - ◆ Pedersen, P. (2000). A handbook for developing multicultural awareness. American Association for Counseling.
 - ◆ Peterson, K. D., & Deal, T. E. (2009). The shaping school culture field book (2nd Edition). Josset-Bass.
 - ◆ Peterson, K. D., & Deal, T. E. (2016). The shaping school culture field book (3rd edition). Josset-Bass.
 - ◆ Petrie, K. (2014). The relationship between school climate and student bullying. *TEACH Journal of Christian Education*, 8(1), 26-35.
 - ◆ Petrović, D. (2018). Sticanje interkulturalnih kompetencija u svetlu razvojnog modela interkulturalne osetljivosti Milтона Beneta. *Godišnjak Pedagoškog fakulteta u Vranju*, 9(2), 27-44.
 - ◆ Pettigrew, T. F., & Tropp, L. R. (2006). A meta-analytic test of intergroup contact theory. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 90, 751-783. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.90.5.751>
 - ◆ Pettigrew, T. F., Tropp, L. R., Wagner, U., & Christ, O. (2011). Recent advances in intergroup contact theory. *International journal of intercultural relations*, 35(3), 271-280. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijintrel.2011.03.001>
 - ◆ Pirchio, S., Passiatore, Y., Panno, A., Maricchiolo, F., & Carrus, G. (2018). A chip off the old block: Parents' subtle ethnic prejudice predicts children's implicit prejudice. *Frontiers in psychology*, 9, 110. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.00110>
 - ◆ Plaut, V.C., Thomas, K.M., Hurd, K., & Romano, C.A. (2018). Docolor blindness and multiculturalism remedy or foster discrimination and racism?. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 27(3), 200-206. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0963721418766068>
 - ◆ Ponterotto, J. G. (2010). Multicultural personality: An evolving theory of optimal functioning in culturally heterogeneous societies. *The Counseling Psychologist*, 38(5), 714-758. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0011000009359203>
 - ◆ Popović-Ćitić, B., Bukvić Branković, L., Kovačević-Lepojević, M., Paraušić, A., Stojanović, M., & Kovačević, M. (2021). Promocija i uvažavanje različitosti i ravnopravnosti u školskom okruženju u cilju prevencije govora mržnje i diskriminacije kod mladih: slučaj beogradske opštine Stari grad. CEPORA – Centar za pozitivan razvoj dece i omladine.
 - ◆ Pravilnik o standardima kompetencija direktora ustanova obrazovanja i vaspitanja (2013). Službeni glasnik, br. 38/2013. <https://zuov.gov.rs/download/pravilnik-o-standardima-kompetencija-di-rektora-ustanova-obrazovanja-i-vaspitanja/>
 - ◆ Prose, J. (1999). The evolution of school culture research. In J. Prosser (Ed.), *School culture* (pp. 1-14). Paul Chapman.
 - ◆ Purić, D. (2017). Usavršavanje učitelja u funkciji razvijanja interkulturalnosti.

Zbornik radova Pedagoškog fakulteta u Užicu, 20(19), 75-92.

◆ Putnam, R. (2007). E Pluribus Unum: Diversity and community in the twenty-first century. The 2006 Johan Skytte prize lecture. *Scandinavian Political Studies*, 30(2), 137-174. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9477.2007.00176.x>

◆ Quaiser-Pohl, C. (2013). Diversity in education and the concept of "diversity" as a topic for educational science studies. In C. Quaiser-Pohl, V. Ruthsatz, & M. Endepohls-Ulpe (Eds.), *Diversity and diversity management in education – A European perspective* (pp. 9-22). Waxmann.

◆ Radulović, M., Radulović, L., & Stančić, M. (2022). Can educator support reduce inequalities in education? Re-examining the relationship between cultural capital and achievement. *British Journal of Sociology of Education*, 43(7), 1012-1031. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01425692.2022.2092449>.

◆ Rannala, I., Gilsenan, M., Martinson, M., & Roslöf, U. (2019). Key Concepts of Youth Work in Youth Work Curricula. https://vuir.vu.edu.au/39923/7/Chapter_nlib-digar_406371.pdf

◆ Robak, S., Sievers, I., & Hauenschild, K. (2013). Einleitung diversity education: Zugänge und Spannungsfelder [Introduction diversity education: Approaches and areas of tension]. In K. Hausenschild, I. Sievers, & S. Robak (Eds.), *Diversity education. Zugänge – Perspektiven Beispiele [Diversity education. Approaches – Perspectives – Examples]* (pp. 15–35). Brandes & Apsel.

◆ Robiyansah, I. E. (2020). The development of inclusive education management model: Practical guidelines for learning in inclusive school. *Journal of Education and Learning (EduLearn)*, 14(1), 80-86. <https://doi.org/10.11591/edulearn.v14i1.13505>

◆ Rodríguez-Izquierdo, R. M. (2018). Researching the links between social-emotional learning and intercultural education: Strategies for enacting a culturally relevant teaching. *Intercultural Education*, 29(5-6), 609-623. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14675986.2018.1528527>

◆ Rutter, M. (1979). *Fifteen thousand hours: Secondary schools and their effects on children*. Harvard University Press.

◆ Saylık, A., Polatcan, M., & Saylık, N. (2016). Diversity management and respect for diversity at schools. *International Journal of Progressive Education*, 12(1), 51-63.

◆ Sayer, N. J. (2014). *Development of an instrument that supports and monitors inclusive cultures; policies and practices in a Western Cape school* (Doctoral dissertation). University of the Western Cape.

◆ Schachner, M. K. (2019). From equality and inclusion to cultural pluralism – Evolution and effects of cultural diversity perspectives in schools. *European Journal of Developmental Psychology*, 16(1), 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17405629.2017.1326378>

◆ Schachner, M. K., Juang, L., Moffitt, U., & van de Vijver, F. J. R. (2018). Schools as acculturative and developmental contexts for youth of immigrant and refugee background. *European Psychologist*, 23(1), 44-56. <https://doi.org/10.1027/1016-9040/a000312>

◆ Schachner, M. K., Noack, P., Van de Vijver, F. J. R., & Eckstein, K. (2016). Cultural diversity climate and psychological adjustment at school-equality and inclusion versus cultural pluralism. *Child Development*, 87(4), 1175-1191. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/cdev.12536>

- ◆ Schachner, M. K., Schwarzenhal, M., van de Vijver, F. J. R., & Noack, P. (2019). How all students can belong and achieve: Effects of the cultural diversity climate amongst students of immigrant and nonimmigrant background in Germany. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 111(4), 703-716. <https://doi.org/10.1037/edu0000303>
- ◆ Scherer, R. (2020). The case for good discipline? Evidence on the interplay between disciplinary climate, socioeconomic status, and science achievement from PISA 2015. In T. S. Frones, A. Pettersen, J. Radišić & N. Buchholtz (Eds.), *Equity, equality and diversity in the Nordic model of education* (pp. 197-224). Springer, Cham.
- ◆ Schoen, L. T., & Teddlie, C. (2008). A new model of school culture: A response to a call for conceptual clarity. *School effectiveness and school improvement*, 19(2), 129-153. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09243450802095278>
- ◆ Schuelka, M. J. (2018). Implementing inclusive education. Knowledge, evidence and learning for development. https://opendocs.ids.ac.uk/opendocs/bitstream/handle/20.500.12413/14230/374_Implementing_Inclusive_Education.pdf?sequence=1
- ◆ Shaw, C. R. & McKay, H. D. (1942). *Juvenile delinquency and urban areas*. University of Chicago Press.
- ◆ Sidler, P., Baysu, G., Kassiş, W., Janousch, C., Chouvati, R., Govaris, C., Graf, U., & Rietz, C. (2022). Minority and majority adolescents' attitudes toward mutual acculturation and its association with psychological adjustment. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 51(8), 1511-1535. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10964-022-01604-6>
- ◆ Smith, H., & Pettigrew, T. F. (2011). A meta-analytic critique of relative deprivation. Unpublished paper, Department of Psychology, Sonoma States University.
- ◆ Smith, J., & Soule, K. E. (2016). Incorporating cultural competence & youth program volunteers: A literature review. *Journal of Youth Development*, 11(1), 20-34. <https://doi.org/10.5195/jyd.2016.431>
- ◆ Solbue, V., Helleve, I., & Smith, K. (2017). "In this class we are so different that I can be myself!" Intercultural dialogue in a first grade upper secondary school in Norway. *Education Inquiry*, 8(2), 137-150. <https://doi.org/10.1080/20004508.2017.1290894>
- ◆ Standardi kompetencija za procenu kompetencija nastavnika i njihovog profesionalnog razvoja (2011). *Službeni glasnik*, br. 5/2011. http://www.cep.edu.rs/sites/default/files/Standardi_kompetencija_za_profesiju_nastavnika.pdf
- ◆ Stier, J. (2003). Internationalisation, ethnic diversity and the acquisition of intercultural competencies. *Intercultural Education*, 14(1), 77-91. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/1467598032000044674>.
- ◆ Stratford, R. (1990). Creating a positive school ethos. *Educational Psychology in Practice*, 5(4), 183-191. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0266736900050404>
- ◆ Sue, D. W., & Sue, D. (2012). *Counseling the culturally diverse: Theory and practice*. John Wiley & Sons.
- ◆ Sue, D. W., Rasheed, M. N., & Rasheed, J. M. (2018). *Multicultural social work practice: A competency-based approach to diversity and social justice*. John Wiley & Sons, Inc. Hoboken.

- ◆ Wilks, T. (2015). Diversity and differences. In L. Bell & T. Hafford-Letchfield (Eds). *Ethics, Values and Social Work Practice* (pp. 90-101). Open University Press.
- ◆ Williams, C. C. (2006). The epistemology of cultural competence. *Families in Society: The Journal of Contemporary Social Services*, 87(2), 209-220. <https://doi.org/10.1606/1044-3894.3514>
- ◆ Williams, R. M., Jr. (1947). The reduction of intergroup tensions. Social Science Research Council.
- ◆ Wood, J., Westwood, S., & Thompson, G. (2014). *Youth work: Preparation for practice*. Routledge.
- ◆ Yang Hansen, K., Radišić, J., Liu, X., & Glassow, L. N. (2020). Exploring diversity in the relationships between educator quality and job satisfaction in the Nordic countries – Insights from TALIS 2013 and 2018. In T. S. Frones, A. Pettersen, J. Radišić & N. Buchholtz (Eds.), *Equity, equality and diversity in the Nordic model of education* (pp. 99-137). Springer, Cham.
- ◆ Young, T.J., & Schartner, A. (2014). The effects of cross-cultural communication education on international students' adjustment and adaptation. *Journal of Multilingual & Multicultural Development*, 35(6), 547-562. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01434632.2014.884099>
- ◆ Zakonom o osnovama sistema obrazovanja i vaspitanja ("Sl. glasnik RS", br. 88/2017, 27/2018 – dr. zakon, 10/2019, 27/2018 - dr. zakon i 6/2020). https://www.paragraf.rs/propisi/zakon_o_osnovama_sistema_obrazovanja_i_vaspitanja.html
- ◆ Zhu, C., Devos, G., & Li, Y. (2011). Educator perceptions of school culture and their organizational commitment and well-being in a Chinese school. *Asia Pacific Education Review*, 12(2), 319-328. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12564-011-9146-0>
- ◆ Zhu, C., Devos, G., & Tondeur, J. (2014). Examining school culture in Flemish and Chinese primary schools. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 42(4), 557-575. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1741143213502190>
- ◆ Zhu, G., & Peng, Z. (2020). Counternarratives: Culturally responsive pedagogy and critical caring in one urban school. *The sage handbook of critical pedagogies*, 854-868.
- ◆ Zubulake, D. M. (2017). Building blocks of professionalism: Values, principles, and ethics in youth work. *Journal of Youth Development*, 12(1), 9-17. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5195/jyd.2017.483>

diversity in contemporary legal frameworks: EU level

Milica Kovačević

Introduction

At the moment, almost every state in Europe is characterized by multi-ethnicity, multilingualism and multiculturalism, or by cultural diversity in the broadest possible sense. Such a state of affairs is conditioned by modern trends that require cooperation between countries and dictate intensive migration processes, but also by the constant exchange of ideas, cultural content and values. It is indisputable that at this level of civilizational development, the intertwining of many cultures is considered an advantage and a valuable resource for the further progress of humanity, and not an obstacle. However, this does not negate the fact that cultural diversity requires adjustments so that members of different races, nations, religions and other groups can truly exercise their rights and enjoy the freedoms that belong to every citizen regardless of personal traits, origin and material circumstances. Therefore, multiculturalism requires complex adjustments of the normative framework within which mechanisms should be envisaged for fostering equality regardless of individual characteristics. Adjustments of the normative framework are being made at the universal, European and national levels. This process has been going on for several decades and its end is not noticeable, given the new and increasingly complex needs that everyday life brings. Economic crises, wars and technological progress continuously put additional demands on the legal system, requiring constant changes, but also the development of new paradigms harmonized with the current moment. The legal analysis that follows focuses on legal documents that encourage and nurture cultural diversity within the three sectors crucial for the realization of human rights. These are the sectors of education, social services and youth work.

Documents of the organization of United Nations – social care and the right to education

We begin the review of international documents with a summary analysis of documents adopted by the United Nations as the most important universal organization in the present time. Namely, the period after the Second World War is characterized by the founding of the United Nations as an international organization that, in addition to preserving world peace and international cooperation, pleads for the respect of human rights in the broadest possible sense.

The realization of any group of human rights is based on the assumption that all human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights. Hence, the whole system of human rights derives from the respect for the individual differences of each human being, which must not be an obstacle to the realization of rights and the enjoyment of freedoms. Nevertheless, the organization of the United Nations recognizes the de facto inequality of members of certain groups and has adopted some documents that explicitly prohibit all forms of discrimination and plead for the eradication of racial, gender and all other forms of inequality.

The following documents are recognized as most relevant:

- ◆ Universal Declaration of Human Rights, 1948
- ◆ International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, 1966
- ◆ International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, 1966
- ◆ International Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination, 1965
- ◆ Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women, 2016
- ◆ Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD), 2006
- ◆ Convention against Discrimination in Education, 1960
- ◆ UNESCO Guidelines for Intercultural Education, 2006
- ◆ Convention on the Rights of the Child, 1989
- ◆ Universal Declaration on Cultural Diversity, 2001
- ◆ Agenda for Sustainable Development until 2030, 2015

The Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UN, 1948) is based on the inviolable postulate that everyone is entitled to human rights and freedoms, without distinction of any kind, such as race, sex, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, property, birth or other status.

International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (UN, 1966), stipulates that the law will prohibit any advocacy of national, racial or religious hatred that constitutes incitement to discrimination, hostility or violence. The Covenant obliges state parties to ensure equal rights for women and men. It is envisaged that the restriction of rights in extraordinary circumstances of public danger cannot take on extensive proportions and that restrictions on rights and freedoms must not be based on discriminatory grounds, for example, race, color, gender, language, religion or social origin.

International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (UN, 1966), guarantees the exercise of economic, social and cultural rights without any discrimination in respect of race, color, sex, language, religion, political or other opinions, national or social origin, property status, birth or any other status (Art. 2).

International Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination (UN, 1965), proclaims the prohibition of all forms of racial discrimination and the promotion of racial discrimination as desirable or acceptable conduct. State parties are to undertake, in accordance with their needs, special and concrete measures in the social, economic, cultural and other fields, so that they ensure the development or protection of certain racial groups, or individuals belonging to these groups, in order to protect their human rights and their freedoms. Measures may not result in the maintenance of unequal or different positions for different racial groups, once the objectives for which these measures were originally taken are achieved.

Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women

(UN, 1979), obliges states to take appropriate measures to eradicate unacceptable social patterns of behavior of men and women, and to eliminate prejudice, traditional customs and practices based on the notion of inferiority or superiority of one or the other sex, as well as the established expectations about the roles of men and women. Measures should be implemented in order to reform family education so that it includes an adequate understanding of motherhood as a social function and respect for the common responsibility of men and women in raising children, implying that in all cases the best interests of the child must be taken into account. An important factor in combating discrimination against women is the education system, as a result of which states are obliged to take measures to eliminate discrimination against women and to provide them with equal rights as men in education, especially: equal conditions in career and career guidance; in terms of opportunities for learning and obtaining diplomas in educational institutions of all categories, both in rural and urban areas; availability of equal curricula; removing the traditional understanding of the roles of men and women at all levels and in all forms of education by encouraging the creation of mixed classes and by revising textbooks and school curricula and adapting teaching methods; reducing the drop-out rate of girls and women and so on.

The Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UN, 2006) prohibits all forms of discrimination against persons with disabilities and advocates for their equality. The basic principles are: respect for dignity, respect for personal abilities and independence of persons with disabilities, social inclusion, respect for differences and acceptance of persons with disabilities as an inherent segment of human diversity; access to all resources, equality of women and men and respect for the evolving capacities of children with disabilities.

The Convention against Discrimination in Education (UNESCO, 1960) condemns all forms of discrimination in education, emphasizing the need to promote equality in terms of educational opportunities and access to all levels of education. However, Art. 2 of the Convention supports the establishment of separate institutions for the purpose of educating members of different sexes, and also the establishment of special institutions for religious or linguistic reasons, but only if attending such institutions is voluntary and if they are not organized according to discriminatory criteria. The education must be accessible to everyone without administrative barriers, while primary education is compulsory and free of charge. States undertake to encourage the education of persons without primary or incomplete primary education and to enable the continuation of education in accordance with the individual traits of students. Article 5 obliges states to ensure that education is aimed at the full development of the individual and the strengthening of respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms, and also to promote understanding, tolerance and friendship among peoples, racial and religious groups.

Furthermore, citizens are guaranteed the right to educate children in institutions that respect their personal beliefs, while no one can be forced into a religious education that is contrary to his personal beliefs. Finally, members of national minorities are guaranteed the right to attend special institutions and study on the languages of national minorities, but this must not prevent members of

national minorities from understanding the language of the majority group and actively participating in the social life of the community as a whole. Also, if special institutions for members of national minorities are established, the curriculum in such institutions cannot be based on lower standards compared to educational institutions attended by the majority of the population, while attending such institutions must be voluntary.

The **UNESCO Guidelines for Intercultural Education** (2006) are based on the principle that multiculturalism covers cultural diversity as a basic feature of human society, while interculturalism is a dynamic concept that refers to ever-changing relationships between members of different cultural groups that can contain unique cultural expression and mutual respect. The document contains three basic guidelines, with the first guideline stipulating that intercultural education is education that respects the cultural identity of students, by providing culturally appropriate and quality education for each individual. According to the second guideline, intercultural education provides all students with cultural skills and knowledge in order to become active and responsible citizens of society. The third guideline stipulates that intercultural education provides knowledge, attitudes and skills that will enable students to develop respect, cooperation and understanding among individuals and ethnic, social and cultural groups and nations.

UN Convention on the Rights of the Child (1989), is a document that comprehensively defines the minimum standards and the protection mechanisms in all areas important for the development and exercise of the rights of minors. The Convention obliges the contracting parties to ensure the exercise and protection of the rights of every child without any discrimination, regardless of race, color, sex, language, religion ... or another status of the child, his parent or legal guardians (Art. 2).

The general comment of the UN Committee on the Rights of the Child (No. 9, 2006) on the rights of children with disabilities, among other things, emphasizes the need to provide special protection for girls with disabilities. The commentary points out that children with disabilities are often discriminated against in multiple ways, given that the problems of these children are particularly complicated if they live in rural areas or if they are of poor financial status. Also, isolating these children makes it difficult for them to be included in the formal education system, which in turn makes it difficult or even impossible for them to find employment and so further increases social exclusion. Therefore, states have special obligations towards children with disabilities and must pay special attention to their equality. The necessity of cooperation between different sectors was emphasized in order for children with disabilities to exercise all their rights and not just be limited to the rights in the field of narrowly understood social protection. It is noticed that the system of providing support for children with developmental disabilities is often disintegrated, which makes the child's position especially difficult, leading him to the situation of repeatedly turning to different services for similar forms of protection. States should support the work of civil sector in the field of protection of children with disabilities and organize educational campaigns to raise awareness of the need to fully respect the rights of these children.

It should be emphasized that children with disabilities claim the same status as all other children. Furthermore, not only do children with disabilities have the right to attend school, but the educational process must be such as to encourage their development and the realization of personal talents, as well as their mental and physical potential. Therefore, it is necessary to modify the teaching practice and train educators in regular schools in order to encourage the development of these children in the best possible way. At the same time, every child with developmental issues has the right for an individualized approach to be applied in order to develop communication skills, verbal capacities, ability to interact and the ability to solve various problems. People who work with children must monitor the child's progress, as well as how he communicates verbally and emotionally, in order to provide the best possible support for children's development.

The education of children with disabilities must be oriented towards the development of inclusive education within the standard and general education system, which does not mean that the needs of those children could be simply neglected. Namely, the general education system should strive to include children with disabilities, instead of a priori allocating them to special institutions, but, if necessary, inclusion in the general system may include specific support measures. However, the Committee on the Rights of the Child does not deny the factual situation in which not all the states are able to form an inclusive education system in the foreseeable future, due to existing constraints and insufficient resources. In connection with the above, it should be borne in mind that inclusion does not only mean the participation of children with disabilities in the general education system. On the contrary, inclusive education implies a system of values, principles and practices that provide quality education for all students, recognizing their very different personal and social predispositions. Hence, the system should primarily recognize student differences. Thus, inclusion may include the inclusion of students with disabilities in standard classes or the formation of special classes in standard schools, or maintaining a standard teaching process or teaching process with special segments of special education. Inclusion mustn't be equated with simply including students with disabilities in standard/general schools, without insight into the needs they may have. Special training is needed for educators and other school staff in order to fully enable them to develop an inclusive education system.

Universal Declaration on Cultural Diversity, adopted by the General Conference of the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization at its thirty-first session on 2 November 2001 is based on the assumption that respect for cultural diversity actually encourages and increases opportunities for personal development of all persons, not only in economic terms, but also in terms of personal and spiritual development of each individual.

The **UN Agenda for Sustainable Development** until 2030, which entered into force in 2016, promotes the intensive engagement of states in eradicating poverty, achieving full equality and overcoming the problems brought about by climate change. During the conception of the Agenda, attention has been given to the representation of the views of as many members of different groups as possible, such as: women, elderly citizens, young people, residents of rural areas, members

of the LGBTI population, Roma and others. Only some of the 17 goals envisaged by the agenda are: quality education - which includes providing inclusive and quality education and promoting lifelong learning opportunities; gender equality - which requires the achievement of essential gender equality and the empowerment of women and girls in the broadest possible sense and peace, justice and strong institutions - which includes promoting a peaceful and inclusive society, ensuring access to justice for all and building efficient and reliable institutions at all levels.

Council of Europe documents

The Council of Europe is an organization committed to respecting democratic values, rule of law and human rights, with cultural diversity being one of the cornerstones on which Europe has been built in the past and which must remain firmly rooted in its foundations. We begin with an overview of documents relevant to the social services sector and youth work, which is followed by a review of documents related to the exercise of the right to education.

The following documents are recognized as most valuable ones:

- ◆ European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, 1950
- ◆ Revised European Social Charter, 1996
- ◆ European Cultural Convention, 1954
- ◆ Reference Framework of Competences for Democratic Culture (RFCDC), 2013
- ◆ ECRI Recommendation on a general policy on combating racism and racial discrimination in and through school education, 2006
- ◆ Convention on the Participation of Foreigners in Public Life at Local Level, 1992
- ◆ Framework Convention for the Protection of National Minorities, 1994
- ◆ Recommendation of the Committee of Ministers of the Council of Europe to member states on "hate speech", 1997
- ◆ Recommendation of the Committee of Ministers to member states on the education of Roma and Travelers in Europe, 2009
- ◆ Recommendation of the Committee of Ministers to Member States on measures to combat discrimination on grounds of sexual orientation and gender identity, 2010
- ◆ Resolution on Access to Education and School for All Children, 2016
- ◆ Declaration of the Committee of Ministers on Cultural Diversity, 2000
- ◆ Declaration on Intercultural Dialogue and Conflict Prevention, 2003
- ◆ Declaration on 50 years of cultural cooperation in Europe, 2004

- ◆ Recommendation of the Committee of Ministers to member States on multilevel policies and governance for intercultural integration, 2022
- ◆ Recommendation of the Committee of Ministers to member states on youth participation and the future of civil society, 1997
- ◆ Recommendation of the Committee of Ministers to member States on protecting youth civil society and young people and supporting their participation in democratic processes, 2022
- ◆ Resolution of the Committee of Ministers on the youth sector strategy 2030, 2022
- ◆ Recommendation on supporting young refugees in transition to adulthood, 2019
- ◆ Recommendation of the Committee of Ministers to member states on research on young people's access to rights, 2016
- ◆ Recommendation on the access of young people from disadvantaged neighborhoods to social rights, 2015
- ◆ Resolution on the Youth Policy of the Council of Europe, 2008
- ◆ Council of Europe Charter on Education for Democratic Citizenship and Human Rights Education, 2010
- ◆ Recommendation of the Committee of Ministers to member states on the promotion and recognition of non-formal education/learning of young people, 2003
- ◆ European Youth Forum recommendations on social protection and young people in Europe, 2000

European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (Rome, 1950, abbreviated: ECHR), guarantees the enjoyment of rights and freedoms without discrimination on grounds such as: sex, race, color, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, affiliation with a national minority, property, birth or other status (Art. 14-Prohibition of Discrimination).

The case law of the **European Court of Human Rights**, which directly affects the eradication of practices and procedures that violate the equality of citizens at the national level, is also extremely important. In the educational context, Protocol No. 1 to the ECHR is of particular significance, specifically Art. 2 - The right to education, according to which no one can be deprived of the right to education, while the state respects the right of parents to ensure the content and conduct of the educational process in accordance with individual religious and philosophical beliefs.

Revised European Social Charter, as a document related to fundamental economic and social rights, attaches special importance to the protection of vulnerable categories of persons such as children, persons with disabilities and migrants. Article 15 of the Charter refers to the rights of persons with disabilities who, regardless of age or nature and extent of disability, should be provided with services to buster their independence, social integration and participation in community life. Therefore, states are obliged to take measures for education

and vocational training, within regular mechanisms whenever possible, or, if not possible, within special institutions, and to promote social integration and participation in the community of persons with disabilities by applying all necessary measures, as well as technical (Art. 15).

The Charter also defines the right of children and youth to social, legal and economical protection. Article 17 stipulates that states are obliged to provide children and young people with a stimulating environment for the development of their spiritual and physical potentials, in which sense states are called to provide adequate capacities, prevent abuse and exploitation of children, provide special support for children without families and guarantee free primary and secondary education.

The **European Cultural Convention** (Paris, 1954) is based on the premise that besides cultural cooperation through bilateral agreements, Europe should also nurture national languages, cultures and civilizations, as well as a unique European cultural heritage. Specifically, Art. 2 of the Convention stipulates that each state will support the study of the culture, language and civilization of other national groups on its territory, as well as that states will support the exchange of cultural knowledge and goods beyond their own borders. In addition, each of the states will strive to preserve cultural goods and values important for European culture as a whole within its competencies.

Council of Europe, **Standing Conference of European Ministers of Education Intercultural education: Managing diversity, strengthening democracy** 21st session Athens, Greece, -10 to 12 November 2003, Declaration by the European ministers of education on intercultural education in the new European context starts from the premise that Europe is characterized by social differences embodied in language, culture and religion. Existing differences, as well as multiculturalism, should actually be nurtured, avoiding the marginalization of any group. Despite that, the creators of the declaration are aware of the presence of xenophobia and racism in the education system, as a result of which respect for human rights, democratic values and intercultural education should be promoted even more decisively. In this regard, the declaration calls for: continued research on intercultural education, development of new methods and tools for intercultural learning, and supports the wide dissemination of good practices. It is necessary to preserve the European dimension of the educational process despite the ever-present globalization trends, while not neglecting the need for general cooperation and the promotion of Euro-Arab dialogue. That is why the declaration supports the understanding and encouragement of linguistic diversity in Europe. Intercultural education should include not only schools but also local communities, parents and students, because the importance of interculturality is not limited to the educational context, but interculturality should be a quality that characterizes society as a whole. In addition, technological progress and modern technological means should be applied as a helping resource to foster intercultural education.

Council of Europe Charter on Education for Democratic Citizenship and Human Rights Education, Recommendation CM/Rec (2010)7, adopted by the Committee of Ministers of the Council of Europe on 11 May 2010, assumes that education has a

key role to play in promoting fundamental values such as democracy and respect for human rights, and that it represents the strongest barrier against the rise of violence, extremism, xenophobia, discrimination and all types of intolerance.

Council of Europe's Reference Framework of Competences for Democratic Culture (RFCDC), originating in an initiative from Andorra (Council of Europe Standing Conference of Ministers of Education, Conclusions from the Andorran Conference Andorra la Vella, 7-8 February 2013) is based on the belief that the education system should prepare students to be active participants in democratic processes. This implies that students need to know and understand the challenges that they will face, as well as to be aware of the actions they need to avoid. The document contains materials that can be used to teach students so that they acquire competencies needed for active involvement in social life.

ECRI General Policy Recommendation No. 1 on combating racism, xenophobia, antisemitism and intolerance (ECRI, 1996) calls on states: to take measures in the field of education and information to strengthen the fight against racism, xenophobia, antisemitism and intolerance; to adopt a general policy of raising awareness of the wealth that cultural diversity brings to society; to undertake research on the nature, causes and manifestations of racism, xenophobia, antisemitism and intolerance at the local, regional and national levels; to ensure that curricula, for example in the field of history teaching, are designed to increase the level of respect for cultural diversity; to organize courses to improve understanding of different cultures and knowledge of the legal aspects of discrimination and raise awareness of prejudices that would be attended by those responsible for recruitment and promotion procedures, those in direct contact with the public and those responsible for adhering to standards, policies of non-discrimination and equal opportunities in a particular organization.

ECRI Recommendation No. 10 on a general policy on combating racism and racial discrimination in and through school education, ECRI (2006) suggests that states should ensure the fight against racism and racial discrimination in schools to become part of a permanent policy and establish a system for monitoring racist incidents in schools and for collecting data on incidents in order to design long-term policies to combat them.

Convention on the Participation of Foreigners in Public Life at Local Level, (Strasbourg, 1992), CETS 144 guarantees foreign residents the right to be consulted on important community issues and to be involved in all activities of social importance at the local level.

Council of Europe **Framework Convention for the Protection of National Minorities** (1995) provides that persons belonging to national minorities have the right to study their cultures and historical heritage through the education system and that it is, therefore, necessary to enable the education of educators in that sense. Relevant literature and textbooks should be available. Namely, the convention starts from the historical experience of Europe, which argues that the protection of minority rights is the basis of stability, democracy and peace on the entire continent. A society based on democratic principles respects the ethnic,

cultural, linguistic and religious identity of each individual, and at the same time enables him to express, nurture and develop that identity. Also, only a society based on tolerance and encouragement of dialogue should expect cultural diversity to be a factor of cohesion, instead of the basis for further divisions. Article 1 of the Convention states that the protection of minority rights is an integral part of the protection of human rights which are well recognized at the international level. Article 5 stipulates that every individual has the right to preserve and nurture his or her special identity and that the state must not support the processes of assimilation of members of minority groups. In order to encourage the preservation of diversity, the state encourages education and research in the field of cultural, linguistic, historical and religious characteristics of minority groups.

Recommendation of the Committee of Ministers to member states on "hate speech", CM/Rec (97)20, adopted on 30 October 1997 at the 607th meeting of the Ministers' Deputies, states that hate speech includes all forms of expression that disseminate, encourage, promote and justify racial hatred, xenophobia, antisemitism, as well as all other forms of hatred based on intolerance, including: aggressive nationalism and ethnocentrism, discrimination and hostility towards minorities, migrants and people of immigrant origin. Such forms of expression should be prohibited.

Recommendation of the Committee of Ministers to member states on the education of Roma and Travelers in Europe, CM/Rec (2009)4, adopted by the Committee of Ministers on 17 June 2009 at the 1061st meeting of the Ministers' Deputies, envisages that the governments of member states should, with due regard for structures of their education systems, ensure that Roma and Traveler children are effectively accepted in school. Considering the recommendations and policy orientations included in the White Paper on Intercultural Dialogue "Living together as equals in dignity", launched at the 118th Session of the Committee of Ministers (Strasbourg, 7 May 2008) the recommendation is based on the indisputable fact that Roma, Travelers and other homeless people have been discriminated against and rejected by society for centuries, as well as they have encountered significant problems in the field of education and in the field of exercising their human rights in general. The Recommendation acknowledges the fact that Roma and members of similar groups have traditionally been either assimilated within an educational process that did not recognize their needs, or subjected to segregation into closed groups. Due to the specifics of their culture, they were declared socially and culturally handicapped. Therefore, the recommendation condemns all forms of segregation of Roma and Travelers in the education system, especially emphasizing the importance of the case law of the European Court of Human Rights, which has repeatedly stated that Roma's rights have been violated within national education systems.

The Council of Europe emphasizes that the marginalized position of the Roma cannot be overcome without the inclusion of Roma children in the educational process. States are obliged to recognize obstacles to the substantial inclusion of Roma and Travelers in the educational process. Curricula should be designed to enable the educational process in the mother tongue of the Roma, as well as to recognize their experiences and culture as a significant part of cultural diversity.

The specific needs of the Roma should be detected, and the fact that some of them lead nomadic or semi-nomadic lives should be taken into account. Special attention should be paid to the educational needs of Roma girls, while the attendance of primary education by Roma children should be controlled as strictly as the compulsory primary education of non-Roma children. The educational process in European countries must include materials aimed at eradicating prejudice and negative evaluation of Roma and its traditions. Educators should pay attention to the fact that Roma students are to be involved in all types of activities, also they must not narrow the criteria based on which the acquired knowledge is assessed and thus prevent the realization of the full personal potential of Roma students.

Recommendation of the Committee of Ministers to member states on intercultural dialogue and the image of the other in history teaching, CM/Rec (2011)6, adopted by the Committee of Ministers on 6 July 2011 at the 1118th meeting of the Ministers' Deputies, is based on the premise that respect for cultural diversity depends on learning about the past and historical heritage and that the globalization processes and cultural diversity also condition education in the field of history. The complexity of teaching about the past is to be recognized, while having in mind the numerous conflicts that have marked it, but at the same time the recommendation states that the past is, by all means, based on exchange and cooperation between different groups. Despite numerous difficulties, the process of education in the field of history should be directed towards intercultural dialogue and glorification of tolerance, as well as critical and analytical thinking about events from the past. One of the goals of history education is to get to know other cultures and civilizations in order to understand them, while focusing on national, regional and local cultural heritage.

The European Charter for Regional or Minority Languages (Strasbourg, 1992), CETS 148, is based on the premise that preserving linguistic richness enables cultural diversity and a democratic Europe. It states that the languages of national minorities are languages traditionally used in certain countries by members of minority groups. The languages of national minorities do not include different dialects of one language, nor the languages of migrants. Article 7 of the Charter stipulates that different languages are part of the cultural wealth and that their use should be encouraged in both private and public life. States are called upon to provide adequate conditions for the teaching of these languages, as well as for language research. Also, members of the majority group should be enabled to learn minority languages if they wish to do so and it should be possible to learn these languages at universities. The use of national minority languages should be possible at all levels of the education system, from pre-school to higher education, as well as within adult education. States undertake to provide persons belonging to national minorities with: education in the language of a national minority or partial education in the language of a national minority or the teaching of a minority language to be part of the curriculum. In addition to teaching minority languages, education on the culture and historical heritage of members of these minority groups should also be provided.

Recommendation of the Committee of Ministers to Member States on measures to combat discrimination on grounds of sexual orientation and

gender identity, CM/Rec (2010)5, adopted at its 1081st meeting on 31 March 2010, states that it should be recognized that lesbians, homosexuals, bisexuals and transgender people have been exposed to homophobia, transphobia and other forms of intolerance and discrimination for centuries. It should be noted that these people were also abused and discriminated against within their own families. Victimization, marginalization, violence and social exclusion are the daily lives of these people, which is why they deserve support in order to achieve equality in human rights with other citizens. Culture, tradition and cultural attitudes of the majority must not be the basis for justifying the discrimination of these persons. It is emphasized that discrimination and social exclusion due to gender identity and sexual orientation can be eradicated by joint measures aimed at members of the minority group and the entire population. States parties must take measures to prevent any form of public and media expression that justifies discrimination and violence against LGBTI persons. The state must prevent any kind of hate speech, while also taking into account the general right to freedom of expression guaranteed by Art. 10 of the ECHR, which has been confirmed many times by the case law of the European Court of Human Rights.

Furthermore, no child should be prevented from enjoying the right to education because of his or her sexual orientation and gender identity. States have to take measures to prevent violence and discrimination against children of a specific sexual orientation and gender identity. Peer violence or degrading treatment is completely unacceptable. The education system must ensure full respect for everyone's personal dignity. Therefore, the school must provide adequate information and education on issues related to sexual orientation and gender identity. Every student must have the opportunity to participate on an equal footing in the educational process by freely expressing their sexual orientation and gender identity. In that sense, educators and other staff should be specially trained in order to meet the needs of students and to improve safety. The rights of parents regarding the education of their children should also be taken into account.

When it comes to exercising the social rights of LGBTI people, it should be borne in mind that they are entitled to enjoy the right to an adequate standard of living, and therefore the right to housing. The illegal eviction of LGBTI people should be prevented and the housing issue should be resolved either through the purchase or lease of real estate or otherwise. Special measures can be applied to prevent homelessness of persons of specific sexual orientation and gender identity, which also applies to children and young people, bearing in mind the frequent rejection of these persons by their families. Therefore, the housing needs of LGBTI people should be assessed without any discrimination.

Combating rising hate against LGBTI people, the Draft resolution, version of 27 September 2021, **Committee on Equality and Non-Discrimination**, notes that in recent years, despite the formal guarantee of human rights of LGBTI people, there have been aggressive outbursts and campaigns against these individuals with, which is of particular concern, the participation of officials, public figures and religious leaders in such endeavors. It is not just an act based on individual beliefs and prejudices, but an attack on human rights, which affects not only the LGBTI

population but also women. Such statements try to point out that the respect for the rights of LGBTI persons is disabling the respect for the rights of women and children and also disabling the nurturing of prosocial and family values. Such a narrative endangers social cohesion. Member states should condemn incidents of homophobic, transphobic and similar nature. Discrimination based on sexual orientation, gender identity, gender expression and sexual characteristics must be prevented and sanctioned.

Resolution on Access to Education and School for All Children, Res 2097(2016), adopted at the parliamentary session on 29 January 2016, calls for the barriers in the education system to be lifted. The introductory part of the resolution states that, during the last two decades, significant progress has been made in the field of children's access to education in Europe, but that there are still significant problems. In addition, the focus should not only be on the availability of education, but on quality education also and opportunities for each child. At the same time, not only does the child have the right to education, but it is also in the general social interest for the child to exercise that right, so that all citizens become useful members of society and to prevent unemployment problems. Member States are therefore called upon to support the inclusion of children in the educational process, as well as the successful completion of specific levels of education. Particularly important measures are: measures to encourage inclusive education; measures to encourage cooperation with the family of students, as well as to include those students whose families do not take proper care about enrolling their children in schools; measures for learning the language in which the educational process is primarily conducted by children belonging to minority groups and children of migrants; measures to encourage parents to participate in children's literacy, with measures to be adapted to cultural, ethnic and socio-economic circumstances; measures to involve parents in the educational process attended by their children, with special emphasis on parents of lower educational status and parents who use minority languages; measures related to a positive attitude towards education and motivation to learn, which should especially include students from disadvantaged backgrounds; measures to encourage the inclusion of migrant students or students from marginalized groups in schools known for outstanding results; measures to promote tolerance, equality and non-violent conflict resolution; measures to include content on human rights, democracy and tolerance in curricula; measures to encourage educators' ability to work in multilingual groups; measures for pedagogical support to migrant children and children from marginalized groups; measures to include students in all levels of education, with a special focus on Roma, migrants, refugees and girls with disabilities; measures to popularize scientifically based knowledge about LGBTI people and measures of financial investment in inclusive education with a focus on long-term benefits arising from such investments.

Declaration of the Committee of Ministers on Cultural Diversity (2000), adopted on 7 December 2000 at the 733rd meeting of the Ministers' Deputies, emphasizes that modern society is based on cultural diversity, which is significantly influenced by new information technologies, globalization and multilateral trade, recalling that Europe based on cultural diversity and diversity remains its key goal in the 21st century. Cultural diversity implies the coexistence and exchange of culturally

diverse practices and the use of culturally diverse services and products, so that the members of the Council of Europe are called upon to find and promote new ways of preserving cultural and linguistic diversity.

Declaration on Intercultural Dialogue and Conflict Prevention (2003), adopted by the European Ministers of Culture in Opatija on 22 October 2003, addresses the activities of the European Ministries of Culture in order to promote intercultural dialogue, cultural exchange and conflict resolution in post-conflict societies by fostering understanding for the cultures of others. The declaration declares that ignorance of other cultures and rejection of the possibility of learning about them is a source of negative social phenomena, such as xenophobia and racism. The Declaration defines the basic concepts on which cultural exchange in Europe is based. Thus, cultural diversity means that every individual or cultural group has the right to express themselves culturally, artistically, linguistically and in other ways as they wish, as long as they do not oppose basic European values. Everyone has the right to nurture and express their cultural identity, while any expression of intolerance and attempts to assimilate anyone culturally is prohibited. Intercultural dialogue involves communication between different cultural groups at the local and regional levels, as well as between countries. This kind of dialogue takes place in the spirit of tolerance, which does not exclude the possibility of differences of opinion and debate. Intersectoral cooperation and good practices in conflict prevention are based upon the participation of various actors, both state and non-state, in cultural exchange. Meetings of representatives of as diverse cultural groups as possible should be encouraged in order to enable mutual understanding.

Declaration on 50 years of cultural cooperation in Europe (2004) was adopted by the Ministers responsible for culture, education, youth and sports of the signatory states of the European Convention on Culture, Wroclaw (Poland), on the occasion of the 50th anniversary of the European Cultural Convention. Although the declaration summarizes the significant results achieved in terms of cultural cooperation and exchange in Europe, it is noted that there is significant room for improvement. Thus, the declaration states that even though the wide availability of education is enabled and the cultural rights are respected, the exclusion of minority groups and materially deprived citizens is still present. Significant progress has been made in achieving equality between women and men, but there are still attitudes that do not speak in favor of gender equality. Personal freedoms are widely respected, but alienation is also present in society. Much has been done in the field of protection of cultural heritage and the environment, but these assets are still endangered in situations when conflicts escalate. Citizens have the opportunity to access all sorts of information, but at the same time, it does not mean their cognitive abilities develop at the same pace. There is no ideology that we should all adhere to, but the fact is that racism, xenophobia, antisemitism and extreme nationalism are reviving. That is why the cultural cooperation in Europe must focus on all these issues in the future.

Recommendation of the Committee of Ministers to member States on multilevel policies and governance for intercultural integration, CM/Rec (2022)10, adopted by the Committee of Ministers on 6 April 2022 at the 1431st meeting of the Ministers' Deputies, states that policies at all levels should respect

the importance of cultural diversity, encourage the development of an inclusive society and use existing differences to their advantage.

Recommendation of the Committee of Ministers to member states on youth participation and the future of civil society, CM/Rec (97)3, adopted by the Committee of Ministers on 4 February 1997 at the 583rd meeting of the Ministers' Deputies, refers to international documents guaranteeing human rights of the child, and in particular the right of the child to actively participate in social processes and to express opinions, as well as the assumption that only a society in which there are no marginalized people could be stable and prosperous. The recommendation emphasizes that the engagement of volunteers in the implementation of various policies is extremely important, which is especially important for the countries in Central and Eastern Europe. Therefore, the recommendation calls on states to take steps to enable the functioning of youth organizations at both local and regional levels, as well as to ensure that youth workers acquire appropriate education so that they can support the participation of young people in social processes.

Recommendation of the Committee of Ministers to member States on protecting youth civil society and young people and supporting their participation in democratic processes, CM/Rec (2022)6, adopted by the Committee of Ministers on 17 March 2022 at the 1429th meeting of the Ministers' Deputies, is based on the irrefutable assumption that without the participation of young people in political life there could be no democracy nor respect for human rights. It implies that a democratic society is based on the creativity, competencies and commitment of young people. States are urged to take as many measures as possible to encourage the participation of young people in civil society activities and in democratic political life. In doing so, special attention should be paid to the needs of young people and to the obstacles faced by young members of marginalized groups, which may make it difficult or impossible for them to participate in social life. In addition to the application of measures, it is necessary to evaluate their effects, in order to know whether the measures contribute to the involvement of young people. In order for all young people, especially those from marginalized groups, to participate in civil society activities, it is necessary to strengthen their competencies primarily through the formal education system, but also through non-formal education. Special attention should be paid to the digital and media literacy of young members of marginalized social groups, and to the adoption of democratic values by these individuals.

Resolution of the Committee of Ministers on the youth sector strategy 2030, CM/Res (2020) 2, adopted by The Committee of Ministers on 22 January 2020 at the 1365th meeting of the Ministers' Deputies, is based on the notion that young people across Europe should enjoy, promote and nurture the core values advocated by the Council of Europe, namely: respect for human rights, the rule of democracy and the rule of law. For young people to be satisfied and to promote prosocial values, it is necessary to enable their education and participation in social life. Implementation of different measures should especially include young members of marginalized groups, but should also be aimed at respecting the cultural differences that characterize young people across Europe.

Recommendation on supporting young refugees in transition to adulthood, CM/Rec (2019) 4, adopted by the Committee of Ministers on 24 April 2019 at the 1344th meeting of the Ministers' Deputies, pays special attention to young refugees, bearing in mind that the values on which modern Europe is based imply the full social inclusion of every citizen, regardless of their background and personal experiences. Young refugees need to be given complex support as they move into adulthood. States are called upon to prevent discrimination against these persons, as well as to take into account the special needs that may arise from victimization through sexual violence, trafficking in human beings and gender-based violence. It is indisputable that after reaching the age of 18, these young people may be deprived of their human rights, given that national legal systems are designed to guarantee special protection primarily for children or minors or persons under 18 years of age. In order to prevent the deprivation of human rights, states should implement adequate measures for these youngsters.

Recommendation of the Committee of Ministers to member states on research on young people's access to rights, CM/Rec (2016)7, adopted by the Committee of Ministers on 28 September 2016 at the 1266th meeting of the Ministers' Deputies, starts from the assumption that in order to preserve Europe based on democratic values young people must be included in all social processes. Nevertheless, young people often suffer social exclusion due to socio-economic crises in Europe and the world. Therefore, it is recommended that states take all measures to combat multiple discrimination affecting young people due to the non-compliance with Art. 14 of the ECHR which guarantees equality of all citizens regardless of their personal characteristics. It is emphasized that young people face problems in accessing quality education, with limited opportunities for higher education, as well as the lack of resources that would enable their social and economic independence. States should take measures to make human rights mechanisms easily accessible to young people, as well as to support the education of youth workers so that youth workers could provide more effective services to young people. It is noted that the youth work sector could be a particularly important resource for improving the position of young people. Also, the role and importance of non-formal education should be focused upon. A special segment of the recommendation refers to the local community in a society characterized by cultural diversity. In order to respect diversity, it is necessary to combat discrimination, intolerance and social exclusion, while the inclusion and participation of young people, especially those belonging to marginalized groups, should be encouraged. When it comes to conflict and post-conflict societies, they should especially encourage respect for peace and tolerance.

Recommendation on the access of young people from disadvantaged neighborhoods to social rights, CM/Rec (2015)3, adopted by the Committee of Ministers on 21 January 2015 at the 1217th meeting of the Ministers' Deputies, suggests that countries should develop policies to eliminate the social exclusion of young people from underprivileged groups and to eliminate discrimination, poverty and violence that these young people often experience. Local, regional and central authorities should provide young people from disadvantaged areas with the right to social and health care, housing standards, education and adequate information, as well as to enable them to participate in cultural

and recreational activities. One of the measures that could be of great practical importance is the sustainable financing of youth work and youth organizations that would continuously strive for the realization of the rights of young people from disadvantaged backgrounds, while making them visible and empowered.

Resolution on the Youth Policy of the Council of Europe, CM/Res (2008)23, adopted by the Committee of Ministers on 25 November 2008 at the 1042nd meeting of the Ministers' Deputies, promotes equal opportunities for all girls and boys, and also for young women and young men to develop their knowledge and skills and to become active participants in all social processes. The resolution calls on postulates highlighted in 2005 campaign "All different-all equal", which was organized in order to stimulate young people to get involved in politics. The resolution focuses in particular on today's society of many differences, where young people should be encouraged to engage in intercultural dialogue, reconciliation and tolerance, especially in societies with different conflicts, with a focus on religiously based conflicts. It is important to invest in work with asylum seekers, refugees and homeless people. When it comes to youth work and training for youth workers, one should keep in mind the need to conceive a set of minimum standards through cooperation and exchange of knowledge between different countries.

Council of Europe Charter on Education for Democratic Citizenship and Human Rights Education, adopted on 11 May 2010 in the framework of Recommendation CM/Rec(2010)7 of the Committee of Ministers, is an important document, although it is not formally binding. The charter was created as a result of many years of research and exchange of good practices in the field of educating young people about democratic values and human rights. It is based on the scientifically proven claim that education is the most effective tool against racism, xenophobia, discrimination and violence. The charter refers to all forms of education through which one can learn about human rights and democracy. Thus, formal education is important - as attending a formal program in official institutions, such as schools and universities, as well as non-formal education - the implementation of various educational programs that are not conducted directly within the formal education system and informal education - the use of diverse life experiences and encounters with other people in order to acquire knowledge and skills. Education about democratic values, on one side, and education on societal participation and education on human rights, on the other, are intertwined, but also fundamentally different. Thus, education on democratic values is primarily aimed at stimulating citizens to actively participate in political life, while education on human rights refers to educating citizens about all human rights that belong to them, regardless of their political engagement. The Charter insists that all segments of education are important and it advocates for strengthening the role of the civil sector and youth work in non-formal education.

Recommendation of the Committee of Ministers to member states on the promotion and recognition of non-formal education/ learning of young people, CM/Rec (2003) 8, adopted by the Committee of Ministers on 30 April 2003 at the 838th meeting of the Ministers' Deputies, praises the role of non-formal education, emphasizing that it could be a form of education that enables young people

to actively participate in social processes. Therefore, a more precise definition of the non-formal education sector is needed, both in terms of enabling better competencies of those who educate others through non-formal education and the evaluation of the factual effects that result from non-formal education. Since it is indisputable that non-formal education can be used as a method of lifelong learning, measures should be devised in order to multiply non-formal education programs, especially those that are important for young people and even more important for members of marginalized groups. The exchange of best practices should be supported, as well as cooperation between the Council of Europe and the European Union in the field of exchange of knowledge and experiences.

European Youth Forum recommendations on social protection and young people in Europe, adopted by the General Assembly Brussels (Belgium) 19-21 October 2000, 0708-2K –FINAL, is a document adopted by the platform of youth organizations in Europe, which cooperates intensively with both the Council of Europe and the European Union. The document states that exercising the right to social protection is especially difficult for young people, given that adult citizens are directly linked to social services in situations of job loss or unemployment, so that they can exercise their basic social rights without practical and technical problems. The position of young people in the entire EU is not at an enviable level, while young people in Eastern and Central Europe and outside the EU are facing additional difficulties. Young people face difficulties in exercising their right to an adequate standard, housing and similar. For all young people, the critical period starts from the end of schooling and ends with acquiring a job, which is especially true for "invisible" young people who are not involved in the educational process or the labor market. The "invisible" youngsters do not exercise their rights to social protection, which increasingly pushes them into social exclusion. The realization of social rights is directly related to the realization of the right to education and information, which implies that young people from rural areas and excluded from the education system deserve special support in order to get to an equal position with their peers. In recent years European Youth Forum has been particularly committed to promoting the political and participatory rights of young people, especially those who for various reasons (gender, economic status, coming from minority groups) can be considered marginalized or unequal.

European Union documents

Although the European Union was primarily created as a supranational organization striving for the united European market and for economic and political cooperation of EU member states, nevertheless it also intensively deals with other issues important for the prosperity of the old continent and its citizens. In that sense, a significant number of documents refer to the sphere of exercising social rights and encouraging cultural exchange.

The following documents are recognized as most valuable ones:

- ◆ Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, 2000

- ◆ Directive on the implementing the principle of equal treatment regardless of racial or ethnic origin, 2020
- ◆ Framework for establishing a European Youth Work Agenda, 2020
- ◆ Council Conclusions on Education and Training of Youth Workers, 2019
- ◆ Youth Strategy 2019-2027, 2018
- ◆ The European Pillar of Social Rights, 2017

Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (Official Journal of the European Union, 2007/C 303/01) guarantees the prohibition of discrimination on any personal ground (sex, race, social origin, genetic characteristics, sexual orientation ...), as well as based on citizenship (Art. 21). The right to cultural, religious and linguistic diversity, as well as equality between women and men in all areas, is guaranteed, provided that the application of measures in favor of the underrepresented sex in various spheres is not considered discrimination (Art. 22 and 23).

Directive on the Implementation of the Principle of Equal Treatment regardless of Racial or Ethnic Origin, 2000/43/EC of 29 June 2000, states that discrimination based on racial or ethnic origin may jeopardize the achievement of EU goals and objectives. Discrimination is especially detrimental in the field of employment, social protection, living standards and quality of life and incompatible with the EU as a community based on the principles of freedom, security and justice. Unequal treatment of citizens shatters economic and social cohesion and solidarity.

Resolution of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States meeting within the Council on the **Framework for establishing a European Youth Work Agenda** (2020/C 415/01), refers to all types of formal and informal work with young people in order for them to achieve social inclusion both as a group and as individuals, regardless of their personal characteristics. Despite the great differences in the formats of engagement of youth workers across the EU, the essence of their engagement is to enable young people to learn and experience the values embodied in human rights, gender equality, democracy, peace, pluralism, diversity, inclusion, solidarity, tolerance and justice. It is necessary for youth work to respect the practical needs of young people and to create the best possible environment for acquiring knowledge. The beginning of the realization of the agenda is called the Bonn Process, after an online event broadcasted from Bonn and the guiding idea is to strengthen the youth work sector by connecting the local and European levels, both by creating appropriate contexts and strengthening competencies. In the coming period, it is necessary to focus on possible new crises situations, such as Covid-19, in order to plan strategies for overcoming them, in which context digital technologies could be extremely important. Also, intra-European cooperation is needed in order to promote intercultural learning, as well as the exchange of knowledge between young people themselves.

Council Conclusions on Education and Training of Youth Workers (Official Journal of the European Union 2019/C412) state that there are basic standards on which the training and work of youth workers everywhere should be based in

Europe as a whole, but that the specific needs of each country should be taken into account. Therefore, the education of youth workers requires a flexible and user-oriented approach, as well as cross-sectoral cooperation. It was noted that at the EU level there is a lack of programs for the education of youth workers, as well as that there are no adequate mechanisms for the exchange of knowledge in this field. Research, exchange of good practices and an approach that summarizes individual experiences in a generally relevant way are essential for the further development of youth work.

European **Union Youth Strategy** 2019-2027, Resolution of the Council of the European Union and the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States meeting within the Council on a framework for European cooperation in the youth field, Official Journal of the European Union, 2018/C 456/01) is a document that directs strategically youth policy in order to realize the potential of youth in the best possible way. The strategy is based on providing support to young people for active participation in political life, which implies that young people should have access to the necessary resources. The three key concepts in this document are the inclusion, connection and empowerment of young people, through which 11 key goals of youth policy are then to be achieved. Some of the goals are: popularizing the idea of a strong EU and reducing Euroscepticism among young people, gender equality, the inclusion of all categories of young people in social processes, creating preconditions for youth equality in rural areas, equal opportunities for education with a focus on non-formal education and spatial and other conditions for the participation of young people, especially through the provision of appropriate infrastructure and support for youth work.

The **European Pillar of Social Rights** is an important document that ensures standards and coordination in the field of social rights. On 17th November 2017, the Council of the EU, the European Parliament and the European Commission published and signed the European Pillar of Social Rights. This document is not formally binding and calls upon a set of documents relevant to the labor market, inclusion and social protection in the broadest possible sense. The pillar is based on 20 key standards, including: gender equality, equal opportunities for all, social dialogue and inclusion of workers in decision-making on their rights, work-life balance, social security, child protection, guaranteeing a minimum standard of living and social inclusion for persons with disabilities.

List of used international documents:

- ◆ United Nations (1948). Universal Declaration of Human Rights. <https://www.un.org/sites/un2.un.org/files/2021/03/udhr.pdf>
- ◆ United Nations (1966). International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights. <https://www.ohchr.org/sites/default/files/ccpr.pdf>
- ◆ United Nations (1966). International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights. <https://www.ohchr.org/sites/default/files/cescr.pdf>
- ◆ United Nations (1965). International Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination. <https://www.ohchr.org/sites/default/files/cerd.pdf>
- ◆ United Nations (UN Women) (2016). Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women. <https://www.unwomen.org/en/digital-library/publications/2016/12/cedaw-for-youth>
- ◆ United Nations (2006). Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD). <https://www.ohchr.org/en/instruments-mechanisms/instruments/convention-rights-persons-disabilities>
- ◆ United Nations (1960). Convention against Discrimination in Education. <https://www.ohchr.org/en/instruments-mechanisms/instruments/convention-against-discrimination-education>
- ◆ UNESCO (2006). UNESCO Guidelines for Intercultural Education. <https://www.gcedclearinghouse.org/resources/unesco-guidelines-intercultural-education>
- ◆ United Nations (1989). Convention on the Rights of the Child. <https://www.ohchr.org/en/instruments-mechanisms/instruments/convention-rights-child>
- ◆ United Nations (2001). Universal Declaration on Cultural Diversity. <http://orcp.hustoj.com/unesco-universal-declaration-on-cultural-diversity-2001/>
- ◆ United Nations (2015). Agenda for Sustainable Development until 2030. <https://sdgs.un.org/2030agenda>
- ◆ Council of Europe (1950). European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms. https://www.eods.eu/library/CoE-European%20Convention%20for%20the%20Protection%20of%20Human%20Rights%20and%20Fundamental%20Freedoms_1950_EN.pdf
- ◆ Council of Europe (1996). Revised European Social Charter. <https://www.refworld.org/pdfid/3ae6b3678.pdf>
- ◆ Council of Europe (1954). European Cultural Convention. <https://www.coe.int/en/web/culture-and-heritage/european-cultural-convention>
- ◆ Council of Europe (2013). Reference Framework of Competences for Democratic Culture (RFCDC). <https://www.coe.int/en/web/reference-framework-of-competences-for-democratic-culture>
- ◆ Council of Europe (2006). ECRI Recommendation on a general policy on combating racism and racial discrimination in and through school education. <https://www.coe.int/en/web/european-commission-against-racism-and-intolerance/recommendation-no.10>
- ◆ Council of Europe (1992). Convention on the Participation of Foreigners in

- Public Life at Local Level. <https://rm.coe.int/168007bd26>
- ◆ Council of Europe (1994). Framework Convention for the Protection of National Minorities. <https://www.coe.int/en/web/minorities/at-a-glance>
 - ◆ Council of Europe (1997). Recommendation of the Committee of Ministers of the Council of Europe to member states on "hate speech". <https://www.legal-tools.org/doc/rx2ckd/>
 - ◆ Council of Europe (2009). Recommendation of the Committee of Ministers to member states on the education of Roma and Travelers in Europe. <https://tandis.odihr.pl/handle/20.500.12389/20787>
 - ◆ Council of Europe (2010). Recommendation of the Committee of Ministers to Member States on measures to combat discrimination on grounds of sexual orientation and gender identity. <https://www.coe.int/en/web/sogi/rec-2010-5>
 - ◆ Council of Europe (2016). Resolution on Access to Education and School for All Children. <https://assembly.coe.int/nw/xml/XRef/Xref-XML2HTML-en.asp?fileid=22510>
 - ◆ Council of Europe (2000). Declaration of the Committee of Ministers on Cultural Diversity. <https://rm.coe.int/16804bfc0b>
 - ◆ Council of Europe (2003). Declaration on Intercultural Dialogue and Conflict Prevention. <http://www.ericarts-institute.org/web/files/131/en/OpatijaDeclaration.pdf>
 - ◆ Council of Europe (2004). Declaration on 50 years of cultural cooperation in Europe. https://www.coe.int/t/dg4/culturalconvention/Declaration_en.asp
 - ◆ Council of Europe (2022). Recommendation of the Committee of Ministers to member States on multilevel policies and governance for intercultural integration. <https://www.coe.int/en/web/interculturalcities/-/the-committee-of-ministers-adopts-a-landmark-legal-standard-on-multilevel-policies-and-governance-for-intercultural-integration>
 - ◆ Council of Europe (1997). Recommendation of the Committee of Ministers to member states on youth participation and the future of civil society. <https://participationpool.eu/resource/recommendation-no-r-97-3-of-the-committee-of-ministers-to-member-states-on-youth-participation-and-the-future-of-civil-society/>
 - ◆ Council of Europe (2022). Recommendation of the Committee of Ministers to member States on protecting youth civil society and young people and supporting their participation in democratic processes. <https://rm.coe.int/0900001680a5e7f3>
 - ◆ Council of Europe (2020). Resolution of the Committee of Ministers on the youth sector strategy 2030. <https://rm.coe.int/0900001680998935>
 - ◆ Council of Europe (2019). Recommendation on supporting young refugees in transition to adulthood. <https://edoc.coe.int/en/refugees/8233-supporting-young-refugees-in-transition-to-adulthood-recommendation-cmrec20194.html>
 - ◆ Council of Europe (2016). Recommendation of the Committee of Ministers to member states on research on young people's access to rights. <https://www.coe.int/en/web/youth/-/recommendation-on-young-people-s-access-to-rights>
 - ◆ Council of Europe (2015). Recommendation on the access of young people from disadvantaged neighborhoods to social rights. <https://www.coe.int/en/web/>

[youth/-/recommendation-on-the-access-of-young-people-from-disadvantaged-neighbourhoods-to-social-rights](#)

- ◆ Council of Europe (2008). Resolution on the Youth Policy of the Council of Europe. https://pjp-eu.coe.int/documents/42128013/47262391/CM_Res_08_youth_policy_en.pdf/7df7229a-3c5b-90bf-3eea-22900881b71f?t=1496158649000
- ◆ Council of Europe (2010). Council of Europe Charter on Education for Democratic Citizenship and Human Rights Education. <https://rm.coe.int/16803034e5>
- ◆ Council of Europe (2003). Recommendation of the Committee of Ministers to member states on the promotion and recognition of non-formal education/learning of young people. <https://rm.coe.int/16805e00a9>
- ◆ Council of Europe (2000). European Youth Forum recommendations on social protection and young people in Europe. <https://www.youthforum.org/files/0708-2ke1.pdf>
- ◆ European Union (2000). Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union. https://www.europarl.europa.eu/charter/pdf/text_en.pdf
- ◆ European Union (2000). Directive on the implementing the principle of equal treatment regardless of racial or ethnic origin. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32000L0043>
- ◆ European Union (2020). Framework for establishing a European Youth Work Agenda. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A42020Y1201%2801%29>
- ◆ European Union (2019). Council Conclusions on Education and Training of Youth Workers. <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-13595-2019-REV-1/en/pdf>
- ◆ European Union (2018). Youth Strategy 2019-2027. https://youth.europa.eu/strategy_en
- ◆ European Union (2017). The European Pillar of Social Rights. <https://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?catId=1606&langId=en>

**instead of
a conclusion:
minimum standards
for diversity fostering
in practice**

The Authors

Minimum standards for respecting diversity in practice

Based on the review of scientific knowledge, the legal framework and the way in which institutions (national, regional, international) and civil society organizations deal with respecting diversity, it can be concluded that the success and level of respecting diversity depends on the systematic, comprehensive and structured approach in this regard.

In order for the institution/organization to be **culturally competent**, i.e. to successfully respond to the diverse needs of its employees and users with whom it works, it is necessary that the promotion of this value permeates all aspects of the institutional functioning of the institution/organization (culture and climate) and that it arises from individual actions employees (cultural competence).

In other words, in order for an institution/organization to be said to respect diversity, it must meet four **minimum standards**, i.e. have:

- 1 **ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE** whose elements exude respecting diversity: vision and mission that imply respecting diversity; policies, procedures and practices that clearly emphasize the importance of respecting diversity; rituals, traditions and ceremonies that take into account the needs of all employees; architecture, artifacts and/or symbols that reflect diversity;
- 2 **ORGANIZATIONAL CLIMATE** characterized by: respect and appreciation of all employees; open communication and cooperation; security; consistent and fair application of policies, procedures and practices;
- 3 **EMPLOYEES WITH DEVELOPED CULTURAL COMPETENCES** who have: adequate and appropriate attitudes, opinions and assumptions about different cultures; understanding of own and other cultures in terms of cultural norms; and the ability to effectively and impartially communicate and interact with individuals belonging to different cultural groups.
- 4 **Simultaneous and congruent appreciation of diversity at ALL THREE LEVELS OF FUNCTIONING** – organizational culture, organizational climate and employees.

Appenndix:
current national
legislation on diversity
in Serbia, Italy
and Slovenia

Current national legislation on diversity in Serbia

Milica Kovačević

Achieving cultural diversity and creating a context in which everyone can express their uniqueness and fulfill their personal potential requires a society based on democratic values, tolerance, social justice and the rule of law. Such a context is built by the implementation of an adequate legal framework, with the Constitution at the top of the pyramid of legal acts, followed by laws and bylaws.

Therefore, we begin review of the Serbian national legal context relevant to achieving cultural diversity by summarizing some of the most important provisions of the Constitution relating to equality and non-discrimination. That is followed by a summary of laws that are not directly related to the education system, social protection and youth work, but are also essential for establishing a system based on the principle of equity and respect for the personal dignity of every citizen.

Constitution of the Republic of Serbia, Official Gazette of RS, no. 98/2006 and 115/21, contains a significant number of provisions related to the protection of the rights of members of minority groups and provisions on the creation of overall conditions and opportunities which are necessary for the development of culturally sensitive society. Thus, pursuant to Art. 14, the state guarantees special protection to national minorities, in order to achieve full equality and preserve their identity, while Art. 15 guarantees the equality of men and women while ensuring equal opportunities for both sexes. Human and minority rights are directly guaranteed by the Constitution, so that laws cannot affect their essence, pursuant to Art. 18. The provisions on both human and minority rights are to be interpreted in the spirit of democratic values and in accordance with international standards, as well as the practice of relevant international institutions. The Constitution explicitly proclaims the prohibition of discrimination, stating that before the Constitution and the law everyone is equal, in the sense of Art. 21.

The Constitution guarantees special protection of the family, mother, single parent and child (Art. 66), while the right to social protection is exercised in accordance with the principles of social justice, humanism and respect for personal dignity (Art. 69). The right to social protection belongs to those citizens and families who need social assistance in order to overcome life's difficulties and satisfy basic needs. According to Art. 71, everyone has the right to education, with primary education being compulsory and free, while all citizens are entitled to an equal right to access higher education.

When it comes to members of national minorities, in addition to the rights that belong to all citizens, they also have special individual and collective rights aimed at protecting the specific rights of these persons. Individual and collective minority

rights are exercised in accordance with the Constitution, national regulations and international standards. Any form of discrimination on the grounds of belonging to a national minority is prohibited, as well as violent assimilation of members of national minorities (Art. 76 and 78). The right of members of national minorities to preserve their identity includes the protection and development of cultural, religious, ethnic and national identity, which includes school programs in national minority languages, the use of national minority languages in official procedures and the establishment of minority public media resources, in accordance with Art. 79 of the Constitution. In the event of a state of emergency or war, derogations from human and minority rights are allowed, but only to the necessary extent. Measures derogating from human and minority rights must not result in discrimination based on sex, racial, religious or national origin, or language or social origin, under Art. 202.

The Constitution states that Serbia encourages the development of tolerance and intercultural dialogue in the field of education, culture and mass media, in order to promote understanding and cooperation among all people living on its territory, regardless of their personal identities (Art. 81).

In the part related to the territorial organization of the state, the Constitution stipulates that municipalities as local self-government units have several specific competencies important for meeting the needs of citizens, including competencies in meeting the needs of citizens in education, culture, health, social and child protection, sports and physical culture (Art. 190).

Criminal Code, Official Gazette of RS, no. 85/2005, 88/2005, 107/2007, 92/2009, 111/2009, 121/2012, 104/2013, 108/2014, 94/2016 and 35/2019, envisages a series of incriminations that protect the equality and equity of citizens and that prevent discrimination and the spread of hatred and intolerance. Some of the criminal offenses are: violation of equity (Art. 128), violation of freedom of expression of national or ethnic origin (Art. 130) and incitement of national racial and religious hatred and intolerance (Art. 317). A special aggravating circumstance that affects the sentencing is the notion that the crime was committed out of hatred due to race and religion, nationality or ethnicity, gender, sexual orientation or gender identity of the victimized person, so that this circumstance will be considered aggravating by the court, except if it is not prescribed as a distinct feature of a criminal offense (Article 54a).

Law on Prohibition of Manifestations of Neo-Nazi or Fascist Organizations and Associations and Prohibition of the Use of Neo-Nazi or Fascist Symbols, Official Gazette of RS, no. 41/2009, among other things, it prohibits the production, presentation and dissemination of materials prepared in order to spread hatred and intolerance towards citizens of specific origin or background. It is prohibited to provoke or encourage religious, racial, or national hatred and intolerance (Art. 3).

Law on Public Information and Media, Official Gazette of RS, no. 83/2014, 58/2015 and 12/2016, stipulates that the rules on public media functioning are designed in such a way as to ensure the exchange of information, ideas and opinions and to preserve democratic values, peace, truthfulness and personal development (Art.

2). Public media resources are not to be subjected to censorship, pursuant to Art. 4, provided that, at the request of the public prosecutor, the court may prohibit the distribution of certain media content if that is necessary in a democratic society and if the content calls upon direct violence against a person or group of persons based on their national, racial, religious, sexual orientation, disability or any other personal characteristic (Art. 59). Hate speech is prohibited, so media content must not encourage or spread hatred based on any personal traits of citizens, regardless of whether such an announcement is a criminal offense (Art. 75).

Law on the Protection of the Rights and Freedoms of National Minorities, Official Gazette of the FRY, no. 11/2002 and the Official Gazette of RS, no. 72/2009 and 97/2013, defines a national minority as any group of citizens of the Republic of Serbia that is sufficiently represented and permanently seated on the territory of the state. A national minority should be characterized by special characteristics such as language, culture or nationality. Members of certain minority groups are interested in preserving their distinctive identity (Art. 2). The law prohibits discrimination against persons belonging to national minorities, while stipulating that the application of special measures in order to achieve full equality of minority groups shall not be considered discrimination (Art. 3 and 4). The law provides for a number of rights through which the prerogative to preserve national specificity is exercised, so that they include, among others: the right to use native languages, the right to nurture culture and traditions and the right to education in native languages. When it comes to schooling in the native languages, members of national minorities have the right to be educated in their own language in institutions within the public education system, provided that the law may prescribe a certain minimum number of students as a prerequisite for exercising this right. The curriculum for schooling in the native language should contain topics related to the history, culture and art of the specific national minority, under Art. 13 of the law.

Law on Official Use of Languages and Scripts, Official Gazette of RS, No. 45/91, 53/93, 67/93, 48/94, 101/2005, 30/2010, 47/2018 and 48/2018, among other things, defines issues regarding the official use of languages and scripts of national minorities. It envisages that members of a national minority are entitled to use their native language and script in the territories of local self-government units where these national minorities traditionally live in larger numbers. The unit of local self-government is obliged to introduce certain minority languages and scripts into official use if the percentage of members of that national minority in the total population in the given unit reaches at least 15% of the total population. The national minority language is to be in official use within 90 days of determining the conditions prescribed by law (Art. 11). The official use of language in this sense implies the use of the language and script of the national minority in judicial, administrative and other legally regulated procedures, as well as in official communication with the authorities. It is envisaged that the names of streets and other public signs should be stated both in the Serbian language and in the languages and scripts of the respective national minorities.

Law on Prohibition of Discrimination, Official Gazette of RS, no. 22/2009 and 52/2021, provides that the terms "discrimination" and "discriminatory treatment"

signifies any unjustified discrimination or unequal treatment or maltreatment (exclusion, restriction or preference), overt or covert, of persons or groups, as well as members of their families or persons close to them, based on race, color, ancestry, nationality, ethnicity or ethnic origin, language, religion or political affiliation, sex, gender, gender identity, sexual orientation, income level, wealth, birth, genetic characteristics, health status, disability, marital and family status, conviction, age, appearance, membership in political, trade union and other organizations and other real or assumed personal characteristics. Discrimination is prohibited by all means.

Law on Prevention of Discrimination against Persons with Disabilities, Official Gazette of RS, no. 33/2017, regulates, among other things, the area of potential discrimination in connection with upbringing and education, as well as it prohibits placing barriers to the inclusion of persons with disabilities in the educational process, pursuant to Art. 18. Harassment, insulting and belittling of a preschool child or student is defined as a particularly severe form of discrimination.

Law on Gender Equality, Official Gazette of RS, no. 52/2021, defines the concept and meaning of the term gender equality/equity, policy measures for achieving and promoting gender equality and other important issues related to gender equality. Measures provided by law should enable equality of women and men in all areas and activities, as well as prevention and suppression of all forms of gender-based violence. According to Art. 3 gender equality/equity signifies "equal rights, responsibilities and opportunities, equal participation and balanced representation of women and men in all areas of social life, equal opportunities for exercising rights and freedoms, use of personal knowledge and skills for personal and social development, equal opportunities and rights in access to goods and services, as well as achieving equal benefits from the results of work, while respecting biological, social and cultural differences between men and women and different interests, needs and priorities of women and men in public and other policies and decisions on rights and obligations." The legislator clarifies that "gender" implies roles, characteristics and relationships that society considers appropriate for women and men, while "sex" signifies a biological characteristic on the basis of which people are defined as women or men (Art. 6, para. 1, 1 and 3). All forms of discrimination, both direct and indirect, on the basis of sex and gender are prohibited, including harassment, degrading treatment, threats, extortion, gender-based hate speech, gender-based violence and other, in accordance with Art. 4.

Among the areas in which special measures for achieving full gender equality are implemented, the legislator especially emphasizes the field of social and health care, as well as the field of education, upbringing, science and technological development. In the field of education, upbringing, science and technological development, the authorities should take special care to integrate gender equality topics into teaching content, while excluding gender stereotypes, sexist content and the like, taking into account the age of students (Art. 37).

Strategy for Gender Equality from 2021 to 2030, Official Gazette of RS, no. 103/2021, states that in the period of validity of the previous strategy for gender

equality some fine results were achieved in the normative field, as well as some normative improvements were made in order to get closer to some international standards relevant in this field. However, modest results were achieved in the field of economic empowerment of women and in the field of gender-sensitive education. Some of the key challenges in achieving gender equality are: changing patriarchal attitudes and patterns that are conflicted with achieving full equality between women and men, combating misogyny and anti-gender discourse and implementing specific support measures for women who face additional problems in achieving gender equality due to belonging to marginalized groups.

The strategy explicitly states that without gender-sensitive education there is no possibility for the development of a gender-equal society, and therefore for such a society that respects differences. It is necessary to introduce a gender perspective in the education system, which requires gender-sensitive curricula, as well as to improve the gender competencies of teachers. It is necessary to reconsider the status of the subject of Civic Education and to work on the development of competencies of teachers who teach this subject, given that the program of Civic Education primarily teaches about issues of gender equality.

There are certain disparities in terms of attending certain levels and types of education, so it has been noticed that a slightly higher percentage of women receive higher education, but also that women are more represented in the social sciences and humanities, while a higher percentage of men receive higher education in areas of technical and natural sciences.

When it comes to gender equality in the field of social protection, it was noticed that there are no adequate data on gender sensitivity in the provision of services in this area. It is indisputable that women with disabilities are one of the most vulnerable categories and that they encounter multiple obstacles in exercising their right to social protection.

The general goal of the strategy is to overcome the gender gap and achieve gender equality for boys and girls and women and men, which is also the basis for the overall progress of society. Specific objectives are related to the development of a gender equality education system, which should strengthen the capacity of relevant institutions. In that sense, one of the measures is the revision of teaching content in order to eliminate gender stereotypes and discriminatory attitudes. Also, the equality of Roma girls and girls with disabilities should be encouraged in this and many other areas.

Strategy for Prevention and Suppression of Trafficking in Human Beings, Especially Women and Children and Protection of Victims 2017–2022, Official Gazette of RS, no. 77/2017, devises an approach to combating trafficking in human beings, bearing in mind that in recent years it has been noticed that the number of victims among Serbian citizens has increased and that types of possible exploitation are multiplying. One of the special goals is the protection of children from human trafficking and in order to achieve it various measures are to be applied, including preventive programs that will be adapted to the needs of children and especially the needs of children from vulnerable social groups.

- Measures should also include the implementation of programs about gender discrimination and its consequences, which should be organized in the education system for children of primary and secondary school age.

The following review summarizes legal documents important for the preservation and promotion of cultural diversity in the sectors of education, social protection and youth work.

Education

Respect for cultural diversity, nurturing of democratic values and the rule of law are unattainable ideals without an adequate education system. In order to create a democratic and humanistic context, certain knowledge, skills and abilities are to be acquired. The education system in Serbia is regulated by a series of laws and bylaws that inevitably emphasize the need to respect the rights of all citizens, regardless of their cultural values and personal traits.

Law on Fundamentals of the Education System, Official Gazette of RS, no. 88/2017, 27/2018, 10/2019 and 6/2020, stipulates that the education system must ensure: respect for human rights and the rights of every child, respect for human dignity and education in a democratically organized and socially responsible institution that fosters openness, cooperation, tolerance, awareness of cultural and civilizational connections in the world and commitment to basic moral values, values of justice, truth and solidarity (segment related to the General Principles of Education and Upbringing (Art. 7, para. 1, item 3...)). All citizens of the Republic of Serbia are entitled to equal rights to education, while persons with disabilities have the right to education and upbringing that respects their needs, which could also include individual or group support, according to the individual circumstances of every person (Art. 3).

The goals of education and upbringing, among other things, are: providing support for the overall development of the child; developing of self-awareness, critical thinking and motivation; developing positive human values, solidarity and sense for cooperation with others; developing respect for racial, national, cultural, linguistic, religious, gender, sex and age equality, tolerance and respect for diversity and development of personal and national identity, developing a sense of belonging to the Republic of Serbia, respect and nurture of Serbian language and native languages, preservation of Serbian and national minority tradition and culture, development of interculturality and preservation of national and world cultural heritage (Art. 8).

The law defines the concept of key competencies for lifelong learning as a set of integrated knowledge, skills and attitudes needed by each individual for personal fulfillment and development. On the other hand, general interdisciplinary competencies are based on key competencies and are developed through the teaching of all subjects, so that they are applicable in different situations and contexts and also in solving various problems and tasks (Art. 11 and 12).

If needed, it is possible to adopt an individual educational plan in the cases of students who, due to social deprivation, developmental disabilities, other disabilities, learning difficulties, risk of early school leaving and other reasons, need additional support in education, as well as for students who achieve results that exceed expected level of educational achievement. Also, the institution provides the removal of physical and communication barriers according to the needs of certain students.

Law on Primary Education, Official Gazette of RS, no. 55/2013, 101/2017, 27/2018 and 10/2019, envisages, among the goals of primary education: providing a stimulating and safe environment for the overall development of students; developing non-violent behavior and establishing zero-tolerance policy for violence; developing a sense of solidarity, understanding and constructive cooperation with others and fostering camaraderie and friendship; development and respect for racial, national, cultural, linguistic, religious, gender, sex and age equality; development of tolerance and respect for diversity and of personal and national identity; development of awareness and sense of belonging to the Republic of Serbia; developing respect and nurture of Serbian language and native languages of national minorities; nurturing tradition and culture of the Serbian people and national minorities with the development of interculturality and developing respect and preservation of national and world cultural heritage (Art. 21).

Law on Secondary Education and Upbringing, Official Gazette of RS, no. 55/2013, 101/2017, 27/2018 and 6/2020, envisages that one of the goals of secondary education is to respect racial, national, cultural, linguistic, religious, gender, sex and age equality, and to develop tolerance and respect for diversity. (Art. 2).

Law on the Use of Sign Language, Official Gazette of RS, no. 38/2015, stipulates that deaf people have the right to use sign language, which includes the right to learn the language and the right to use the services of a sign language interpreter, whereby parents and elders of a deaf child, as well as all other persons, cannot prohibit a child to learn and use sign language (Art. 4). When it comes to the use of sign language in educational institutions, activities and programs could be conducted in sign language, while attending such a program is conditioned by the assessment on the need for additional support by appropriate interdepartmental commission (Art. 9).

Law on Pupil and Student Standards, Official Gazette of RS, no. 8/2010, 55/2013, 27/2018 and 10/2019, defines activities in the field of providing more accessible, efficient and quality education and upbringing for pupils and students. A high school student, among other things, has the right to: accommodation, food, educational work, student scholarships and additional activities such as cultural, artistic and non-formal education activities (Art. 3). In principle, all high school students from the territory of the Republic of Serbia can exercise their rights in the field of living standards, with the proviso that students belonging to vulnerable groups can exercise their rights under privileged conditions and in accordance with the law. The legislator defines students from vulnerable groups as students from economically deprived families, children without parental care, children belonging to Roma national minority, refugees, displaced persons and others (Article 4).

Law on Textbooks, Official Gazette of RS, no. 27/2018, defines the notion of textbooks, textbook sets, manuals and additional teaching aids. When it comes to the preparation, printing and distribution of textbooks, the Government decides on financing these activities, especially taking into account students coming from deprived settings, as well as students with disabilities. The legislator defines the term “low-circulation textbooks”, which include, among other things, textbooks in the languages and scripts of national minorities, as well as textbooks for special programs, such as programs for gifted students. Special funding rules apply to low-circulation textbooks. Textbooks and other resources should encourage equal opportunities and respect for diversity with their content and form (Art. 13).

Law on Adult Education, Official Gazette of RS, no. 55/2013, 88/2017, 27/2018 and 6/2020, envisages that adult education is part of the unique education system of the Republic of Serbia, which provides for the acquisition of competencies and qualifications necessary for personal and professional development, work and employment, or socially responsible behavior, in which adult education is realized as formal education, non-formal education and informal learning. One of the principles of adult education is the principle of equal opportunities, which includes inclusion in education regardless of age, gender, disability, developmental disabilities, racial, national and religious affiliation, sexual orientation and other personal characteristics.

Strategy for the Development of Education and Upbringing in the Republic of Serbia until 2030, Official Gazette of RS, no. 63/2021, builds on the strategy applied until 2020, as well as on the Strategy for the Prevention and Protection of Children from Violence for the period from 2020 to 2023. The new vision of the development of education in Serbia is based, among other things, on educational institutions that will build their own culture in which everyone is respected and cared for, as well as a culture of solidarity and mutual respect. The general goal is to provide quality education in order to realize full personal potential. Achievement of such a general goal implies setting a special goal in the form of improving teaching and learning. Improving teaching and learning, among other things, means reaffirming and strengthening the educational role of educational institutions that should also have an important public and cultural function:

The strategy states that the existing positive legal framework in the field of education is mostly harmonized with the relevant international anti-discrimination standards. Legislation in the field of education that has been adopted in recent years supports inclusive education by all means, not only when it comes to students with disabilities, but also for students who are at increased risk of exclusion from the system due to specific socio-economical conditions. However, this strategic document emphasizes that despite some progress, there is still no relevant data on the extent to which the goals of inclusive education have been achieved. It was noted that the appropriate level of inclusion has not been reached when it comes to people with disabilities and children with disabilities, so that the practice of forming special classes for these students is present even nowadays. Also, there is a lack of special measures for children who, due to social exclusion, do not use all the benefits of the educational process. Furthermore, the Strategy for the Development of Education in the Republic of Serbia until 2030 recognizes groups

that are at special risk of social exclusion and poverty and whose rights in the field of education should be especially guarded, so that among them are: children, pupils and students whose families have low socioeconomic status; members of the Roma national minority group, especially those living in disadvantage neighborhoods; persons with disabilities; residents of rural areas, especially residents of villages in border areas, etc.

It was noticed that a high number of children enrolled in primary education should be considered in the context of other data indicating that as many as 15% of children from Roma neighborhoods are outside primary education, and that Roma children most often drop out of schooling. Roma children continue to face discrimination and segregation and frequent enrollment in special schools, although modern science and international standards argue that educational neglect and material deprivation should not be the reason for enrollment in special schools. Schools attended exclusively by Roma children are still represented in the Serbian education system. It is worrying that the completion rate of secondary school in the general population is significantly higher than the rate for Roma. Inequalities are also present in the education of children with disabilities in relation to the education of the remaining student population.

The strategy emphasizes that individual discrimination is present in education in Serbia, as well as sexual harassment and homophobic behavior. Discriminatory and homophobic content is present in textbooks and teaching materials. There is a lack of content in teaching materials and textbooks that would encourage the nurturing of interculturality. Therefore, within the measures for improving programs in educational institutions, teaching and learning in pre-university education and upbringing, it is envisaged that textbooks should be adapted in order to be sensitive to gender equality and the specifics of different social groups, including vulnerable groups (without stereotypes, prejudices and discrimination). Also, activities to strengthen the capacity of employees in education should be aimed at fostering the principles of gender equality and non-discriminatory attitudes and behavior.

Strategy of scientific and technological development of the Republic of Serbia for the period from 2021 to 2025, “The Power of Knowledge”, is based on the assumption that Serbia will become a progressive and prosperous state if the fund of knowledge available to its people increases. The general goal of the strategy is a scientific-technological and innovation system that contributes to the accelerated development of Serbia through improving the quality and efficiency of science, technological development and innovation and to the further integration into the European Research Area, which contributes to reaching the standards of developed economies.

The document **Strategic Priorities for the Development of Culture from 2021 to 2025 - Cultural Policy, Challenges Today and in the Future Years**, adopted by the RS Government, identifies 20 priorities of cultural policy that require special attention. Policies in the world, Europe and the region are at a major turning point. One of the priority points is the preservation of cultural and historical heritage, bearing in mind that the preservation of national cultural heritage has a direct

impact on the adoption and nurturing of cultural and social values as a whole.

Rulebook on the protocol of actions in the institution in response to violence, abuse and neglect, Official Gazette of RS, no. 46/2019 and 104/2020, prescribes the content and methods of implementation of preventive and intervention activities, conditions and methods for risk assessment, methods of protection against violence, abuse and neglect, and monitoring the effects of measures and activities. The rulebook is to be applied in all sorts of institutions in the education system.

Rulebook on detailed criteria for recognizing forms of discrimination by an employee, child, student or third party in an educational institution, Official Gazette of RS, no. 22/2016, defines discrimination and discriminatory treatment in the educational context, while emphasizing that every participant in the education system has the right to be protected from discrimination. According to the Rulebook, discrimination and discriminatory treatment cover any unjustified discrimination, unequal treatment (exclusion, restriction or giving priority) or neglect, in relation to a person or groups of persons, as well as members of their families or relatives, in an open or covert manner, based on their personal characteristics.

Rulebook on the conduct of the institution in the case of suspicion or established discriminatory behavior and insult to the reputation or dignity of the person, Official Gazette of RS, no. 65/2018, defines the procedure to be applied in the institution when discriminatory behavior is suspected or established or when it is suspected or established that the reputation or dignity of a person has been insulted. The rulebook covers; ways of carrying out preventive and intervention activities; obligations and responsibilities of the child, student, adult, parent, or other legal representatives, employee, a third party in the institution, bodies of the institution and other issues. It is especially important that this bylaw also refers to segregation in the education system and that it defines preventive and interventional activities to combat this negative phenomenon.

Rulebook on performing community service and humanitarian work, Official Gazette of RS, no. 68/2018, defines community service and humanitarian work, which is determined for the student in parallel with the imposition of educational and educational-disciplinary measures. It is a work that includes activities which should nurture socially responsible behavior of students and which should help to restore the damage in the community.

Rulebook on quality standards of work of the institution, Official Gazette of RS – Education Gazette, no. 14/18, in the second part of the text which refers to the quality standards of school work in the field of quality number 4- Support to students – prescribes that the school has a support system for students from vulnerable groups, while in the field of quality number 5 – Ethos, it implies that adequate interpersonal relations are to be established at the school, measures and sanctions are to be consistently applied for discriminatory behavior, as well as the system of protection against violence should be functional.

Social protection

Different human rights are essentially intertwined nowadays, which implies that the establishment of a system in which cultural diversity is highly respected requires the realization of at least a minimal social rights.

The Law on Social Protection, Official Gazette of RS, no. 24/2011, defines the activities in the field of social protection, goals and principles on which the social protection system is based, as well as other issues essential for exercising the rights of users of social protection services. It should be emphasized that this law is based on a significantly different paradigm compared to previously valid regulations, given that the focus is on the service user who is seen as a bearer of potential for positive change and as a center towards which the entire social protection process is directed to. In a given system, the holder of a crucial role is the case manager, as an expert involved in the process of assessing and planning the necessary services, as well as an agent arranging access to necessary services. Social protection is defined as an organized activity of general interest, whose main goal is to provide assistance to achieve a productive and independent life, as well as to prevent and eliminate the consequences of social exclusion, in accordance with Art. 2. The right to social protection is exercised by every individual and family in need of help and support in overcoming life's difficulties and satisfying basic living needs, while the rights of the citizens are realized through social protection services and material support (Art. 4). Beneficiaries of social protection are citizens of Serbia, but they can also be foreign citizens and stateless persons, if it is in accordance with the law and relevant international agreements. Institutions that provide social protection cooperate closely with the education system, police, judiciary, health care system and all other sectors and institutions, primarily based on signing cooperation agreements.

The key institution in the social protection system is the center for social work, and next to it there are institutions for the education of children and youth, institutes for social protection and other entities. Funds for performing social protection activities come from the budget of Serbia, territorial autonomies and local self-government units, as well as from performing social protection activities. It should be emphasized that social care institutions, as well as social protection service providers, can be established with both public and private funds.

Among the principles on which social protection has based some principles especially stand out: the principle of respect for the integrity and dignity of beneficiaries, the principle of the best interests of beneficiaries and the principle of non-discrimination, Art. 24-32. The principle of accessibility and individualization of social protection implies that social protection services are provided in a way that implies their accessibility to users and also in a way that respects cultural and other differences, Art. 33.

The basic groups of beneficiaries of social protection are children and youth, under which entity the law recognizes minors and adults under 26 years of age. Children and young people may need social protection because they cannot meet their

basic needs within the family or they cannot overcome social exclusion, while the reasons for their difficult situation may include: lack of parental care or parents who are unable to meet their needs of young people; development issues; addiction and conflict with the law.

Social protection services are divided into: assessment and planning services, daily community services, independent living support services, counseling-therapeutic and social-educational services and accommodation services. In situations where the poverty and survival of the beneficiaries are endangered, emergency intervention services are also provided.

The administrative procedure needed for children and young people in order to exercise social rights is conducted exclusively by social work centers, which applies to all groups of users, whereby the centers with case managers decide on specific services that users will be catered to. The Center for Social Work issues referrals for the use of the social protection services, whereby the service is realized in the social protection institution or with the assistance of another authorized service provider. Depending on the circumstances of the specific case, the service will be financed from the budget or with partial or full coverage of costs by the service user or persons close to him.

In addition to using social protection services, children and young people can be beneficiaries of the right to material support. Material support includes financial social assistance, one-time financial assistance, training assistance and other types of material support. The right to financial social assistance can be exercised under certain conditions, while the basic condition refers to the fact that an individual or his family cannot satisfy their basic needs with their own income. A family in a state of social need is entitled to increased financial assistance if there are children under the age of 15 within the family, or if the family member is a young person under 26 and in regular schooling, since the law considers these two categories of persons incapable of work (Art. 85).

When it comes to children and young people, various social protection services, as well as the provision of material support, can be particularly important in preventing their social exclusion. Therefore, there is often talk about the need for cross-sectoral cooperation, so that with the cooperation of different services, children and young people would be able to realize their human rights and fulfill their personal potential.

The Law on Social Card, Official Gazette of RS, no 14/2021, defines the establishment and maintenance of the public register Social Card. This register records data on the users of social protection services and persons related to them, on the socio-economic status of these persons, as well as data related to the services and social protection rights used by these persons. The purpose of keeping such a register is, among other things, to improve the procedure for exercising the rights and services of social protection, equitable distribution of social services and insight into the effects of applied social policy measures, while the register is maintained by the competent ministry. Other data on members of vulnerable and socially vulnerable groups is also collected for the purposes of providing and planning assistance (Art. 6).

Law on Financial Support to Families with Children, Official Gazette of RS, no 113/2017, 50/2018, 46/2021, 51/2021 and 53/2021, contains provisions aimed at providing support to families with children, in order to enable exercise of the rights of the child and to provide support to parents in upbringing their children. Some of the rights that can be exercised in accordance with the provisions of the law are: the right to child allowance, the right to parental allowance, the right to funds for construction, participation in the purchase or purchase of a family building or apartment based on the birth of a child and one-time assistance for the birth of the second and third child. Families whose total income per member does not exceed the statutory threshold are entitled to the right to child allowance. The beneficiary of financial social assistance whose children attend school does not have to submit proof of financial status periodically, while the beneficiary whose child receives allowance for assistance and care of another person realizes the right to child allowance regardless of his income, in the sense of Art. 30.

Family Law, Official Gazette of RS, no 18/2005, 72/2011 and 6/2015, defines the property and personal family relations, as well as the status and rights of the child. Article 6 stipulates that everyone is obliged to be guided by the best interests of the child in every activity related to the child, while the state must take all measures to protect the child from neglect, abuse and exploitation. Children born outside marriage are completely equal to children born in marriage, while the same rules apply to the relationship between an adopted child and an adoptive parent as to the relationship between a child and a parent. When it comes to children without parental care, the state is obliged to provide them with family protection whenever possible.

The legislator has dedicated a special part of the text to the rights of the child. Thus, the child, among other things, has the right to be provided with the best possible conditions for proper and complete development, as well as the right to education in accordance with his wishes, preferences and abilities (Art. 62 and 63). Also, a child who is able to form an opinion has the right to express that opinion, as well as the right to be informed in a timely manner in order to form his/ her opinion. Due attention must be paid to the child's opinion, especially in the case of decisions related to the exercise of his rights, while a child who has reached 10 years of age may independently address the authorities to exercise the right to express an opinion (Art. 65). When it comes to foster care, it is based on the decision of the competent guardianship authority in order to protect the child's best interest. A child older than 10 years of age and capable of reasoning must agree with a foster care status, while foster parents should be persons who have passed the foster care preparation program (Art. 110-118).

The Law on Asylum and Temporary Protection, Official Gazette of the RS, no 24/2018, regulates the legal status of asylum seekers and persons granted asylum and temporary protection. Persons seeking or enjoying asylum and temporary protection shall not be discriminated against on the basis of any personal characteristics. The law provides special rights for minors who are asylum seekers or beneficiaries of asylum and temporary protection. Thus, the principle of protection of family is applied, so that based on it the authorities take all necessary measures to maintain the unity of the family of asylum seekers and other protected persons.

The law is applied in accordance with the principle of protection of the best interests of the minor, taking into account the welfare, social development and origin of the minor, his opinion depending on age and maturity, the principle of family unity, as well as the protection and safety of the minor. Special care is needed if there is a suspicion that a minor is a victim of human trafficking or a victim of domestic violence (Art. 10), while an unaccompanied minor is immediately assigned to a temporary guardian (Art. 12). Asylum seekers and users of asylum and temporary protection, as well as minors with their families, have the right to social assistance, health care and education. Under Art. 55 of the law, an asylum seeker is entitled to free primary and secondary education, in accordance with special regulations, while a minor asylum seeker is immediately provided with education services. It should be emphasized that users of asylum have the right to pre-school, primary, secondary and higher education under the same conditions as citizens of the Republic of Serbia, based on the regulations governing the field of education (Art. 64). According to Art. 71 Serbia is obliged to ensure the inclusion in the social, economic and cultural life of persons who have been granted the right to asylum. Persons who have been granted temporary protection (for a period of up to one year), which may occur in the event of a mass influx of displaced persons, are also eligible for free primary and secondary education in public schools (Article 76).

Strategy for the Development of Social Protection, Official Gazette of RS, no. 108/05, included activities in the social protection sector to be implemented until 2009, and its key objectives were: deinstitutionalization, decentralization and democratization of social protection services, improving social protection of the poorest citizens and developing the network of community services.

When it comes to social protection in Serbia at present time, the DRAFT Strategy of social protection in the Republic of Serbia for the period from 2019 to 2025 is currently available (initial version). The existing draft is in line with European values and good practices, bearing in mind the ongoing process of negotiations on Serbia's accession to the European Union.

The draft strategy states that the general social and demographic situation in Serbia is still characterized by a high emigration rate, intensive aging of the population and a high poverty rate. When it comes to the state of the social protection system, it was stated that the number of users of the social protection system is growing, while material support measures in the form of financial social assistance and child allowance are very common. About a third of children in Serbia receive a child allowance, with its amount in 2016 amounting to 2.660,00 dinars, while the increased child allowance amounted to 3.450,00 dinars. It is noticed that families with children are provided with fragmented and insufficiently coordinated support, while children who leave institutional accommodation are among the most vulnerable categories. Furthermore, when it comes to social protection services that are under the jurisdiction of local self-government units, it can be noticed that they are insufficiently represented and underdeveloped, with the most developed services being those for the elderly and for the children and youth with disabilities. Nevertheless, social care for elderly citizens is not at a satisfactory level.

It was stated that the social protection system has a significant role in providing educational support, especially for marginalized categories of the population, but that in this field the cooperation between educational institutions and the social welfare system is not sufficiently developed. There is an obvious lack of capacity and resources in social work/care centers that do not have an adequate number of skilled workers and are burdened with administrative work to the detriment of work with beneficiaries of social services.

One of the special goals of the Draft Strategy is the system of social protection which contributes to reducing social exclusion and encourages the active participation of citizens in society, with an emphasis on supporting families at risk and promoting gender and intergenerational solidarity. In that sense, the target values that should be reached by the end of 2025 are the increased share of funds of local self-government units in the provision of social protection services by 25%, and reduced rates of children and youth in institutional accommodation by at least 20%. Measures to be implemented to achieve these goals relate to the transformation of institutional accommodation capacity, primarily through their downsizing, while at the same time redirecting resources to satisfy social needs in the community, with a focus on protecting families and providing support for education.

Strategy for Social Inclusion of Roma Men and Roma Women in the Republic of Serbia for the period from 2016 to 2025, Official Gazette of RS, no. 26/2016, refers to the verified reports according to which the majority of Roma men and women face social exclusion and poverty, as well as open, and even more often, covert discrimination. The financial situation of Roma men and women is extremely difficult, so that according to relevant data, the share of users of social protection services in the Roma population is almost four times higher than in the total population in the Republic of Serbia. When it comes to education, children from the Roma community face numerous difficulties in exercising their rights to quality education, and are exposed to negative stereotypes and discrimination by educational institutions. Roma children are often not involved in the educational process, which has an extremely negative impact on their competitiveness in the labor market. It can be said that the Roma are in fact discriminated against in the exercise of all human rights, given that certain rights are intertwined, so that the strategy is aimed at improving the overall position of the Roma. The focus is on involving the Roma community in the process of defining and implementing measures, while eliminating discrimination. In this regard, the fact that scientific research on the issues of inclusion, life and customs, status and identity of Roma is insufficiently present in the social sciences and humanities in Serbia should be taken into account.

In order to improve the position of Roma, it is necessary to provide their equal access to the education system, but also to implement measures that will support the completion of the appropriate level of education by Roma students. It is indisputable that Roma students face discrimination in the education system, that they often do not have access to quality education and that they are unjustifiably enrolled in special schools. This is evidenced by the fact that the coverage of primary education in the general population is almost complete, while among the

Roma it is only 85%, with a significant number of students who do not complete primary education. Problems were noted regarding insufficient knowledge of the language in which teaching takes place, as well as insufficient support for learning the Romani language and the development of Romani cultural identity within formal education. Segregation of Roma is still present, so that despite some changes, there are cases of forming special Roma departments or entire Roma schools, especially within or near Roma neighborhoods. Segregated schools then face a lack of adequate teaching staff and inadequate curriculum quality. These phenomena naturally result in a lack of professional staff within the Roma population that could support the educational empowerment of Roma.

Having in mind the described situation, the general goal of the strategy is to improve the socio-economic position of the Roma national minority with full realization of minority rights, elimination of discrimination and achievement of greater social inclusion of Roma men and women in all segments of social life. One of the special goals is the inclusion of Roma children and youth in the education system, as well as the inclusion of young people and adults who have not been educated at all in a formal way. One of the measures to be implemented is the provision of additional social, economic and other support needed for inclusion in education, as well as, if necessary, the engagement of pedagogical assistants who would support the inclusion of Roma children in standard schools. In addition to the above, a number of measures and activities in the field of guaranteeing the right to housing and social protection are needed, in order for the Roma to truly become equal members of the community. In this regard, the workers of the centers for social work should develop culturally competent practices that would enable them to reach out to those citizens who actually need social protection services the most.

Within the Action Plan for the implementation of the Strategy for Social Inclusion of Roma Men and Women in the Republic of Serbia for the period from 2016 to 2025, one of the measures envisages the development of educational institutions as inclusive, intercultural, non-discriminatory and safe environment for Roma and all other children. development of an inclusive educational environment based on respect for diversity and promotion of equality, children's rights and human rights, while among the activities that should be implemented is the development of appropriate guidelines for anti-discrimination rules, and the removal of curricula that spread negative stereotypes about Roma, providing affirmative content about the Romani language, culture, history and traditions in the programs of various subjects, as well as elements of intercultural education.

The Strategy for Improving the Position of Persons with Disabilities in the Republic of Serbia for the Period from 2020 to 2024, Official Gazette of RS, no. 44/2020, and the accompanying Action Plan envisage that the main goal of implementing measures is to improve the overall social and economic position of persons with disabilities and to foster the realization of their full equality.

A person with a disability is defined as a person who has permanent physical, mental, intellectual or sensory difficulties that hinder the full realization of personal potential and participation in social processes. The strategy points out,

referring to the data from 2011, that as many as 8% of the population in Serbia are people with disabilities. Of particular concern is the fact that a significant number of people with disabilities continue to live in social care institutions, although the general trend is to force deinstitutionalization. Various stereotypes about the roles and characteristics of persons with disabilities are still present in the public, while an approach based on the “medical model of disability” is often present among professionals, although such an approach is known to be outdated. Particularly vulnerable categories are women with disabilities who may be discriminated against in multiple ways and also exposed to gender-based violence.

The vision the strategy is striving for is Serbia as an inclusive society in which persons with disabilities can exercise their rights on an equal basis and enjoy the freedoms guaranteed by national and international legal frameworks. The general goal of the strategy is to equalize the possibilities of persons with disabilities in relation to the possibilities of other citizens, and this is to be achieved through measures such as ensuring full accessibility of facilities, the inclusion of persons with disabilities in public life, providing measures to support community living instead of institutionalization, adequate and personalized support to include people with disabilities in an inclusive education system.

Strategy for Prevention and Control of HIV Infection and AIDS in the Republic of Serbia, 2018-2025, Official Gazette of RS, no. 61/2018, calls upon full exercise of the rights of persons infected with HIV, as well as to the eradication of their discrimination. The document states that Serbia is one of the countries with a low frequency of HIV infection, so that according to the data from 2017, there were about 3,100 infected people in the country, with an assumption that there is also around 3,100 people who are not aware of their HIV positive status. The vision of the strategy is Serbia as a country without new HIV infections and discrimination against people living with HIV and against key populations at risk of HIV. One of the specific goals is to reduce stigma and eliminate discrimination against people living with HIV, by implementing measures to improve the capacity to combat discrimination. It is necessary to implement activities in the form of training for professionals in various sectors, including the education and social protection sector, in order to raise their awareness of the need to fully realize the notion of human rights of people living with HIV.

Strategy for deinstitutionalization and development of social protection services in the community for the period 2022-2026, Official Gazette of RS, no. 12/2022 envisages the development of a network of community-based services, which will enable citizens to fulfill most of their needs at the local level and consequently reduce the number of citizens who in need of institutional accommodation services. The document is primarily aimed at people with mental disabilities, who are at the highest risk of institutionalization and social exclusion. The strategy emphasizes that it is indisputable that the number of children and young people in institutions has decreased in recent years, while the situation is not so favorable when it comes to adults.

The main problem that the strategy focuses on is the lack of services that are provided in the community, as well as the insufficient investment of funds at the local level in the organization and subsequent maintenance of such services.

Namely, the idea that came from the implementation of the previous strategy was to gradually transform institutions for accommodation into institutions that will provide accommodation services with only a minimal part of their capacity, while focusing on support services for families and children with disabilities and on respite services. At the same time, it would increase the number of users with social protection services provided in the community. However, such an idea was realized on a modest level, primarily due to inconsistencies in the financing of services at the local level. Hence, the new strategy envisages measures and activities to improve the system in terms of personnel and infrastructure.

The vision of the strategic document implies a society in which everyone lives in the community and has their needs met in the natural environment, while the general goal is to completely finalize the processes of deinstitutionalization and social inclusion. One of the special goals is to empower users for the deinstitutionalization process, but also to empower professionals and other actors to implement and advocate for the deinstitutionalization. Relevant trainings should be organized to develop skills and knowledge of professionals and their coworkers in the social protection system. All professionals should pass at least one accredited program in the field of deinstitutionalization, while both professionals and the general public are expected to manifest greater knowledge about the rights of people with intellectual disabilities at the end of the strategy period.

Strategy for Prevention and Protection against Discrimination for the period from 2022 to 2030, Official Gazette of RS, no. 12/2022, is based on the vision of the Republic of Serbia as an inclusive society, with zero tolerance for discrimination, in which all citizens, regardless of personal characteristics, have equal opportunities to enjoy all rights and freedoms. However, the strategy states that, despite the successes achieved in achieving the goals of the previous strategy, there is still a risk of social exclusion of many members of different marginalized groups. Unlike the previous strategy, which singled out groups at special risk of discrimination (national minorities, women, LGBT persons, persons with disabilities, elderly, children, refugees, internally displaced persons and migrants, religious minorities and people discriminated against due to health conditions), the current strategy deals with the analysis of the risk of discrimination in various areas of human rights. The following areas have been highlighted: public administration and the judiciary; defense, home affairs and security; education, vocational training and science; work and employment; social protection; housing; health care and sports, culture and media.

The change that needs to be achieved through the implementation of the strategy is to build an inclusive society that does not tolerate, but notices and respects differences, and in which each person can realize their full potential, feel accepted and participate equally in all areas of social life. The basis for building such a society is the elimination of stereotypes, harmful patterns and prejudices, the promotion of a culture of human rights and respect for every person regardless of personal characteristics that characterize him or her.

Rulebook on additional educational, health and social support for children, students and adults, Official Gazette of RS, no. 80/2018, regulates conditions for

assessing the need for providing additional educational, health and social support for children, students and adults, as well as the composition and modus operandi of the interdepartmental commission that values the need for additional support. Additional support includes rights, services and resources that provide the student with help for overcoming physical, communicational and social barriers within educational institutions and in the community. Support measures include the provision of additional resources and services to meet the educational, health and social needs of students with disabilities, but may also include the provision of support measures to overcome the language barrier for students whose native language is not spoken at school and also the application of other measures that are needed in a particular case.

Rulebook on conditions and standards for the provision of social protection services, Official Gazette of RS, no. 42/2013, 89/2018 and 73/2019, stipulates the minimum standards relating to the provision of all social protection services. Minimum standards include the minimum structural standards, which refer to the infrastructure, personnel and organization, and the minimum functional standards, which refer to the necessary traits and structure of professional procedures. There are some common minimum standards that apply to all services and to all groups of users and special minimum standards that can apply to a specific service and a specific group of users, taking into account the specifics of both services and groups of users. Common minimum structural standards address issues such as publicity of work, hygiene and working hours of the service provider, while common minimum functional standards relate to the reception of users, assessment of needs, development of staff competencies and other.

When it comes to providing daycare services, these services are available for: children and young people with physical disabilities; persons with intellectual disabilities, who need daycare and supervision as well as support in maintaining and developing their potential and children and young people in conflict with the law, parents, school or community (Art. 68). As for the purpose of the daycare services, it is reflected in improving the quality of life of users in their own social environment through maintaining and developing social and other functions and skills, in order to enable them to live as independently as possible. Development needs of users are being met through the daycare service, so that they acquire and develop life skills, personal and social responsibility, as well as develop other functions (Art. 69).

Among other services, some users can have access to the shelter service, which is founded for children, young people, adults and the elderly who live or work on the street and who voluntarily request or agree to this service. The purpose of the shelter service is to provide temporary or occasional interventions and to meet the current needs of users, as well as to mediate in ensuring the availability of other services in the community (Art. 78).

Rulebook on professional affairs in social protection, Official Gazette of RS, no. 1/2012, stipulates that the basic professional activities in social protection are giving information, assessment, planning, mediation and advocacy in the exercise of rights for users, guidance, socio-educational activities, implementation of protective

measures and monitoring the effects of services and measures in direct work with the user. A professional worker can be by education: social worker, psychologist, pedagogue, andragogue, special educator and special pedagogue, who has a license to perform basic tasks in social protection. Specialized social protection activities include: individual and group counseling and family therapy, mediation, implementation of accredited programs of intensive family support services, accredited socio-educational programs and accredited treatment programs (Art. 6), while these activities can be performed by professionals who have acquired knowledge, skills and a license to perform a specific specialized task.

Rulebook on prohibited actions of employees in social protection system, Official Gazette of RS, no. 8/2012 emphasizes that physical, emotional and any other abuse and neglect of users of social services is strictly prohibited. It was pointed out that discrimination based on nationality, ethnicity, cultural and linguistic differences, religious, gender, socio-economic differences and differences due to disability and sexual orientation or other personal characteristics is considered a form of abuse. In the case of abuse and neglect of the minor, the Protocol on the Protection of the Child from Abuse and Neglect must be applied.

Youth work

Law on Youth, Official Gazette of RS, no. 50/2011, regulates the principle of equality and non-discrimination of young people, stating that all young people are equal, and that any discrimination, direct or indirect, or unequal treatment of young people is prohibited, especially if it is based on race, sex, nationality, religious beliefs, language, social origin, economic status, membership in political parties, unions and other organizations, mental or physical disability, health status, physical appearance, sexual orientation, gender identity and other real or presumed personal characteristics. The law stipulates that youth policy includes measures and activities of state bodies, institutions, associations and other entities aimed at improving the position of youth, while the youth sector includes all areas in which youth activities are performed, which are defined by the general goals of the National Youth Strategy.

All persons who are over 15 and under 30 years of age are considered young people. Youth work covers all sorts of youth activities that are organized with young people and for young people based on non-formal education. Youth activities take place within the free time of young people and are organized to improve the conditions for personal and social development of young people in accordance with their needs and abilities and with their voluntary participation.

Non-formal education for young people is a set of organized and youth-friendly educational activities that are not provided for in the formal education system. Non-formal education activities are based on the needs and interests of young people, and the principles of voluntary and active participation of young people in the learning process and the promotion of democratic values, so that young people acquire competencies necessary for personal development, active participation in society and better employability.

The basic principles in working with young people are: the principle of support for young people, the principle of equality and non-discrimination, the principle of equal opportunities, the principle of raising awareness of the importance of young people and their social role, the principle of active youth participation and the principle of responsibility and solidarity.

When it comes to conceiving and implementing policies in the youth sector, the Government, at the proposal of the relevant ministry, establishes the Youth Council as an advisory body that encourages and coordinates activities related to the development and implementation and of youth policy and proposes measures for its improvement. The Youth Council consists of representatives of state administration bodies whose areas of interest are youth and representatives of the provincial administration body responsible for youth issues, associations and federations, youth offices, as well as a joint representative of national councils of national minorities and distinguished experts. At least one-third of the members of the Youth Council are representatives of young people from the ranks of associations and federations.

The Provincial Youth Council, the Youth Council of Local Self-Government Units, the Youth Office and the Youth Agency can also be established, all in the spirit of mobilizing young people to participate in political life, both in terms of issues directly related to them and in matters of general social interest.

National Youth Strategy for the period from 2015 to 2025, Official Gazette of RS, no. 22/2015, envisages the principle of respect for human and minority rights, equality and non-discrimination as one of the key principles on which the implementation of youth policies is based on. Strategy is oriented towards improving the social position of young people and creating conditions for exercising the rights and interests of this population in all areas. The strategy stipulates that the term "young" covers all persons aged from 15 to 30 and emphasizes that all young people are equal, so that they should enjoy the same position and equal legal protection regardless of personal characteristics. The analysis of the current situation in the youth field indicates the need to strengthen the capacity of the ministry responsible for youth and sports, as well as the need to build local infrastructure to support youth. There is a need for a more transparent decision-making process with timely information for young people and the need for greater youth strategic activities, which is especially true for young members of vulnerable social groups. Among the strategic goals defined by the strategy some goals are: capacity building for youth qualifications and competencies, active participation of young men and women in society, support for social inclusion of young people at risk of social exclusion and youth participation in creating cultural content.

When it comes to youth education, it is emphasized that in addition to acquiring qualifications, the basic goal of education is to collect quality knowledge and build skills and attitudes for personal achievement and development, inclusion and employment. In addition to formal education for young people, increasing the capacity for non-formal education is extremely important. The number of non-formal education programs should be increased and also it is necessary to formally recognize the competencies acquired through youth work. Experience

indicates that the competencies acquired through non-formal education are those that have a positive effect on finding employment, as well as that the level of development of competencies is significantly influenced by the length of participation and frequency of participation in non-formal education programs. The strategy notes that the activities should be aimed at strengthening the competencies of members of marginalized groups, such as Roma, but that the development of competencies of talented young people should also be supported, which is already done to some extent through the support provided by the Fund for Young Talents.

Encouraging volunteerism is also important, both in society as a whole and especially among young people. In the spirit of encouraging volunteerism, the strategy suggests the implementation of activities such as: supporting the inclusion of young volunteers in short-term and long-term volunteer programs; encouraging educational, cultural and sports institutions to recognize and support youth volunteering and establishing a system for recognizing skills acquired through volunteering.

The social inclusion of young people should also be encouraged, especially bearing in mind that young people are at very high risk of poverty. The enjoyment of social protection services by young people is greatly influenced by the fact that they are not seen as a separate social group, bearing in mind that social regulations recognize young people between 18 and 26 years of age, while according to categories from the census young people are those that are less than 29 years old. In addition, there is a significant number of young people from vulnerable groups within the youth population, such as LGBTI people and Roma, so their age and marginalization should be taken into account when meeting their needs. When it comes to social protection, it is extremely important to increase the number of local social services for children and youth, given that mostly only daycare services for children and youth with disabilities have been developed so far.

Strategy for Prevention and Protection of Children from Violence for the Period from 2020 to 2023, Official Gazette of RS, no. 80/2020, is based on the postulate that the prevention and suppression of violence against children and the protection of children from violence are among the crucial priorities of the national policy of Serbia. It is further stated that 1.263.128 children live in Serbia, which represents 21% of the total population of the country, and that various types of abuse and neglect of children are unfortunately widely represented. Thus, violence against children is manifested in the family, as well as in educational institutions, communities, social institutions and the digital sphere. The strategy defines 11 key priorities on which the policy of treatment of children should be based, whereby children must not be exposed to any kind of discrimination concerning origin, family status, language, gender or any personal characteristics. Some of the mentioned priorities are: to support the family in order to develop parental competencies, develop prevention services for children, direct support and protection of children from vulnerable groups (such as children with disabilities and children in conflict with the law) and encourage deinstitutionalization with a better system of supervising the remaining institutions for the accommodation of children. One of the special goals of the

strategy is to change attitudes towards violence against children, in which sense measures and activities are taken to strengthen the competencies of those who work with children, but also measures and activities are taken to sensitize wider public in order to understand the phenomenon of violence against children.

Current national legislation on diversity in Italy

Eleonora Di Liberto, Giulia Messina

An analysis of the state of the policy framework for social inclusion in Italy in the fields of social welfare, education and youth work from the constitution to laws and strategies.

I – Italian Constitution

The Constitution of the Italian Republic provides 4 articles about education, social welfare and youth work.

1.1. Education

In Italy, Constitution provides Education for everyone, without any discrimination. The 34th article of the Italian Constitution is a symbol of the openness of education to everyone. It says: "Schools are open to all. Lower education, given for at least eight years, is compulsory and free. Those students capable and deserving, even if without financial means, have the right to reach the highest levels of studies. The Republic makes this right effective with scholarships, family allowances and other benefits, which must be awarded by competition."

First of all, in Italy education is a duty, because culture is a fundamental value for the intellectual growth of individuals and for the development of society. The 34th article is about the right to education, in continuity with Article 33. It starts from a principle of extreme social importance, in line with the provisions of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the Union European: the fact that the school is free and open to all. It does not discriminate in terms of financial means or learning ability, the right to study is also recognized for students with disabilities for whom personalised educational plans with support teachers are provided. Also, for migrant students, in addition to courses for learning the Italian language, a specific cultural mediation is provided. The education system in Italy is organised according to the subsidiary principle and autonomy of schools (33rd article). The State has exclusive competence on general issues on education, on minimum standards to be guaranteed throughout the country and on the fundamental principles that Regions should comply within their competences. Regions have exclusive competence on vocational education and training. Schools are autonomous as for didactic, organisation and research and development activities.

1.2. Social welfare

About Social Welfare (called as Previdenza sociale), the 3rd article of Italian Constitution says: "It is a duty of the Republic to remove any obstacles that

constrain freedom and equality of citizens to assure the full development of the human person". Article 3 should be divided into two parts: the first part it is recognized equality in a formal sense ("All citizens have equal social dignity and are equal before the law, without distinction of sex, race, language, religion, political opinions, personal and social conditions") while 2nd paragraph establishes equality in a concrete way (" It is the duty of the Republic to remove the obstacles of an economic and social and the equality of citizens, prevent the full development of the human person ").

A formal equality means that people are on the same level: everyone is equal before the law and must respond to it without any diverse treatment dictated by a particular social background, culture, or gender. And for this reason, Italy has a duty in that sense: to remove obstacles in self-realisation of its citizens. As far as substantial equality is concerned, it can be summarised in this way: each individual has the possibility of realising his own life without any kind of obstacle related with social background or with other types of particular constraints. This means that, with the right commitment and a good dose of luck, even a humble person can become wealthy.

1.3. Youth work

About youth work there is nothing very specific in Italy, above all in the Italian Constitution. Otherwise, it is guaranteed a form of protection by the State. About this topic, the 31st article says: "(The State) protects motherhood, childhood and youth, promoting the institutions necessary for this purpose". The legislation, inspired by the 31st article, provides for a series of measures for the creation of structures and bodies aimed at promoting policies in support of children and young people, for example in the fields of culture, sport and education. The protection of youth is provided also in the workplace, with the various support for recruitment provided for by law in favour of young people (for whom, some forms of social security relief are often provided). So, the laws that facilitate the employment of young people are due to the Constitution itself, which protects youth the most. On the other hand, the 117th article says that issues relating to young people are governed by concurrent legislation. Therefore, the legislative power about youth policies is attributed both to the central government and to the regions and autonomous provinces; the determination of the fundamental principles is instead reserved to the law of the State. It means, there are fundamental topics like social welfare or protection of motherhood, children and youth, which are under the protection of the government of Italy.

II - Italian legislation (laws and strategies)

2.1. Education

The education system in Italy is organised according to the subsidiary principle and autonomy of schools.

The State has exclusive competence on general issues on education, on minimum standards to be guaranteed throughout the country and on the fundamental principles that Regions should comply within their competences. Regions have exclusive competence on vocational education and training. Schools are autonomous as for didactic, organisation and research and development activities. Education is compulsory for 10 years, from 6 to 16 years of age, and covers the eight-year first cycle of education (5 years of primary school and 3 years of lower secondary school) and the first two years of the second cycle (DM 139/2007). However, all students have the formal right to continue their studies via general or vocational pathways until the age of 18/19, including students with disabilities.

Educational provision is granted for students with disabilities in all phases of education, even after compulsory school. Every child from 0 to 3 years of age is entitled to go to the crèche (day nursery) along with all the other children; these facilities are directly dependent on the local Council, which draws up proper regulations for their functioning, and disabled children have priority for admission lists. Law 104/92 provides for the presence of support teachers in all schools. The number of hours spent with the child by the support teacher is based on the Functional Dynamic Profile and is therefore appropriate to the child's needs.

The teacher is assigned to the whole class and collaborates with other teachers to improve the inclusion of the disabled child, who is part of the class as well and to whom all teachers must relate. Often Assistant/educator for inclusion and communication and the assistant for personal hygiene at school and for afternoon home assistance is provided by the Municipality. Most assistants have university degrees. While the specialised support teacher is co-titular in the classroom and therefore responsible for the whole class, the assistant ad personam is a support measure allocated to the student with disabilities only. Where there is a disabled student, it has been established that there cannot be more than 20 pupils in the first classes of the respective cycles. Free transportation to and from school is provided by the Municipality. Specific didactic material is supplied mainly by the Municipalities and partly by the school administration. As regards university, Law 104/92 provides that disabled students with the legal qualifications may negotiate syllabuses and examination modalities with the professors. According to Act 17/99 every university should have a professor in charge of the reception of disabled students and there must be "tutors" (undergraduate students). The University should guarantee the elimination of architectural barriers and there should be assistants to support the mobility.

It is necessary to submit a document attesting the degree of disability at the time when the child is enrolled; this also has to show a functional diagnosis which singles out the areas of the child's functional potential, as well as verifying the kind of disability and its seriousness. The functional diagnosis is written by the team of doctors of the local public health unit.

The Presidential Decree dated on 19.5.2006 states that the Medical Commission in charge for delivering the certificate of disability must refer to the International Indicators OMS – ICF.

From 2017 (Legislative Decree 66/2017 - ART. 16) Educational institutions, in collaboration with the regional school office, local authorities and local health cooperatives can provide home education to guarantee the right education for students whom it is ascertained that it is impossible to attend school for a period of not less than thirty days of lessons, even if not continuous, a cause of serious certified pathologies, also through projects that can make use of the use of new technologies.

As for the phenomenon of recent migration, it was important to answer to new needs in education, through the law 47 of 2017, educational institutions of all types and levels and the educational institutions accredited by the regions and autonomous provinces of Trento and Bolzano activate measures to facilitate the fulfilment of compulsory education and training for unaccompanied foreign minors, also through the preparation of specific projects that involve, where possible, the use or coordination of cultural mediators, as well as agreements aimed at promoting specific apprenticeship programs. Schools have to follow the "Guidelines for the right to education of minors outside the family of origin", that means: "To guarantee the right to study of this type of pupils, it is necessary to allow enrolment and placement in school at any time of the year, even after the deadline has expired and by submitting the enrolment application directly to the chosen school, without having to use the online registration platform." Everyone has the right to study, it is written in Italian constitution and implemented by different laws and strategies: a Ministerial Circular 2 of 8 January 2010 - about integration of pupils with non-Italian citizenship attributes the responsibility of integration and inclusion to the schools through network of schools, diversified educational offer, quality projects for the schools at risk to attract the native students, strengthening of the extra-curricular activities to facilitate the social inclusion of the new-comers. Inclusion of refugees and also of people with special needs: the "Hosting protocol"/ Protocollo di accoglienza is an operational document which is proposed as a guide information for teachers, school staff and parents, functional to the reception and inclusion of pupils with Special Educational Needs.

Education is an important field, and it is valuable to be part of the 4th mission of the Italian recovery plan. State wants to promote reforms and investments to reduce the structural deficiencies of the Italian education system. It includes kindergartens, childcare services, increasing basic skills, tackling early school leaving and educational poverty, active guidance in the school-university transition, extension of full time and canteens and the strengthening of sports infrastructures at school, scholarships for university access, student accommodation and extension of the number of research doctorates.

2.2. Social welfare

In 1992 the Italian Parliament approved the Disabled Persons Bill (L.104/92), it represent the main frame for all disability issues: it guarantees people with disabilities and their families the ownership of specific rights; it provides assistance; it states the full integration and the adoption of prevention measures and functional recovery; it ensures social, economic and legal protection, creating the premises and conditions for full affirmation of civil rights and participation

in the social life (family, school, work, leisure time) of disabled people. It states the principle of inclusion - in any public service and in any funding - as a right of people with disabilities. It contains dispositions about:

- ◆ interventions for prevention and early diagnosis;
- ◆ care and rehabilitation;
- ◆ services for social integration;
- ◆ labour inclusion;
- ◆ personal support provided by the local authorities;
- ◆ daily centres and rehabilitation centres;
- ◆ adapting Public and Private buildings and equipment enabling the removal of any barriers (architectural and sensorial);
- ◆ transport: Local Authorities are required to provide free transport for people with disabilities - in particular, Local Boards have to provide the daily transport of people with disabilities to schools and education and health centres and sport and leisure time centres during the day (according to their budget);
- ◆ work permits for carers to assist their relatives with disability;
- ◆ education and school life.

Work placement and economic autonomy are absolutely very important factors for social integration of people with disabilities. The Italian law has had a significant development in that field, in fact the 68/99 Act "Norme per il diritto al lavoro dei disabili" (law for right of working disable people), promotes work placement and work integration of disabled people by supporting services and aimed employment. The principle of aimed employment foresees that the placement of the disabled person respects the working capacities of the workers without penalising the expectations of the employing company. In other words, the company has to charge the disable person with a necessary job and at the same time suitable for his capacities and adapted to his needs (through support aids if necessary) in order that the engagement will result fruitful for each other. The accommodation of disabled persons in a job is decided by a medical commission of the local ASP (Provincial Sanitary Agency).

This commission has the following tasks: to formulate a functional diagnosis in order to determine the whole ability of disabled persons i.e. to specify the grade and quality of his/her impairments and the type of this; to propose the lines to facilitate his/her accommodation in a job. The commission will precisè the position of disabled persons inside his/her environment, attitudes, family relations, taking into account the school's degree and the work already effected in order to create a detailed schedule of the work potential of the person with disability. The system for the aimed working placement is focused on people in working age with physical, psychic, sensorial, intellectual and relational disabilities, furthermore to the people with civil disability; up of 45%, working disability up of 33%, total blindness o with blindness a residual of no more than one tenth in both eyes with a correction, deafness at birth or before the speaking learning, war disability, civil disability of war and disability for service. Compulsory employment quota system.

Based on the size of the workforce, both private and public sector employers are required to hire a certain percentage of disabled workers:

- ◆ Employers with more than 50 employees must meet a 7% disability employment quota;
- ◆ At least two disabled workers must be hired in workplaces with 36 to 50 employees;
- ◆ Workplaces of 15 to 35 employees must hire at least one disabled worker if they operate a new intake.

The 68/99 Act foresees an incentive for the enterprises which conform their behaviour to the law: exempting the companies from social security taxes up to 100% and up to eight years proportionally to the disability of the workers to be employed; partially reimbursing the expenses for the adaptation of the work environment; financing activities aimed to support work placement of invalids. Law 68/99 established the creation of lists for employment.

On 10 October 2002 the President of the Italian Republic promulgated a Regulation n. 333 to implement the law 1999, which contains a further specification of people having the right to be enclosed into the special lists for the compulsory assumption, the duty to reserved parts, the exceptions to such duties and the suspension from them, the way to enrol people. The principle indicated in that act regards the so-called nominative assumptions that means that the public and private employers have the possibility to choose inside of the lists the Disabled Person who has more ability to effect a certain work and to call this person. Italian legislation pays special attention to the cooperative enterprises which are divided in two categories in conformity with art. 1 of Law 8 November 1991 n. 381: category A - finalised to the management of social-sanitary and educational services; category B - with the aim to give job opportunities to disabled persons.

Most type B social cooperatives have been established to provide temporary employment for disabled people and subsequently ensure they are hired by standard companies. However, although the main objective of such cooperatives is to find outside work for disabled people, they may also employ them permanently within their own co-operative or find jobs in other cooperatives when workers are unable to find other employment.

Another important law in the field of inclusion is the Law 180/78, the reform of the psychiatric system in Italy: it contained directives for the closing down of all psychiatric hospitals and led to their gradual replacement with a whole range of community-based service. This law is a revolutionary measure regarding mental health and it that all health treatments are voluntary (except in a few cases). After this law, all the asylums were closed, and the concept of mental rehabilitation was revised: no more restraints and the promotion of inclusion and integration of people with mental health problems in society. It gave dignity to psychiatric patients removing barriers and bad terminology regarding mental health and protection for people with mental health issues.

About the provision of social services, in general there is the trend to decentralise

it, at first through the Law 381/91 which recognized and defined the role of social co-operatives, non-profit organisations to deliver social services, by agreement with municipalities, able to produce wider benefits for the local community and its citizens, especially if these citizens are disadvantaged. This process had its maximum expression with Law 328/00, that aims to refine "Integrated system of interventions and social services"; it is a welfare reform to develop "local welfare" and an integrated system of social services introducing the use of Local Social Plans, based on the principles of subsidiarity, co-operation and services integration, and the individual project of life that families can request and agree with Municipalities in order to realise a full integration "within the family and social life".

Non-discrimination in speech, acts and work is ensured by the law n. 205/93, which sanctions and condemns phrases, gestures, actions and slogans with the purpose of inciting hatred, incitement to violence, discrimination and violence on racial, ethnic, religious or national grounds, and by the legislative decrees 215 and 216 - 2003, introduced according to European directives of 2000 - the States develops and implements new possibilities about the equal treatment of races, religions, disabilities and sexual orientation and the European objectives of promotion of gender equality from the point of view of economic independence, remuneration for equal work performed and participation in decisions. Legislative Decree 215/2003 is thus applicable to discrimination on the grounds of race and ethnic origin in all the fields mentioned in Directive 2000/43/EC, while Decree 216/2003 applies within the field of employment to discrimination based on religion and belief, sexual orientation, disability and age.

Equality means equality in any field, for these reason in 2006 the Law 76 ruled LGBT civil marriage in Italy and the rights for homosexual people connected to marriage.

As regards the topic of gender equality in our country is not governed by the State but in our Recovery Plan (1st Mission), it is suggested as a strategy for the years 2021-2026, to encourage female participation in the labour market, directly or indirectly, and to correct the asymmetries that hinder equal opportunities from school age. It aims to promote equality, although there are no specifically gender-specific measures. Among other things, the mission provides for the adoption of new recruitment mechanisms and the revision of those to identify managers, in order to neutralize discrimination and bring out merit in a path that often penalizes women. The measures dedicated to agile work and connectivity are designed to encourage a better balance between professional and private life, for the benefit of those (much more often women) who are forced to choose between work and family. From a technical and technological point of view, the allocations provided for the ultra-broadband are designed to support entrepreneurship, including those run by women. In the 4th Mission of Recovery Plan there is the promise to increase in employment and inclusion prospects with respect to marginal situations: through the strengthening of Employment Centres, the creation of women's businesses, the universal civil service for young people between 18 and 28 and the so-called "dual system" which, in line with what we saw in mission 4, sets itself the task of linking training and the labour market using an on-the-job learning approach.

2.3 Youth work

At a national level a framework law on young people hasn't been approved yet, among the 20 Italian regions, 16 have their own legislation on youth policies.

Nevertheless, Italy has its own National Youth Strategy: each year the national government establishes the priorities of policies for young people, after consultation with the Regions and other competent local authorities. The Department for Youth Policy and Universal Civil Service (DPGSCU) manages the Annual Fund for Youth Policy, which aims to promote the rights of young people and support the annual strategy, through calls for proposals by youth organisations and civil society organisations. From 2006 the fund for youth policy is being funding initiatives to promote:

- ◆ **Non formal and informal education***
- ◆ **Young people access to the job market**, including the creation of start-ups and youth entrepreneurship
- ◆ **Social inclusion** and specific measures to reach the disadvantaged groups of young people
- ◆ **Youth participation** and rights
- ◆ Cultural activities, talent development
- ◆ **Prevention and contrast of addictions**
- ◆ Volunteering and access to European programmes and projects

*In bold are the national political priorities for the field of youth.

...

The above analysis underlines how the Italian constitution states the formal equality of all the citizens and the duty of the government to remove obstacles in self-realisation of its citizens, as well as it provides Education for everyone, without any discrimination. In both the fields of social welfare and education the measures for the inclusion of people with disabilities are the ones more structured and detailed, able to provide a comprehensive framework of measures and rights both to the beneficiaries of the laws and to the service providers. That, in spite of the fact that the laws related to the inclusion of people with disability are very old (the one about the inclusion of people with disabilities in the labour market has been approved in 1968, the one about the inclusion of people with disability is from 1992); if these laws were futuristic in the years they have been drafted, they really need to be revised now, most of all about the definition of disability they are based on, as a physical, psychological, sensory impairment. As regards the measures addressing non-discrimination, they appear fragmented and too general in terms of concrete application: for example, the legislative decrees 215 and 216 - 2003 refer to the duty for the employer to provide a "reasonable accommodation" but they do not give a definition of reasonable accommodation nor any sort of guidance to employers on how to respect this duty, but simply compels employers to make provision for reasonable accommodation. This together with the lack of provision of funds to be allocated to the cause of fostering non-discrimination, makes the application of the law's provisions harder to be realised.

However, the field of education is the one more exhaustively covered and protected by the Italian legislation and protocols with specific measures both for the inclusion of pupils with disability and foreigner students and with concrete measures to ensure education for all.

The field of youth work is not even covered in the national framework of laws and the youth policies are regulated by regional laws but only in the 80% of the regions. The national strategy for youth together with a national programme of paid traineeship (Garanzia Giovani) and some tax relief for those who employ under 35 with a permanent contract are the main elements of the national provisions for young people in Italy. It seems that Diversity revolution in Italy still needs to define its strategy.

Current national legislation on diversity in Slovenia

Tea Radojković, Anja Palčič

The Constitution

Article 14 (Equality before the Law) – In Slovenia everyone shall be guaranteed equal human rights and fundamental freedoms irrespective of national origin, race, sex, language, religion, political, or other conviction, material standing, birth, education, social status, disability, or any other personal circumstance. All are equal before the law.

Article 52 (Rights of Disabled Persons) – Disabled persons shall be guaranteed protection and work-training in accordance with the law. Physically or mentally handicapped children and other severely disabled persons have the right to education and training for an active life in society. The education and training referred to in the preceding paragraph shall be financed from public funds.

Article 57 (Education and Schooling) – Freedom of education shall be guaranteed. Primary education is compulsory and shall be financed from public funds. The state shall create the opportunities for citizens to obtain a proper education.

Article 64 (Special Rights of the Autochthonous Italian and Hungarian National Communities in Slovenia) – The autochthonous Italian and Hungarian national communities and their members shall be guaranteed the right to use their national symbols freely and, in order to preserve their national identity, the right to establish organisations and develop economic, cultural, scientific, and research activities, as well as activities in the field of public media and publishing. In accordance with laws, these two national communities and their members have the right to education and schooling in their own languages, as well as the right to establish and develop such education and schooling. The geographic areas in which bilingual schools are compulsory shall be established by law. These national communities and their members shall be guaranteed the right to foster relations with their nations of origin and their respective countries. The state shall provide material and moral support for the exercise of these rights. In order to exercise their rights, the members of these communities shall establish their own self-governing communities in the geographic areas where they live. On the proposal of these self-governing national communities, the state may authorise them to perform certain functions under national jurisdiction, and shall provide funds for the performing of such functions. The two national communities shall be directly represented in representative bodies of local self-government and in the National Assembly. The position of the Italian and Hungarian national communities and the manner in which their rights are exercised in the geographic areas where they live, the obligations of the self-governing local communities for the exercise of

these rights, and those rights which the members of these national communities exercise also outside these areas, shall all be regulated by law. The rights of both national communities and their members shall be guaranteed irrespective of the number of members of these communities. Laws, regulations, and other general acts that concern the exercise of the constitutionally provided rights and the position of the national communities exclusively, may not be adopted without the consent of representatives of these national communities.

Article 65 (Status and Special Rights of the Romany Community in Slovenia) – The status and special rights of the Romany community living in Slovenia shall be regulated by law.

Education

In the Basic school act, article 2a (Safe and Supportive Learning Environment) it is pointed out that kindergartens, schools and other institutions for education of SEN children shall in line with the goals of the previous article, guarantee a safe and supportive learning environment wherein physical punishment of children and of any kind of violence against and among children, as well as discrimination on the grounds of gender, sexual orientation, social and cultural background, religion, race, ethnic and national origin, physical and mental development shall be disallowed.

In the Placement of children with special needs act, article 3 (Application of regulations on education) it is indicated that education of children with special needs shall be carried out in accordance with this Act and the regulations governing the field of pre-school education, basic school education, vocational and technical education and general upper-secondary education (hereinafter: regulations in the field of education). In article 9 (Implementation of additional professional assistance) it is pointed out that: (1) Additional professional assistance shall be provided individually or in a group, inside or outside the classroom, in educational or social protection institution.; (2) Where it is not possible to provide additional professional assistance in accordance with the preceding paragraph, additional professional assistance may also be offered to the child at home. As a rule, additional professional assistance shall be provided on a weekly basis. If professionally substantiated, additional professional assistance may also be offered in an abridged and periodical manner under conditions determined by the minister responsible for education (hereinafter: the minister).; (3) The total number of hours of additional professional assistance shall not exceed five hours per week, of which at least one hour of counselling services shall be provided. For blind and partially sighted children or children with multiple disorders as referred to in Article 2 of this Act, a greater number of hours for overcoming deficiencies may be determined, but for no more than three hours more per week, as a rule during the first educational period.; (4) The scope and manner of providing additional professional assistance shall be determined by a special educational needs guidance decision pursuant to the rules adopted by the minister, while the manner of providing additional assistance shall be defined in detail by the individualised education programme (hereinafter: individualised programme).;

(5) Pre-school children shall be entitled to the counselling service as additional professional assistance prior to the institution of the placement procedure, up to a maximum of two hours per month on a doctor's proposal. In article 10 (Material conditions and physical assistance) it is singled out: (1) The premises and devices for children with special needs who have been placed in programmes for pre-school children and education programmes with adapted implementation and additional professional assistance, or in adapted programmes and a special programme for children with moderate, severe and profound intellectual impairment, must be adapted in accordance with the instructions for the adapted implementation of the programmes and in accordance with the adapted programmes adopted or determined by the competent council of experts.; (2) The devices indispensable for the inclusion of children with special needs in an education programme shall be provided by the founder of the public institution if not provided on the basis of other regulations, and if for objective reasons the child is unable to use one and the same device both at home and in the educational institution. Children with motor disabilities are entitled to special aids in accordance with the regulations governing health insurance; devices that are intended for use in children's domestic environment are not required to be brought to the educational institution (balls, rollers, stools, stands) on a daily basis.; (3) A permanent or temporary attendant for the provision of physical assistance during schooling may be granted to children who have severe and profound impairments in motor skills and to blind children who have been placed in education programmes with adapted implementation and additional professional assistance.; (4) Children with a long-term illness, partially sighted children or children with visual impairment, children with autistic disorders and children with emotional and behavioural disorders may exceptionally be granted a temporary attendant on the basis of the criteria determined by the minister.

Integration of migrant children into the Slovenian education system

The **Strategy** (2007) states that as specified by educational law children of foreign citizens residing in the Republic of Slovenia are entitled to integration into the basic or upper secondary school under the same conditions as children of Slovenian citizens. Citizens of other EU member states, Slovenian nationals without Slovenian citizenship and refugees can pursue education under the same conditions as Slovenian citizens, while such rights of other foreign citizens are based on the principle of reciprocity (on the basis of international treaties the minister responsible for education allocates the number of vacancies for such upper secondary students). The Kindergarten Act does not refer to children of foreign citizens particularly, however, it states explicitly that pre-school education is based on the principle of equal opportunities for both children and parents with due consideration of diversity among children and their right of choice and right to be different.

Alongside the focus on newly-arrived migrant children, the Guidelines (2012) further specify that: "the Guidelines advocate the inclusive approach to integration of migrant children, basic school and upper secondary students or second and

third generation migrant children whose parents moved from abroad at the time of their integration into the education system, and give an incentive to setting up conditions for successful learning for all participants regardless of differences in their psycho-physical abilities, language, their family's socio-economic status, if any, as so forth".

The Ministry of Education, Science and Sport has been funding Slovenian language learning support lessons at basic schools with migrant children attending school in Slovenia, namely first and second year of their inclusion.

In 2008, a provision was included in the Rules on knowledge assessment and grading and pupils' progression in basic schools, warranting the possibility for an adapted assessment of migrant students. As by the Rules, the assessment methods and times, number of marks and so forth may be adapted to migrant students who are foreign nationals or persons without citizenship residing in the Republic of Slovenia, namely in agreement with their parents. The knowledge of migrant student may be assessed as to the student's progress in achieving educational goals and knowledge standards as specified by the subject-curricula. The teacher's assembly decides on the adjustments. The adapted assessment applies for up to two school years only. At the end of the first school year the migrant students attended basic school in the Republic of Slovenia, they may progress even if they failed to receive a pass mark in separate subjects. At the recommendation of the form teacher, the teacher's assembly decides on the progression.

The Constitution of the Republic of Slovenia sets out the equal rights and opportunities in education for all irrespective of their race, gender, nationality, social or cultural background, religion, political and other convictions, education, social status, disability, or any other personal circumstances. The the White Paper (1996) lists "equal opportunities and non-discrimination" under principles of the public education system. The core principles, the foundation of the public system of education, of the White Paper (2011) include fairness and the provision of equal education opportunities in the scope of this principle. Moreover, one adopted several relevant regulations on education, healthcare, elimination of barriers and obstacles in the setting, social and financial aid, employment, and social inclusion. The national and development programmes include solutions relevant to the equal opportunities. The Protection against discrimination Act makes additional provision for equal opportunities. The dimension of equal opportunities is specified exhaustively for the educational process of children with special educational needs.

The provision of education for children and young people with special educational needs (SEN) is public service; in special circumstances, it may be in private settings without concession or a private institute, and in the form of home schooling. All sector-specific laws make allowance for the education of the SEN students. The law is completed by:

- ◆ Act Regulating the Integrated Early Treatment of Preschool Children with Special Needs;
- ◆ Placement of Children with Special Needs Act;
- ◆ Act on the Intervention for Children and Youth with Emotional and

Behavioral disorders in Education.

Those documents represent an important step towards realizing the inclusive paradigm. They set out conditions of continuous support to children with special educational needs.

The Act on special rights of members of the Italian and Hungarian national communities in education specifies the relevant special rights. The members of the Roma community have their special rights set out in the Roma community in the Republic of Slovenia Act. The common legislation in education lays down the rights of disadvantaged or vulnerable students, as well. The regulations all attention to the talented students, migrant students whose first language is not Slovenian, and students with learning difficulties.

Educational policy outlook

The Childminding of Preschool Children Programme (2008, amended in 2012) provides special grants for parents whose children did not get a spot in public kindergartens. The grant amounts to 20% of the cost of the programme in the kindergarten where they would have been enrolled.

To make student work less attractive to employers, the Act on Occasional Student Work (2014) was incorporated into the Public Finance Balance Act. It introduced a minimum hourly wage and social security contributions for student work, while allowing student contracts to remain the cheapest form of employment for employers.

In 2012, a new Regulation on the Methodology of Financing Educational Programmes for Upper Secondary Schools was adopted. Under this regulation, all upper secondary schools as well as all residence halls for upper secondary students switched to a per-student funding formula and block grant financing.

Support Measures for Learners in Early Childhood and School Education

All kindergartens and schools have internal counselling services. School counsellors are psychologists, social pedagogues, education specialists and social workers. The main purpose of a counselling service is to take part in complex solving of educational, psychological and social difficulties of children in kindergarten or schools by assisting and cooperating with all participants of the education process, the parents and, if necessary, with relevant external institutions. It offers assistance to individuals and groups in kindergartens or schools in order to ensure optimal development of all children, regardless of their personal circumstances or the social-economic or cultural situation.

Definition of the Target Group(s)

The rules specify groups of children, pupils and students eligible for assistance

or special measures in view of their personal, socio-economic or cultural circumstances:

- ◆ Members of the Italian and Hungarian national communities have the right to education in their mother tongue and provision of education in ethnically mixed areas. Rights are specified in detail by the Act Regulating the Exercise of the Special Rights of Members of the Italian and Hungarian Ethnic Communities in the Field of Education.
- ◆ Members of the Roma community are specified as a special group with special rights defined by the Constitution of the Republic of Slovenia. The exercise of special rights is specified by the Roma Community Act and, in education, by the Kindergarten Act and Basic School Act.
- ◆ Migrants (foreign nationals): the rights of children of foreign nationals are specified in detail by the Kindergarten Act, Basic School Act, Gimnazije Act and Vocational Education Act; the Asylum Act specifies the right to education of refugees and asylum seekers;
- ◆ Talented pupils or students: as specified by the Basic School Act, Gimnazije Act and VET Act, the provision of instruction to talented children or pupils may be adapted to their needs; the Basic School Act specifies that pupils who show high and above average levels of thinking skills or achieve exceptional results in separate learning fields, arts or sports are defined as talented pupils.
- ◆ Pupils with learning problems: provisions of the Basic School Act specify the right these children have to an adapted instruction; without adapted methods and forms of class work, these pupils struggle to attain standards of knowledge.

As specified by Kindergarten Act and Basic School Act, children in hospital care may have pre-school and basic school education organized in the hospital;

In the scope of the education objectives specified by the Organization and Financing of Education Act, children from less favourable social and economic environments may receive support and assistance by kindergartens or schools.

National reforms

In December 2017, the Government of the Republic of Slovenia adopted the Slovenian Development Strategy 2030, It is the new long-term national development framework. Its primary objective is to ensure quality of life for all ("Slovenia, a country with high quality of life for all"). Future development of Slovenia rests on five strategic guidelines and twelve related goals. The strategy rests on the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development by the United Nations as well, and so Slovenia attached the significance to sustainable and inclusive future in which the society as a whole can flourish.

At the end of 2019, the Government adopted the National Strategy for the Development of Reading Literacy for the period 2019–2030. Its strategic objectives are to establish an effective social framework for the development of reading literacy, to develop the reading literacy of individuals who have different roles, needs and requirements at different stages of life, thus enabling the continuous development of society and the economy, to increase access to books and other reading material, and to pay greater attention to specific age/target groups within the education system. An Action Plan is foreseen for adoption in the first half of 2022, addressing a number of actions to improve the situation.

In November 2020, the Government of the Republic of Slovenia approved the Programme for children 2020-2025. The programme seeks to improve the well-being of children, create equal opportunities and rights for all children, provide better protection and safety, as well as the foster inclusion and participation of children.

Social welfare

In the **Social security act** it is pointed out that: activities of social assistance shall include preventing and solving social problems of individual persons, families and population groups (article 1); the state cares for preventing the social deprivation in particular with the systematic measures in the field of taxation policy, employment and work, policy of granting scholarships, housing policy, family policy, health care, children's care and education, and in other fields of influence upon the social situation of inhabitants, as well as upon the development of demographically endangered areas (article 9); Help to the family under this Act shall imply help for home, help at home and social service; professional counselling and help at re-establishing relations among family members, at taking care of children and educating the family to implement its role in everyday life; social care of the entitled persons in case of disability, old age and other cases where social care at home can replace institutional care; Social service shall include help at domestic and other chores in case of childbirth, illness, disability, old age, in cases of accidents and other cases where such help is necessary to include persons in everyday life (article 15).

In the **Rules on the co-financing of social assistance programmes**, article 2 ((areas of social protection programs) it is pointed out that social protection programs are intended to prevent and solve social hardships of individual vulnerable groups in the following areas: 1. violence prevention, assistance programs for victims of violence and programs for work with perpetrators of violence, 2. addiction (illicit drugs, alcoholism, eating disorders, gambling and other forms of addiction), 3. mental health, 4. homelessness, reducing the risk of poverty, tackling the effects of poverty, 5. children and adolescents who are deprived of a decent family life and adolescents with difficulties growing up, 6. Elderly people at risk of social exclusion or need support and assistance in their daily lives, including assistance and support programs for people with dementia and their relatives, 7. support stay for people with disabilities and a network of other programs for the organization and promotion of independent living of people with disabilities, 8. psychosocial

assistance to children, adolescents, adults and families, 9. social inclusion of Roma, 10. specialist support to victims of crime (if not provided by other social protection programs), 11. other areas aimed at tackling social hardship (promoting the development of volunteering, assisting applicants for international protection, refugees, economic migrants and their family members, former prisoners, evictees, support for the dying and their relatives and mourners, victims of abuse and trafficking in human beings, victims of traffic accidents, etc.).

In the **Rules on standards and norms for social assistance services**, article 1, it is stated that these rules set standards and norms for the following social protection services (hereinafter: services): 1. social assistance 2. personal assistance 3. support to victims of crime 4. assistance to the family at home and at home 5. institutional care 6. management, protection and employment under special conditions.

National reforms

The strategic document for the development of the country's social protection system is the Resolution on the national social assistance programme 2022-2030, adopted by the National Assembly on 23 March 2022. The key objectives pursued by the Resolution are to reduce the risk of poverty and increase social inclusion, to improve the accessibility and availability of services and programmes, to strengthen community-based forms of social protection, and to create a supportive environment/conditions for improving the quality of services and programmes. In defining actions, the Resolution follows the European Pillar of Social Rights Action Plan for the period until 2030.

The adoption of an amendment to the Housing Act in 2021, which will improve the conditions for faster construction of public rental housing, will further contribute to reducing the number of people at risk of poverty and social exclusion. The amendment to the Housing Act establishes the legal basis for the introduction of a realistic level of non-profit rent, which will allow for the adequate maintenance of public rental housing and the gradual expansion of the stock of public rental housing. In parallel with the increase in non-profit rents, the rent subsidy system is being adapted to protect the socially vulnerable in the event of a rise in non-profit rents. The subsidy is increased to a maximum of 85% of the non-profit rent, which ensures that the most socially vulnerable are not affected by the rent increase. The amended Act also allows for higher borrowing by housing funds, up to 50% of the value of the fund's earmarked assets, and a pre-emptive right for the Housing Fund in the sale of building municipal land earmarked for multi-family housing. A public rental service has also been established within the Housing Fund, with the aim of activating the existing but unoccupied housing stock.

Youth work

Personal assistance act regulates the right to personal assistance and the manner of its exercise, in order to enable an individual with long-term physical, mental, intellectual or sensory impairment, which in connection with various obstacles may be limited to Like others, fully and effectively participate in society (hereinafter:

the user) in all areas of life equal opportunities, greater independence, activity and equal inclusion in society, in accordance with the provisions of the **Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities** (article 1). Further, the state is obliged to: plan the development of personal assistance and develop the activity, coordinate it with other areas of social security and adopt appropriate legal bases; to provide conditions and possibilities for equal accessibility, efficiency and rational organization of personal assistance services in the territory of the Republic of Slovenia; provide conditions for education and training; provide funding for the procedure for exercising the right to personal assistance and the provision of personal assistance (article 4).

Public Interest in **Youth Sector Act** and **Youth Council Act** are acts that protect young people and young workers. This law are based on the principles of democracy, plurality, integrity, intergenerational solidarity, equality, non-discrimination and justice, multiculturalism, intercultural dialogue, volunteering, promotion of healthy lifestyles, respect for life and the environment and participation of non-governmental organizations in public affairs.

Protection against discrimination act (ZVarD) shall determine the protection of all persons (hereinafter: person) against discrimination irrespective of their gender, nationality, racial or ethnic origin, language, religion or belief, disability, age, sexual orientation, gender identity or gender expression, social status, property status, education, or any other personal circumstance (hereinafter: personal circumstance) in various fields of social life, when enforcing human rights and fundamental freedoms, exercising rights and obligations and in other legal relationships in political, economic, social, cultural, civil or other fields. This Act shall establish the Advocate of the Principle of Equality (hereinafter: Advocate), as an independent state authority in the field of protection against discrimination, including the Advocate's tasks and powers. Protection against discrimination shall also apply to legal entities defined by the legal order of the Republic of Slovenia if the nature of the circumstances which could be the basis for discrimination refers to such persons. This Act shall define and prohibit discrimination, appoint authorities and determine measures for promoting equal treatment, determine the status and competences of the Advocate, the Advocate's procedure when establishing the existence of discrimination and particularities of legal protection of persons subject to discrimination.

To date, no specific national strategy or programme for youth social inclusion has been adopted in Slovenia. The **National Programme for Youth in Slovenia** (2013) identified key policies and guidelines, including the need to devote special attention to risk factors for poverty and social exclusion among young people. Its other guidelines refer to improving social inclusion of young people with fewer opportunities, the principle of equal opportunities for men and women and the prevention of discrimination, with particular attention to victims of social exclusion (e.g. Roma people, disabled persons).

In November 2015, the National Assembly of the Republic of Slovenia adopted the **Resolution on the National Programme for Equal Opportunities for Women and Men 2015-2020**.

The Ministry of Labour, Family, Social Affairs and Equal Opportunities has proposed two Acts highlighting measures to facilitate youth social inclusion in 2016. **The Amendment on changes and completion of the Social Security Act** that was adopted in 20 December 2016 and The Rules on co-financing social assistance programmes that came into force on 12 November 2016. On 19 April 2018, another Amendment on changes and completion of the Social Security Act was adopted.

National reforms

The epidemic crisis has shown the importance of ensuring more flexible ways of organizing work. The Recovery and Resilience Plan also foresees important measures in this area, such as the establishment of direct support for workers and employers to use more flexible working arrangements in 2022. The Support to more flexible work arrangements project aims to enable greater resilience and labour market inclusion, promote better reconciliation of work and private life, strengthen digital competences of employees (with a focus on older workers) and raise occupational safety and health standards in this area. The project Introducing more flexible work arrangements adapted to the needs of people with disabilities in disability enterprises and employment centres will be implemented to maintain and create new jobs suitable for the most severely disabled workers.

Activation of the unemployed and measures to help the most vulnerable groups to enter the labour market remain a key focus for Slovenia. In this light, in January 2021, the Government adopted the Guidelines for Active Employment Policy 2021–2025, which are a strategic document in this area and provide a framework for the implementation of active employment policy measures over the next five-year period. The main objectives of the document are to reduce the number of long-term unemployed, to accelerate the activation of the unemployed, especially the over-50s, the low-educated and recipients of social assistance, to accelerate the transition of unemployed young people up to 29 years of age to the labour market – the Youth Guarantee, and to address structural imbalances in the labour market, in order to provide the skills needed to meet the labour market needs.

Slovenia pays particular attention to young people in its labour market policies. For example, the Recovery and Resilience Plan foresees the project Faster entry of young people into the labour market (2022–2024), which aims to accelerate the activation of young people up to and including 25 years of age by means of subsidies for permanent employment (at least 4,000 jobs). The project addresses the key challenges young people face in their transition to the labour market. By providing work experience, compulsory training during subsidised employment and promoting permanent employment, it also strengthens the long-term resilience of young workers to economic fluctuations in the face of crises. The measure will encourage young people to take up supplementary pension insurance.

**diversity
revolution**
FROM VALUE TO PRACTICE

